

**Österreichische
UNESCO-Kommission**
Jahrbuch 2021

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Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission

Jahrbuch 2021

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Österreichische
UNESCO-Kommission
Austrian Commission
for UNESCO

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Mag.ª Patrizia Jankovic, Generalsekretärin

Ähnlich wie das Vorjahr, war auch das Jahr 2021 noch deutlich von pandemiebedingten Einschränkungen geprägt – etliche Veranstaltungen konnten weiterhin „nur“ digital stattfinden, und das Arbeiten im „remote mode“ wurde endgültig zur Normalität. Nichtsdestotrotz kann die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission auf ein erfolgreiches Jahr zurückblicken. Die Beiträge auf den folgenden Seiten zeigen die vielfältigen Aktivitäten auf:

Die Präsentation des Weltbildungsberichts „Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses?“ fand abermals internationale Aufmerksamkeit und spannte den Bogen zwischen dem Globalen Süden und dem Globalen Norden. Die UNESCO-Schuljahrestagung bot ein vielseitiges Programm zum Generalthema „Futures of Education“, und die neue Initiative der ÖUK, bei der Schulen unterschiedliche Workshops zu den 17 Zielen für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung angeboten bekommen, fand großen Anklang bei Schüler*innen und Lehrpersonen.

Im Rahmen der ‚For Women in Science‘-Initiative wurden auch dieses Jahr vier herausragende Grundlagenforscherinnen mit einem UNESCO-L’Oréal Österreich Stipendium ausgezeichnet. Außerdem ist für den Bereich Wissenschaft die Einrichtung des „UNESCO-Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Future Design“ an der Kunstuniversität Linz hervorzuheben.

Im Kulturbereich setzte die Kontaktstelle Kulturelle Vielfalt mit der Veranstaltungsreihe „Forum Fair Culture“ einen neuen Themenschwerpunkt zur Frage der Vorzugsbehandlung im (post-)migrantischen Österreich sowie Anti-Diskriminierung in der (internationalen) Kulturpolitik.

Am 18. April 2021 wurde der erste österreichische Welt-erbetag begangen, der als gemeinsamer Aktionstag der Österreichischen Welterbestätten auf die außergewöhnlichen universellen Werte des Welterbes in Österreich und weltweit aufmerksam macht.

Außerdem sind, auf internationaler Ebene, die erfolgreiche Einschreibung der „Great Spa Towns of Europe“ mit Baden bei Wien sowie der positive Abschluss des langjährige Nominierungsprozesses des „Donaulimes“ zu berichten. Für das Immaterielle Kulturerbe stand das Jahr 2021 u.a. im Zeichen der Traditionellen Bewässerung. Ausgehend von der Tiroler Rieselbewässerung wurde unter der Federführung Österreichs eine multinationale Einreichung für die Repräsentative Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes vorbereitet.

Diese Erfolge sind nur durch die gute Zusammenarbeit aller erreichbar – besonders bedanken möchte ich mich bei allen Mitarbeiter*innen, bei ÖUK-Präsidium und -Vorstand für ihr Engagement und ihren unermüdlichen Einsatz sowie bei jenen Bundesministerien, die uns seit langem unterstützen.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Patrizia Jankovic". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Mag.ª Patrizia Jankovic

Dr.ⁱⁿ Sabine Haag, Präsidentin

Die UNESCO ist heute als Forum der globalen intellektuellen Zusammenarbeit wichtiger denn je. Nicht zuletzt die Covid-19-Pandemie hat deutlich gemacht, dass den Herausforderungen unserer Zeit nur kooperativ und multilateral begegnet werden kann.

Die Arbeit der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission richtet sich einerseits daran aus, die Ziele der UNESCO in Österreich zu implementieren. Andererseits arbeiten wir – gemeinsam mit den zuständigen Ressorts – auch an der Verankerung österreichischer Positionen, Anliegen und Projekte innerhalb der UNESCO mit.

Alle zwei Jahre versammeln sich die Mitgliedsstaaten im Rahmen der Generalkonferenz, dem obersten Entscheidungs- und Kontrollorgan der UNESCO. Auch 2021 war Österreich durch Vertreter*innen der zuständigen Ressorts, der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission sowie Expert*innen aus Kunst, Kultur, Bildung und Wissenschaft im November in Paris vertreten. Wir sind besonders stolz darauf, dass Österreich im Rahmen der 41. UNESCO-Generalkonferenz zum vierten Mal in den UNESCO-Exekutivrat, das wichtigste Steuerungsgremium der Institution, gewählt wurde.

Österreich ist aber nicht nur dort, sondern auch in zahlreichen weiteren UNESCO-Lenkungsausschüssen und -Komitees vertreten, so aktuell u.a. im Internationalen Koordinierungsrat des UNESCO-Programms „Der Mensch und die Biosphäre“ (MAB), dem Zwischenstaatlichen Rat des „Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme“ (IHP) oder dem Zwischenstaatlichen Komitee für den Schutz und die Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen – um nur einige aufzuzählen. Den genannten ist gemeinsam, dass

die ÖUK wesentlich zur Koordinierung der nationalen Expertise beiträgt und so die inhaltliche Diskussion auf fachlich fundierte Beine stellt. Gleichzeitig bringt die Mitwirkung österreichischer Expert*innen an internationalen Programmen geradezu zwangsläufig auch eine Internationalisierung der österreichischen Debatten mit sich. Exemplarisch für eine solche wechselseitige Befruchtung berichtet in diesem Jahrbuch Dr. Günter Köck über seine langjährige Tätigkeit für das MAB-Programm.

Die Zusammenarbeit mit Dr. Köck und der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften ist nur ein Beispiel unter vielen, wie sich die ÖUK in ihren Tätigkeiten auf Fachwissen aus Wissenschaft, Kunst, Kultur und Bildung stützt. In derzeit sechs Fachgremien beraten, informieren und evaluieren angesehene Expert*innen die ÖUK hinsichtlich der Umsetzung der Ziele der UNESCO in Österreich. Für die stets gewinnbringende Zusammenarbeit und die vielen fruchtbaren Diskussionen möchte ich mich an dieser Stelle sehr bedanken!

Wir danken außerdem allen Partnerorganisationen und Förderer*innen, insbesondere aus den zuständigen Bundesministerien, herzlich für ihre Unterstützung und Wegbegleitung!

Dr.ⁱⁿ Sabine Haag

Open Science & Künstliche Intelligenz – zwei zukunftsweisende UNESCO-Empfehlungen

Im November 2021 verabschiedete die Generalkonferenz der UNESCO auf ihrer 41. Sitzung eine Empfehlung zu Open Science sowie eine vielbeachtete Empfehlung zur Ethik der Künstlichen Intelligenz (KI). Dr. Stefan Hanslik, Leiter des Referats „Technische Wissenschaften“ im Bundesministerium für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung, zeigt die Bedeutung beider UNESCO-Instrumente für die Entwicklung entsprechender Maßnahmen und Politiken in Österreich auf und stellt die aktuelle österreichische Position vor.

UNESCO-Empfehlung zu Open Science – Ein weiterer Schritt in die richtige Richtung

Die Vision von Open Science ist es, wissenschaftliche Prozesse offener und effektiver zu gestalten und sowohl wissenschaftliche Exzellenz als auch innovative und angewandte Forschung zu nutzen, um aktuelle und zukünftige gesellschaftliche, sozioökonomische oder ökologische Herausforderungen anzugehen. Open Science ist ein wichtiges Instrument, um bedeutende Erfolge bei der Bewältigung gegenwärtiger und zukünftiger gesellschaftlicher Herausforderungen zu erzielen. Mit der Vorbereitung eines internationalen standardsetzenden Instruments in Form einer Empfehlung zu Open Science unternahm die UNESCO einen entscheidenden Schritt, um die vielschichtige globale Bewegung von Open Science zum Nutzen aller zu lenken und zu steuern. Zusammen mit den Zielen der EU im Bereich der Forschungs- und Datenpolitik bildete diese Empfehlung die Grundlage für die Entwicklung einer österreichischen Politik (im Sinne einer gemeinsamen Ausrichtung) zu Open Science und der European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Die Entwicklung einer offenen, transparenten und inklusiven Wissenschaft und die Förderung eines fairen Umgangs mit Forschungsprozessen und deren Ergebnissen hat für Österreich Priorität. So wurde Open Science in Form eines klaren Bekenntnisses

zu „Horizon Europe“ und der aktiven Mitarbeit Österreichs im Europäischen Forschungsraum (ERA) auch in die Strategie der Bundesregierung für Forschung, Technologie und Innovation (FTI-Strategie 2030) aufgenommen.

In der Folge wurde intensiv an der Entwicklung einer österreichischen Policy zu Open Science und der European Open Science Cloud gearbeitet. An diesem Prozess waren, neben dem Bundesministerium für Bildung,

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Wissenschaft und Forschung (BMBWF) auch das Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Energie, Mobilität, Innovation und Technologie (BMK) sowie das Bundesministerium für Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort (BMDW) beteiligt. Im Zuge dieser Entwicklung zeigt sich die hohe Relevanz einer proaktiven Beteiligung am Umsetzungsprozess der European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), einem World Wide Web für FAIRe Forschungsdaten und -dienste, um Forschungsdaten möglichst frei, zugänglich und so offen wie möglich zu halten.

Rechtzeitig und korrespondierend zu den UNESCO-Aktivitäten wurde im Februar 2022 die Open Science Policy Austria im Rahmen eines gemeinsamen Ministerratsvortrages von BMBWF, BMDW und BMK als für die Open-Science-Bewegung führend zuständigen österreichischen Ministerien verabschiedet: Durch die Umsetzung der UNESCO-Empfehlung zu Open Science in Österreich wird die Entwicklung eines offenen, transparenten und inklusiven Wissenschaftsumfelds und damit der faire Umgang mit Forschungsprozessen und deren Ergebnissen auf nationaler Ebene gefördert.

Empfehlung zur Ethik der Künstlichen Intelligenz – Eine wichtige Voraussetzung für den Umgang mit KI

Diese UNESCO-Empfehlung ist eine wichtige Voraussetzung für den Umgang mit Künstlicher Intelligenz in einem globalen Kontext, da rasante technologische Entwicklungen wie das Aufkommen der Künstlichen Intelligenz (KI) unsere Gesellschaften bereits heute tiefgreifend beeinflussen. Die Frage, welche Fähigkeiten und Rahmenbedingungen die menschliche Welt entwickeln muss, um sich in einer zunehmend automatisierten Welt friedlich weiterzuentwickeln, wird also ohne Zweifel enorm an Bedeutung gewinnen.

In Wissensgesellschaften kann Künstliche Intelligenz beispielsweise im

Lehren und Lernen eingesetzt werden, um interaktives und personalisiertes Lernen zu fördern, und trägt so zur Steigerung der Qualität des Lehrens, Lernens und der Vielfalt der Lehrmethoden bei. KI muss und wird beispielsweise Teil der Aus- und Weiterbildung im MINT-Bereich sowie in der Lehrer*innenausbildung sein, um eine hohe Qualität der State-of-the-Art-Ausbildung zu gewährleisten.

Durch die Umsetzung der UNESCO-Empfehlung zu Open Science in Österreich wird die Entwicklung eines offenen, transparenten und inklusiven Wissenschaftsumfelds und damit der faire Umgang mit Forschungsprozessen und deren Ergebnissen auf nationaler Ebene gefördert.

Künstliche Intelligenz kann für marginalisierte Gruppen wie Kinder, Jugendliche und Erwachsene, die in ländlichen oder Krisengebieten leben, sowie für Menschen mit Behinderungen von großem Nutzen sein, sofern sie Zugang zu neuen Technologien haben. Die Gewährung eines solchen Zugangs und Schritte zur Beseitigung der digitalen Kluft sind eine wesentliche Voraussetzung.

Da KI-Technologien nicht neutral sind und KI derzeit blind für die Folgen ihrer Anwendung ist, befürwortet Österreich nachdrücklich das UNESCO-Engagement für Künstliche Intelligenz, insbesondere mit dem Fokus auf deren ethische Dimension. „Responsible Science“ als Konzept zur Zusammenführung von wissenschaftlicher Exzellenz und gesellschaftlicher Relevanz kann einen wesentlichen Beitrag zur Sensibilisierung für potenzielle Herausforderungen und Risiken im Rahmen dieser neuen Technologie leisten.

Die menschliche Analyse sowie die strenge Kontrolle von KI-basierten

Entscheidungen müssen gewährleistet sein – KI kann und darf die natürliche Intelligenz nicht ersetzen, sondern muss den Menschen in bestimmten Bereichen und mit Fachwissen sowie unter menschlicher Aufsicht dienen. Nicht zuletzt daher müssen wir die Menschen stärker in den Prozess der Entwicklung von KI und die Rahmenbedingungen einbeziehen, unabhängig von Geschlecht, Abstammung, Weltanschauung, Alter, sexueller Orientierung oder besonderen Bedürfnissen.

Nur ein auf Menschenrechten, Ethik und wissenschaftlicher Integrität basierender Ansatz kann einen Rahmen bieten, der sowohl den erfolgreichen Einsatz künstlicher Intelligenz als auch den Schutz der Persönlichkeitsrechte und -bedürfnisse jedes Einzelnen sowie die Wahrung von Fairness und Transparenz in allen gesellschaftlichen Bereichen ermöglicht.

Zusammenfassend ist es für Österreich von sehr hoher Relevanz, an einem nationalen KI-Rahmenwerk zu arbeiten sowie sich auf ein internationales standardsetzendes Instrument zur Ethik der künstlichen Intelligenz zu verständigen, wie es von der UNESCO verabschiedet wurde.

DR. STEFAN HANSLIK promovierte in Biologie/ Genetik. Er leitet das Referat „Technische Wissenschaften“ im Bundesministerium für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung. Er vertritt Österreich in zahlreichen internationalen Gremien, u.a. in verschiedenen HORIZON Europe Programm-Komitees, in der OECD-Arbeitsgruppe zu Biotechnologie oder dem Council der European Synchrotron Radiation Facility.

BILDUNG

Mit der Verabschiedung der Agenda 2030 für nachhaltige Entwicklung hat die internationale Staatengemeinschaft die zentrale Rolle der Bildung für die Umsetzung der darin enthaltenen 17 Nachhaltigkeitsziele hervorgehoben. Bildung ist der Schlüssel, um Nachhaltigkeit weltweit in den Bildungssystemen zu verankern und die Umsetzung der 17 SDGs voranzutreiben.

UNESCO-BILDUNGSPROGRAMME

Auf dem Weg zu einer gerechten Welt für alle

Um eine friedliche, gerechte und nachhaltige Zukunft zu gestalten, muss die Bildung selbst verändert werden.

– so lautet die Forderung des globalen Berichts der *International Commission on the Futures of Education*: „Reimagining our futures together: a new social contract for education“. Der Bericht stellt die Frage, welche Rolle die Bildung bei der Gestaltung unserer Welt und unserer gemeinsamen Zukunft mit Blick auf das Jahr 2050 und darüber hinaus spielen kann. Die vorgelegten Vorschläge sind Ergebnis eines zweijährigen globalen Prozesses des Engagements und der Zusammenarbeit. Er widmet sich Themen wie der Neugestaltung von Lernräumen, der Entkolonialisierung von Lehrplänen und der Bedeutung von sozialem und emotionalem Lernen und greift reale und wachsende Ängste vor dem Klimawandel, vor Krisen wie COVID-19, Fake News und der digitalen Kluft auf. Bildung – die Art und Weise, wie wir das Lehren und Lernen während des gesamten Lebens organisieren – spielt eine grundlegende Rolle bei der Gestaltung der menschlichen Gesellschaften. Sie verbindet uns mit der Welt und miteinander, zeigt uns neue Möglichkeiten auf und stärkt unsere Fähigkeiten zum Dialog und zum Handeln.

Bildungsagenda – No one shall be left behind

Während die Ausweitung der Bildungssysteme vielen Menschen neue Möglichkeiten eröffnet hat, ist die Qualität der Bildung für eine große Zahl von Menschen mangelhaft. Die Art und Weise, wie Bildung weltweit organisiert wird, reicht derzeit nicht aus, um gerechte und friedliche Gesellschaften, einen gesunden Planeten und einen gemeinsamen Fortschritt zu gewährleisten, der allen zugutekommt. Tatsächlich sind einige Schwierigkeiten auf die Art und Weise zurückzuführen, wie Bildung vermittelt wird. Einerseits müssen die enormen Transformationspotenziale von digitalen Technologien genutzt werden, andererseits muss die aktivere Bürger*innenbeteiligung und der aufkommende Aktivismus, der gegen Diskriminierung und Ungerechtigkeit vorgeht, in das Bildungsgeschehen integriert werden, um Bildung als öffentliches Anliegen und Gemeinwohl zu stärken.

Bildung und die SDGs

Die globale Bildungsagenda 2030 leitet sich aus der Agenda 2030 ab, die im September 2015 von den Vereinten Nationen verabschiedet wurde. Bildung spielt eine zentrale Rolle für die erfolgreiche Umsetzung aller 17 Entwicklungsziele. Darüber hinaus ist der Bildung ein eigenständiges Ziel gewidmet, das lautet: „Bis 2030 für alle Menschen inklusive, chancengerechte und hochwertige Bildung sicherstellen sowie Möglichkeiten zum lebenslangen Lernen fördern“. Die UNESCO hat als einzige Sonderorganisation der Vereinten Nationen das Mandat, alle Aspekte der Bildung abzudecken und ist federführend in der weltweiten Umsetzung der Bildungsziele.

SGD 4: Bildungsziele

Bis 2030 für alle Menschen inklusive, chancengerechte und hochwertige Bildung sicherstellen sowie Möglichkeiten zum lebenslangen Lernen fördern.

4.1. Bis 2030 allen Mädchen und Buben den Abschluss einer kostenlosen, chancengerechten und hochwertigen Primar- und Sekundarschulbildung ermöglichen, die zu relevanten und effektiven Lernergebnissen führt.

4.2. Bis 2030 allen Mädchen und Buben den Zugang zu hochwertiger frühkindlicher Bildung, Betreuung und Erziehung sichern, die ihnen einen erfolgreichen Übergang in die Schule ermöglichen.

4.3. Bis 2030 allen Frauen und Männern einen gleichberechtigten und leistbaren Zugang zu hochwertiger beruflicher und akademischer Bildung ermöglichen.

4.4. Bis 2030 sicherstellen, dass eine deutlich höhere Anzahl an Jugendlichen und Erwachsenen die für eine Beschäftigung oder Selbstständigkeit relevanten Kenntnisse, Fähigkeiten und Fertigkeiten erwirbt.

4.5. Bis 2030 Benachteiligungen aufgrund der Geschlechtszugehörigkeit auf allen Bildungsstufen beseitigen und allen Menschen gleichberechtigten Zugang zu allen Bildungsstufen sichern, einschließlich Menschen mit Behinderung, indigenen Völkern und benachteiligten Kindern.

4.6. Bis 2030 den Erwerb ausreichender Lese-, Schreib- und Rechenfähigkeiten für alle Jugendlichen und für einen erheblichen Anteil der Erwachsenen sicherstellen.

4.7. Bis 2030 sicherstellen, dass alle Lernenden die für nachhaltige Entwicklung notwendigen Kenntnisse und Fähigkeiten erwerben, u.a. durch Bildung für nachhaltige Entwicklung, für nachhaltige Lebensweise, für Menschenrechte, für Gleichberechtigung der Geschlechter, durch Förderung einer Kultur des Friedens und der Gewaltfreiheit, durch Global Citizenship Education und Wertschätzung kultureller Vielfalt und durch den Beitrag der Kultur zu nachhaltiger Entwicklung.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

In der nationalen Umsetzung der internationalen Bildungsprogramme hat die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission eine unterstützende und beratende Funktion für die unterschiedlichen Akteur*innen. Dabei orientiert sie sich an den jeweils aktuellen Arbeitsschwerpunkten der UNESCO und insbesondere an der globalen Bildungsagenda 2030.

• Präsentation des UNESCO-Weltbildungsberichts 2021

Der Report dient unter anderem dazu die Umsetzung der Bildungsagenda 2030 zu überwachen, zu dokumentieren und zu analysieren und Empfehlungen zur besseren Umsetzung zu formulieren. Der Bericht 2021/2022 trägt den Titel „Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses?“ und wurde im Dezember 2021 veröffentlicht. Hierin fordert die UNESCO bessere Aufsicht über private Bildungseinrichtungen, um Ungleichheiten zu verringern, fordert die Mitgliedsstaaten auf, Qualitätsstandards für staatliche und nicht-staatliche Einrichtungen festzulegen, die Anstrengungen zu kostenloser Grund- und Sekundarschulbildung zu verstärken, Akteur*innen aus den verschiedensten Bildungsbereichen zusammenzuführen, staatliche Kapazitäten zur Kontrolle und Durchsetzung von Vorschriften zu stärken und vor allem Bildung vor Eigeninteressen zu schützen.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Bildung und SDGs Die Bildung steht im Mittelpunkt der Agenda 2030. Sie spielt eine zentrale Rolle für die erfolgreiche Umsetzung aller 17 Entwicklungsziele. Darüber hinaus ist der Bildung ein eigenständiges Ziel gewidmet, **SDG4**, das lautet: „Bis 2030 für alle Menschen inklusive, chancengerechte und hochwertige Bildung sicherstellen sowie Möglichkeiten zum lebenslangen Lernen fördern“.

- **Fachbeirat Transformative Bildung / Global Citizenship Education**

Der im März 2017 an der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission ins Leben gerufene Fachbeirat widmet sich dem Monitoring und der Begleitung der nationalen Umsetzung von SDG 4, im speziellen des SDG 4.7. 2021 wurde Dr. Gerhard Bisovsky, Generalsekretär des Verbandes Österreichischer Volkshochschulen, als neues Mitglied in den Fachbeirat aufgenommen.

- **Youth Representative der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission**

Um die Stimme von jungen Menschen zu stärken, schuf die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission 2019 die auf zwei Jahre ausgelegte Position der „Youth Representatives“. Diese vertreten die ÖUK-Jugendpositionen nach außen und setzen zusammen mit dem ÖUK-Sekretariat UNESCO-relevante Jugendaktivitäten um. 2021 übernahm Maria Blomenhofer dieses Ehrenamt, das sie bis Mitte 2023 ausüben wird.

- **„Turning Point“: Bildung für die SDGs**

„Turning Point: Youth for Sustainable Development“ ist eine Veranstaltungsreihe der Youth Representatives der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission. Sie bringt junge Menschen zusammen, um über dringende Fragen unserer Zeit ins Gespräch zu kommen.

Am 25. und 26. Jänner 2021 fand der Onlineworkshop „Deine Rechte – deine Welt!“ statt. Er wurde gemeinsam mit dem Projekt „Kenne deine Rechte“ organisiert und bot rund 140 jungen Menschen im Alter von 14–25 Jahren die Gelegenheit, sich zu den Themen Menschenrechte und Nachhaltigkeit auszutauschen und mehr über die komplexen Zusammenhänge von Menschenrechten und Klima- und Umweltschutz zu erfahren.

Ist Privatisierung eine Lösung oder ein Symptom?

Der Weltbildungsbericht 2021/22 mit dem Titel „Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses?“ setzt sich mit der Frage auseinander, welche Auswirkungen eine (zunehmende) Privatisierung des Bildungssektors hat. Um den Bogen zwischen dem Globalen Norden und dem Globalen Süden mit Blick auf nicht-staatliche Akteur*innen im Bildungsbereich zu spannen, erläutert Dr.ⁱⁿ Maria Ron Balsera, TaxEd Alliance Koordinatorin¹, anhand einer Studie, durchgeführt in Ghana, Kenia und Uganda, die Situation und die Herausforderungen vor Ort.

Im Jahr 2015 verpflichteten sich Staaten auf der ganzen Welt, „eine integrative und gerechte hochwertige Bildung zu gewährleisten und Möglichkeiten des lebenslangen Lernens für alle zu fördern“ – Das Leitprinzip der Agenda 2030 für nachhaltige Entwicklung lautet: „leave no one behind“. Die Auswirkungen von COVID-19 drohen die erzielten Fortschritte zunichtemachen, was dazu führen wird, dass Hunderte Millionen Menschen in extreme Armut zurückfallen und die Umsetzung der Agenda 2030 immer weiter zurückbleibt. Die (finanziellen) Auswirkungen der COVID-19-Pandemie, in Kombination mit jahrelangen Sparmaßnahmen, haben zu einer verheerenden Krise der staatlichen Finanzierung im Bildungsbereich geführt.

Viele Stimmen drängen auf eine engere Zusammenarbeit mit privaten Akteur*innen. Die negativen Auswirkungen der zunehmenden Privatisierung von Bildung, unter anderem auf Chancengleichheit, werden zu einem zentralen Anliegen für Bildungs-, Entwicklungs- und Menschenrechtswissenschaftler*innen sowie Aktivist*innen. Der Titel „Who chooses? Who loses?“ (Wer wählt? Wer verliert?) zeigt die Folgen der zunehmenden Privatisierung und ihre Auswirkungen in Hinblick auf Exklusion, Segmentierung, Segregation, Chancengleichheit, Stigmatisierung des öffentlichen Bildungswesens, Umverteilung von

Fördermitteln, sinkende Lehrstandards etc., die der GEM-Report zum Teil analysiert.

Die 2019 verabschiedeten Abidjan-Prinzipien regeln die menschenrechtlichen Verpflichtungen von Staaten, öffentliche Bildung bereitzustellen und private Beteiligungen im Bildungswesen zu regulieren. Sie enthalten strenge Leitlinien zur Einschätzung der Rolle privater Anbieter*innen und fassen internationale Rechtsvorschriften in einem einzigen Dokument zusammen,

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welches die staatliche Verantwortung unterstreicht, das Recht auf Bildung zu respektieren und zu schützen.

Grundsatz 25 bezieht sich auf die staatliche Verpflichtung, unmittelbare und mittelbare Diskriminierung in der oder durch die Bildung zu verhindern oder zu beseitigen, beispielsweise durch die Berücksichtigung systemischer Ungleichheit bei Bildungschancen oder -ergebnissen, welche einen sozio-ökonomischen Nachteil offenlegen. Grundsatz 48 bekräftigt, dass private

Akteur*innen die staatliche Bereitstellung von Bildungsangeboten ergänzen, aber nicht verdrängen oder ersetzen können und keine nachteiligen systemischen Auswirkungen, wie beispielsweise das Entstehen oder Verschärfen von Disparitäten in der Bildung, haben dürfen.

Unsere Studie in Ghana, Kenia und Uganda und die kollaborative Forschung in Malawi, Mosambik, Nigeria und Tansania untersuchen, ausgehend von diesen Grundsätzen, die Auswirkungen der Privatisierung auf das Recht auf Bildung. Die Studie kommt zu folgenden Ergebnissen:

- Die untersuchten Staaten kommen ihren Verpflichtungen zur Bereitstellung kostenloser und hochwertiger Bildung sowie zur angemessenen Regulierung privater Bildungsanbieter*innen nicht nach.
- Private Anbieter*innen verdrängen öffentliche Bildung, anstatt sie zu ergänzen.
- Die finanziellen Zuwendungen für das öffentlich zugängliche Bildungsangebot sind unzureichend.
- Die Privatisierung führt zu sozialen Ungleichheiten und verschärft diese.
- Die Vorteile privater Anbieter*innen können nicht eindeutig belegt werden, stattdessen werden ideologische Argumente zur Unterstützung der Agenda herangezogen.

Dementsprechend ist Privatisierung keine Lösung, sondern eher ein Symptom

¹ Die von der GPE-EOL (Global Partnership for Education – Education Out Loud) finanzierte TaxEd-Allianz verbindet zivilgesellschaftliche Interessenvertreter*innen, die sich mit Steuerfragen befassen, mit solchen, die sich mit Bildung befassen, und schafft so einen wirkungsvollen, transnationalen Zusammenschluss von Organisationen der Zivilgesellschaft (CSO). Sie bringt ActionAid, Education International, die Global Campaign for Education, das Tax Justice Network, die Global Alliance for Tax Justice und ihre regionalen Netzwerke Tax And Fiscal Justice Asia und Tax Justice Network - Africa zusammen.

Die Zukunft finanzieren: Bildungsfinanzierung und Steueranreize

Land	Anteil der Bildung am Gesamtbudget	Steuer/BIP	Geschätzter jährlicher Einnahmengang des Staates durch Steueranreize	20% dieser Summe entsprechen	Dieses Geld könnte verwendet werden für
Nepal	14,1% (2018)	18% (13% indirekte, 5% direkte Steuern) (2017)	1,68 Mrd. USD	336,6 Mio. USD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schulplätze für alle im Primar- und Sekundarbereich Mindestgehalt für insgesamt 10.000 Lehrer*innen in der Primar- und Sekundarstufe kostenlose Verpflegung für 600.000 Kinder jährlich 1 Mio. zusätzliche Stipendien für junge Menschen aus vulnerablen Gruppen die geschätzte jährliche Finanzierungslücke (81 Mio. USD, 2021) für den Nepalese School Sector Development Plan
Senegal	22,1% (2020)	16,8% (11,7% indirekte, 5,1% direkte Steuern) (2020)	1,19 Mrd. USD	238 Mio. USD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schulplätze für alle (350.000), die Hälfte der Kinder im Primarschulalter besucht keine Schule 10.000 Lehrer*innen (von 35.000 bis 2030 zu besetzenden Stellen) Verdoppelung der kostenlosen Verpflegung in der Schule
Sambia	12,4% (2020)	16,7% (9% indirekte, 7,7% direkte Steuern) (2019)	406 Mio. USD	81,2 Mio. USD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schulplätze für 350.000 Kinder in der Primarstufe (ca. 2/3 der Kinder, die keine Schule besuchen) 4.000 zusätzliche Lehrer*innen für die Primarstufe kostenlose Verpflegung für 1/2 Mio. Schulkinder
Ghana	18,6% (2018)	12% (5,8% indirekte, 6,5% direkte Steuern) (2019)	1,2 Mrd. USD	240 Mio. USD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schulplätze für 319.000 Kinder in der Primarstufe, die aktuell keine Schule besuchen zusätzlich 10.000 qualifizierte Lehrpersonen kostenlose Verpflegung für 557.892 Kinder
Uganda	11,2% (2018)	11,5% (7,4% indirekte, 1,4% direkte Steuern) (2019)	272 Mio. USD	54,4 Mio. USD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 477.000 Schulplätze in der Primarstufe, für Kinder, die derzeit keine Schule besuchen zusätzlich 20.000 qualifizierte Lehrer*innen kostenlose Verpflegung für 412.047 Kinder

der mangelnden Verfügbarkeit und Qualität von öffentlich zugänglicher Bildung, was wiederum zum Teil eine Folge chronisch unzureichender Finanzierung im Bildungsbereich ist. Unsere Untersuchungen zeigen, dass viele Länder, die ihnen zur Verfügung stehenden Mittel nicht optimal einsetzen und stattdessen Bildungsbudgets ohne Rechtfertigung kürzen.

Im Jahr 2016 berechnete die Bildungskommission, dass 97% der geschätzten Finanzierungslücke im Bildungsbereich aus inländischen Quellen und 3% aus internationaler Hilfe abgedeckt werden sollten. Leider dominiert

trotz des geringen Anteils die internationale Hilfe weiterhin die Debatte. Zudem wird nicht ausreichend darauf geachtet, wie der Großteil der Mittel auf eine Weise aufgebracht werden kann, die ein nachhaltiges Wirtschaftswachstum fördert, die Governance stärkt, die Umwelt schützt und die Menschenrechte einhält. Eine fortschrittliche Steuerreform kann all diese Aspekte berücksichtigen und sollte im Mittelpunkt der Pläne zur Finanzierung der SDGs stehen.

Die Incheon Erklärung empfiehlt, dass mindestens 15–20% des Staatshaushalts für Bildung aufgewendet werden, in einkommensschwachen

Ländern sollten es mindestens 20% sein. Viel zu lange wurde der Anteil des Bildungsbudgets in Abhängigkeit von anderen, konkurrierenden Bereichen, wie zum Beispiel dem Gesundheitsbereich, kalkuliert, ohne die Dynamik zu verstehen, die dem Umfang des Gesamtbudgets zugrunde liegt.

Um ihrer Verpflichtung, dem Recht auf Bildung im Rahmen des SDG 4, nachzukommen und eine angemessene Finanzierung zu gewährleisten, müssen die Länder die **4S** erhöhen:

1. Die Erhöhung des Anteils des Budgets (**Share**) auf ein Minimum von 20%;
2. Den Umfang des Budgets (**Size**) im

- Verhältnis zum BIP durch eine progressive Steuerreform erhöhen;
3. Die Angemessenheit (**Sensitivity**) des Budgets durch Sicherstellung der Mittelzuweisung anhand gerechter Kriterien;
 4. und die Kontrolle (**Scrutiny**) des Budgets durch Gewährleistung von Transparenz, Partizipation, Effizienz und Rechenschaftspflicht.

Der demokratischste und nachhaltigste Weg das Budget zu erhöhen, ist ein progressives Steuersystem, das die **4R** beinhaltet: Einnahmen (**R**evenue), die nachhaltige Mittel für öffentliche Dienstleistungen wie z. B. Bildung generieren; Umverteilung (**R**edistribution), um vertikale und horizontale Ungleichheiten (zwischen Individuen und zwischen Gruppen) einzudämmen; Preisanpassungen (**R**epricing),

Wenn es uns mit [...] SDG 4 ernst ist, müssen wir [...] sowohl die Steuereinnahmen erhöhen als auch die Einnahmeverluste durch illegale Finanzströme und Korruption verringern.

um öffentliche „Übel“ wie Tabakkonsum und Kohlenstoffemissionen zu sanktionieren; Und Repräsentation (**R**epresentation), um funktionierende demokratische Prozesse zu schaffen. Größeres Vertrauen in die Art, wie Staaten Steuergelder investieren, hängt stark mit der Qualität von politischen Entscheidungen und der politischen Partizipation zusammen.

Die Tabelle zeigt die aktuelle Finanzierung des Bildungswesens in Verbindung zu dem durch Steueranreize verlorenen Einkommen in fünf Ländern. Die Länder unterscheiden sich in Bezug auf die Anteile des Bildungsbudgets am Gesamtbudget. Während Senegal mehr als die empfohlenen 20% investiert (andere Quellen sehen auch Ghana über der 20%-Marke), wenden Nepal, Sambia und Uganda

beschämend geringe Beträge für die Bildung auf. Auch wenn es wichtig ist, dass die Länder das Budget gleichmäßig verteilen, müssen wir, wenn wir es mit der Bildungsfinanzierung ernst meinen, die Höhe des Staatshaushalts betrachten, die eng mit der Steuerquote, also dem Verhältnis von Gesamtsteuern und BIP, verbunden ist. Die Tabelle zeigt, dass keines der fünf Länder die niedrige Messlatte von 20% Steuern im Verhältnis zum BIP erreicht (im Gegensatz zu durchschnittlich 41.3% an Steuern in der EU, die für 89.3% der gesamten Staatseinnahmen im Jahr 2020 verantwortlich sind). Die fünf Länder, vor allem Uganda oder Ghana, haben nicht nur ein niedriges Steueraufkommen im Verhältnis zum BIP, sondern weisen auch eine übermäßige Abhängigkeit von indirekter Besteuerung (wie der Mehrwertsteuer oder der Umsatzsteuer) auf, die tendenziell regressiver ist, wie in den Fällen von Nepal und Senegal. Steuerliche Anreize wurden eingesetzt, um ausländische Direktinvestitionen anzuziehen, obwohl zahlreiche Untersuchungen zeigen, dass sie großteils unnötig sind und der Internationale Währungsfonds (IWF) die meisten Formen steuerlicher Anreize inzwischen als schädlich für die Wirtschaft erachtet. Die Tabelle enthält Schätzungen zu den Einnahmeverlusten aufgrund dieser schädlichen Steueranreize und zu dem, was 20% dieses Betrags an Bildungsleistungen hätte finanzieren können. Die Partner*innen der TaxEd Alliance arbeiten in diesen Ländern mit den jeweiligen Verantwortlichen zusammen, um diese Probleme anzugehen und empfehlen progressive Steuerreformen zur Schließung der Finanzierungslücke im Bildungsbereich.

Reichen die staatlichen Einnahmen nicht aus, steigt der von (privaten) Haushalten getragene Anteil an Bildungsausgaben und erreicht in Ländern mit niedrigem Einkommen inzwischen 38% (EFW, 2021). Diese sehr regressiv Art der Bildungsfinanzierung verstärkt geschlechtsspezifische und andere soziale Ungleichheiten und vergrößert

die vertikalen und horizontalen Ungleichheiten innerhalb und zwischen den Ländern.

Die Abschaffung der Schulgebühren in den frühen 2000er Jahren hat bedeutend zur Erhöhung der Einschulungen und in vielen Ländern zu Geschlechterparität beigetragen. Vor diesem Hintergrund ist der wachsende Diskurs über die „Erschwinglichkeit“ von Bildung, der dazu führt, dass mehr Kosten auf Familien abgewälzt werden, äußerst problematisch und kann die Fortschritte, die in den letzten Jahren erzielt wurden, zunichtemachen. Wenn es uns mit der Verwirklichung von SDG 4 ernst ist, müssen wir uns auf die nachhaltige Mobilisierung nationaler Ressourcen konzentrieren, indem wir sowohl die Steuereinnahmen erhöhen als auch die Einnahmeverluste durch illegale Finanzströme und Korruption verringern. Die Länder müssen ihrer Verpflichtung nachkommen, kostenlose öffentliche Bildung von höchstmöglicher Qualität zu bieten, indem sie den Umfang, den Anteil, die Sensibilität und die Kontrolle des Budgets erhöhen, die notwendigen Mittel für öffentliche Schulen bereitstellen und private Anbieter*innen angemessen regulieren.

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DR.^{IN} MARIA RON-BALSERA promovierte 2014 mit einem Marie-Curie-Stipendium in Erziehungswissenschaften an der Universität Bielefeld, Deutschland. Außerdem hat sie einen MSc in Menschenrechten von der London School of Economics und einen LLM in Menschenrechten von der Universidad Carlos III in Madrid. Sie hat als Gastwissenschaftlerin am Institute of Education (UCL) und im Rahmen eines Forschungsaustauschprogramms an der UC Berkeley geforscht. Derzeit ist sie Koordinatorin der Allianz für Steuern und Bildung, eine transnationale Partnerschaft, die ActionAid, Education International, Global Campaign for Education, Tax Justice Network und die Global Alliance for Tax Justice zusammenbringt.

UNESCO-SCHULEN IN ÖSTERREICH

„learning to know, learning to do, learning to be,
learning to live together“

UNESCO-Schulen bilden ein weltweites Netzwerk von über 11.500 Bildungseinrichtungen in 182 Staaten. Die 96 österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen sind Teil dieses internationalen Netzwerks und tragen zur Wahrung des Friedens und der Sicherheit bei, indem jungen Menschen möglichst früh Verständnis, Toleranz und Freundschaft zwischen allen Nationen und Völkern nahegebracht werden.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• UNESCO-Schulen / Tagung 2021

Bereits seit 1997 organisiert die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission jährliche Vernetzungstreffen für alle Referent*innen der österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen.

Die Jahrestagungen tragen wesentlich zur Weiterbildung, zur Vernetzung der Lehrpersonen und zum Gedankenaustausch bei. In Workshops, Vorträgen, durch Exkursionen und den Austausch über Projekte können sich die UNESCO-Schulreferent*innen fortbilden und gegenseitig ermutigen, anspruchsvolle Projekte im Unterricht altersgemäß für Kinder und Jugendliche zu gestalten. Die Jahrestagung 2021 fand abermals virtuell von 13. bis 14. Oktober statt. Das Thema der diesjährigen Veranstaltung lautete „Futures of Education“ angelehnt an den Zukunftsbericht: „Re-imagining our futures together: a new social contract for education“. Die Schwerpunkte der Tagung waren sowohl inhaltlicher als auch struktureller Natur: Inhaltlich gab es Workshops zum Immateriellen Kulturerbe und den 17 Zielen für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung. Strukturell gab es einen tiefen Einblick in die Bildungsarbeit der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission und ihre Tätigkeiten inklusive einem Ausblick auf zukünftige Projekte für österreichische UNESCO-Schulen. Abschließend bot der „Markt der Möglichkeiten“ in bewährter Manier die Gelegenheit zum virtuellen Austausch für die Lehrer*innen. Die Veranstaltung fand unter Teilnahme von 75 Schulen statt.

• Zeitschrift FORUM

Die jährlich erscheinende Zeitschrift FORUM zeigt die große Vielfalt, Kreativität und das Engagement mit der die österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen die Leitideen der UNESCO und die jeweiligen Jahresthemen umsetzen. Die aktuelle Ausgabe des FORUM (Heft 33/2021) trägt den Titel „Futures of Education“.

Anhand von Beiträgen von 50 UNESCO-Schulen wird die Diversität der Themen, mit denen sich Schüler*innen im Schuljahr 2020/2021 praktisch im Unterricht auseinandergesetzt haben, dokumentiert. Der prinzipielle Schwerpunkt lag auf den SDGs, den 17 Zielen für eine Nachhaltige Entwicklung, wobei sich Schulen einerseits verstärkt mit Biodiversität, Nachhaltigkeit und Klimawandel beschäftigten, andererseits, bedingt durch die andauernde Pandemie und die speziellen Gegebenheiten durch virtuellen und hybriden Unterricht, Themen wie Zivilcourage, Integration, Friedenserziehung und Menschenrechte stärker in den Fokus rückten. Beispielsweise kam es zu einigen Online-Nachhilfeprojekten von und für Schüler*innen und zu Spenden- und Hilfsaktionen für Menschen in prekären Verhältnissen.

Ganz im Sinne von „Futures of Education“, einem von der UNESCO publizierten Zukunftsbericht die Bildung betreffend, kam es zu partizipativen Workshops und Projekten, in die sich Schüler*innen aktiv einbringen konnten und die Möglichkeit hatten, selbst ihren Schulalltag, die Lernräume und -orte an sich und auch Unterrichtseinheiten zu gestalten. Wichtiges Thema des Berichts ist auch die Vermittlung von digitalen Werkzeugen, um sowohl die technischen Fähigkeiten als auch den kritischen Geist und die Distanz zu vermitteln, die für ihre sinnvolle Nutzung erforderlich sind.

UNESCO-SCHULEN

1953 von der UNESCO gegründet

Über **11.500** Bildungseinrichtungen in **182** Ländern

Österreich: Mitglied seit **1957**, Schulen aller Schultypen in allen **9** Bundesländern

96 UNESCO-Schulen, **20** Schulen mit Anwärterstatus

Leitlinien: learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, learning to live together.

Themen: Friedenserziehung und Menschenrechtsbildung, Global Citizenship Education, Bildung für Nachhaltige Entwicklung, Kulturelle Bildung, Sustainable Development Goals.

ÖUK-Rolle: Nationale Koordination zur Beratung, Projektinitiation, Information und Kooperation, jährlich dreitägige Jahrestagung, Magazin „FORUM“, Website.

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/:

Zentrale Informations-Website mit einer Liste aller österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen, aktuellen Veranstaltungen, Projekten und Ausschreibungen der Schulen.

• Kulturelle Bildung

2019 wurde das UNESCO-EU Pilot-Projekt „Teaching and Learning with Living Heritage“ in Kooperation mit 10 UNESCO-Schulen europaweit initiiert, aus Österreich beteiligte sich die Mittelschule Bad Goisern. Im Rahmen der Jahrestagung der Österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen wurde das Projekt vorgestellt. Im November 2021 organisierte die ÖUK fachbereichsübergreifend (IKE und Bildung) ein Vernetzungstreffen zwischen Trägerschaften des Immateriellen Kulturerbes und den Schulreferent*innen der Österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen, das regen Zuspruch von beiden Seiten fand. Das Projekt wird im Jahr 2022 weitergeführt und österreichweit mit Facilitators der UNESCO umgesetzt.

Nähere Informationen unter:

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/lehr-und-lernmaterial/immaterielles-kulturerbe

• SDG-Workshops

Die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission baut aufgrund des großen Erfolgs von „Turning point. Youth for sustainable development“, der Veranstaltungsreihe von jungen Menschen für junge Menschen in Österreich, und aufgrund der großen Nachfrage von Schulen, das Angebot zu SDG-Workshops speziell für UNESCO-Schulen aus. Den Österreichischen UNESCO-Schulen wird die Möglichkeit geboten, SDG-Expert*innen mit unterschiedlichen thematischen Schwerpunktsetzungen für einen Online-Workshop zu buchen. Die Inhalte sind breit gefächert und lassen sich in unterschiedliche Unterrichtsfächer integrieren.

Die Schüler*innen im Alter von 14–19 Jahren können sich intensiv mit den globalen Nachhaltigkeitszielen (SDGs) aus verschiedenen Perspektiven auseinandersetzen, um einerseits ihr Wissen zu erweitern, und andererseits deren Facettenreichtum und die fächerübergreifende Anwendung zu erfassen. Die Workshops sind interaktiv und ermutigen Schüler*innen zur selbstständigen Auseinandersetzung mit diesem komplexen Thema.

WISSENSCHAFT

Wissenschaften sind der Grundpfeiler moderner, aufgeklärter, demokratischer Gesellschaften. Die wissenschaftliche Forschung ermöglicht es, gesellschaftliche Entwicklungen und Herausforderungen überhaupt erst zu benennen und Antworten auf die Fragen unserer Zeit zu finden. Wissenschaft ist per se ein internationales Vorhaben, kein Staat ist alleine in der Lage, Forschung voranzutreiben. In der UNESCO arbeiten alle Mitgliedsstaaten zusammen, um die wissenschaftliche Forschung im Spannungsfeld zwischen Wissenschaftsfreiheit und gesellschaftlicher Verantwortung weltweit zu stärken. Sie fördert die globale Forschung zu den drängenden Menschheitsfragen und unterstützt Menschen dabei, Wissen für den Aufbau gerechter und inklusiver Gesellschaften zu nutzen.

UNESCO-WISSENSCHAFTS-PROGRAMME

Die Kernthemen der UNESCO-Wissenschaftsprogramme

Zu den inhaltlichen Schwerpunkten der UNESCO zählen der Klimawandel und die Erhaltung der Artenvielfalt, die Förderung von Wissen zum Schutz von Ozeanen und Küsten sowie die Sicherung der Trinkwasserversorgung.

Beispielgebend sind die drei etablierten UNESCO-Programme – „Man and the Biosphere“ (MAB) und „Intergovernmental Hydrological- und Geoscience-Programme“ (IHP und IGCP), die sich der Erforschung und dem Schutz der Lebensumwelt des Menschen widmen.

In Österreich werden die Programme durch das MAB- und Geo/Hydro-Nationalkomitee an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften betreut.

• Man and the Biosphere

Das im Jahr 1971 gegründete UNESCO-Programm „Man and the Biosphere“ (MAB) entwickelt wissenschaftliche und anwendungsorientierte Grundlagen im Bereich der Natur- und Sozialwissenschaften, die der langfristigen Sicherung der natürlichen Lebensgrundlagen und der Artenvielfalt dienen. Ziel ist eine nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Beziehung zwischen Mensch und Umwelt: die Schaffung eines Gleichgewichts zwischen dem Schutz der biologischen Vielfalt, der Förderung der wirtschaftlichen und sozialen Entwicklung und der Bewahrung der jeweiligen kulturellen Werte. Das Biosphärenpark-Netzwerk umfasst derzeit 727 Biosphärenparks in 131 Ländern. In Österreich sind bis dato vier Biosphärenparks (Wienerwald, Großes Walsertal, Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, Unteres Murtal) eingerichtet.

Österreich beteiligt sich auch äußerst aktiv an internationalen Gremien und Ausschüssen zum MAB-Programm. So vertritt aktuell Dr. Günter Köck von der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften die Region „Europa und Nordamerika“ im UNESCO-Lenkungsausschuss des Forschungsprogramms. Köck ist aktuell auch Vize-Vorsitzender. Bereits zum vierten Mal wurde der österreichische Delegierte im Herbst 2020 für das International Coordinating Council des UNESCO-MAB-Programms zum Vize-Vorsitzenden gewählt.

• IHP (Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme) und IGCP (International Geoscience Programme)

Das „Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme“ (IHP) der UNESCO ist das einzige zwischenstaatliche Programm des UN-Systems, das der Wasserforschung und, der Wasserbewirtschaftung sowie dem Capacity-Building diesbezüglich gewidmet ist. Ziel des Programms ist es, einen interdisziplinären und integrierten Ansatz für Wasser-

MAB – MAN AND THE BIOSPHERE PROGRAMME/DER MENSCH UND DIE BIOSPHÄRE

Erstes zwischenstaatliches Umweltprogramm, das sich der **Mensch-Umwelt-beziehung** und der nachhaltigen Nutzung der natürlichen Ressourcen widmet

Globales Netzwerk der UNESCO-Biosphärenparks – Modellregionen, die Naturschutz, Erhaltung der biologischen Diversität und Regionalentwicklung in Einklang bringen

4 Biosphärenparks in Österreich: Großes Walsertal, Wienerwald und Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, Unteres Murtal

Umsetzung in Österreich durch das nationale **MAB-Nationalkomitee**

ÖUK Rolle: Informationsplattform für das Programm, Öffentlichkeitsarbeit

Nähere Informationen zum „Man and the Biosphere Programme“:

einzugsgebiete und das Aquifer-Management zu fördern, der die soziale Dimension der Wasserressourcen einbezieht und die internationale Forschung in den hydrologischen und Süßwasserwissenschaften fördert und entwickelt.

Im Rahmen des 1973 gegründeten „International Geoscience Programme“ (IGCP) werden geowissenschaftliche Kooperationsprojekte zu den von der UNESCO genau definierten Forschungsschwerpunkten gefördert. Dazu zählen auch die UNESCO-Global Geoparks, zu denen in Österreich folgende Geoparks gehören: Steirische Eisenwurz, Erz der Alpen sowie der länderübergreifende Geopark Karawanken/Karavanke.

• UNITWIN/UNESCO-Chairs-Programm

Das 1992 ins Leben gerufene UNITWIN/UNESCO-Chairs-Programm ist ein wichtiger Impulsgeber, um die Anliegen der UNESCO an Hochschulen zu verankern. Es fördert Forschung, Ausbildung und Entwicklung von Hochschulen durch die Bildung von Universitätsnetzwerken und zwischenuniversitäre, grenzüberschreitende Kooperation.

Heute nehmen über 700 Institutionen weltweit an dem Programm teil, zehn davon sind an österreichischen Hochschulen angesiedelt.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• 4 UNESCO-L'ORÉAL-Stipendien in Österreich

The World needs Science – Science needs Women

Wesentliches Ziel der Wissenschaftsprogramme der UNESCO ist die Förderung der Rolle von Frauen in der Wissenschaft, insbesondere in den Biowissenschaften. Die „L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Initiative“ ist ein Teil dieses Engagements. Jährlich werden im Rahmen der „L'Oréal-UNESCO for Women in Science Awards Ceremony“ am UNESCO-Sitz in Paris fünf Preise zu je € 100.000 und fünfzehn L'Oréal-UNESCO Rising Talents Stipendien an herausragende Natur-

wissenschaftlerinnen vergeben. Diese Kooperation wird auch auf nationaler Ebene fortgeführt. Jährlich werden vier Stipendien an junge hochqualifizierte Grundlagenforscherinnen aus den Bereichen Medizin, Naturwissenschaften und Mathematik vergeben.

Seit 2007 vergibt L'Oréal Österreich in Zusammenarbeit mit der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission, der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften und mit Unterstützung des Bundesministeriums für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung (BMBWF) jährlich Stipendien zu je € 25.000,- an exzellente junge Wissenschaftlerinnen in Österreich. Sie verfolgen das Ziel der Anerkennung, Förderung und Ermutigung junger Frauen durch die Schaffung von Rollenvorbildern. Zudem wollen sie die Öffentlichkeit auf wissenschaftliche Spitzenleistungen aufmerksam machen und dabei gleichzeitig das weibliche Gesicht der Forschung zeigen.

IHP – INTERNATIONAL HYDROLOGICAL PROGRAMME

1975 erstes multilaterales Programm zu Wasserforschung und Wasser-Ressourcenmanagement – International Hydrological Programme IHP

8. IHP 2014–2021: IHP widmet sich in der 8. Phase der Verbesserung der Wasserqualität unter Berücksichtigung lokaler, regionaler und globaler Herausforderungen

Kern des Programms: Nachhaltiges Wassermanagement, Förderung und Entwicklung internationaler Wasserforschung sowie globale Netzwerkbildung

Teil der **Agenda 2030**

ÖUK Rolle: Informationsplattform für das Programm, Öffentlichkeitsarbeit

Nähere Informationen zur 8. Implementierungsphase:

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Stipendiatinnen mit den Festredner*innen: Kerstin Rastädter, Sabine Haag, Monika Malik, Martin Netzer, Alice Laciny, Wioletta Rosolowska, Anna Breger, Helmut Denk (v.l.n.r.)

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG und Wissenschaft Die UNESCO-Wissenschaftsprogramme tragen maßgeblich zu allen nachhaltigen Entwicklungszielen (SDGs) bei. Vor allem Wissenschaft, Technologie und Innovation spielen hierbei eine zentrale Rolle. Die Sozial- und Geisteswissenschaften fördern das Verständnis für aktuelle Herausforderungen und helfen somit die Ziele zu erreichen.

Die naturwissenschaftlichen Programme der UNESCO tragen v.a. zur Umsetzung von **SDG 12** (Verantwortungsvolle Konsum- und Produktionsmuster), **SDG 15** (Leben an Land) sowie **SDG 13** (Maßnahmen zum Klimaschutz) bei. Durch die sozial- und geisteswissenschaftlichen Programme der Organisation wird v.a. die Umsetzung von **SDG 16** (Frieden, Gerechtigkeit und starke Institutionen) gefördert. Alle Wissenschaftsprogramme leisten auch Beiträge zur Umsetzung von **SDG 5** (Geschlechtergerechtigkeit) und **SDG 17** (Partnerschaften zur Erreichung der Ziele).

Die Preisträgerinnen 2021:

- Dr.ⁱⁿ Anna Breger, Angewandte Mathematikerin, Universität Wien
- Alice Laciny, PhD, Zoologin, Konrad-Lorenz- Institut für Evolutions- und Kognitionsforschung
- Monika Malik, MSc, Pharmazeutin, Universität Wien
- Dipl.-Ing.ⁱⁿ Kerstin Rastädter, Biotechnologin, Technische Universität Wien

Am 27. Oktober wurden sie im Festsaal der Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien feierlich geehrt. In seiner Eröffnungsrede betonte Dr. Anton Zeilinger die Bedeutung weiblicher Vorbilder in Wissenschaft und Forschung. Anschließend bekräftigte Wioletta Rosolowska, Geschäftsführerin von L'ORÉAL Österreich/Deutschland, den hohen Stellenwert des Stipendiums für L'ORÉAL. Dr.in Sabine Haag, Präsidentin der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission, sprach von der Bedeutung von Frauen in Wissenschaft und Forschung bei der Suche nach innovativen Lösungen für drängende aktuelle Probleme, die uns global beschäftigen. Generalsekretär Mag. Martin Netzer, der in Vertretung von Bundesminister Dr. Heinz Faßmann der Veranstaltung beiwohnte, machte auf die Herausforderungen für Forscherinnen aufgrund der aktuellen Situation aufmerksam und betonte die Wichtigkeit weitreichender struktureller Maßnahmen, um Geschlechtergerechtigkeit an Hochschul- und Forschungseinrichtungen zu schaffen.

• UNITWIN/UNESCO-Chairs-Programm

2021 wurde der „UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Futures Design“ an der Kunstuniversität Linz, als insgesamt zehnter Lehrstuhl in Österreich, eingerichtet. Lehrstuhlinhaber ist Univ.-Prof. Dr. Michael Shamiyeh. Der Lehrstuhl forscht zu neuen sozialen Techniken und Innovations- und Führungsfähigkeiten, die das Öffnen alternativer Sichtweisen, Denk- und Wahrnehmungsmuster ermöglichen. Große Bedeutung kommt dabei der Aktionsforschung zu gegenwärtigen Transformationsprozesse in Organisationen sowie der analytischen Aufarbeitung historischer Beispiele zu.

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IGCP – INTERNATIONAL GEOSCIENCE PROGRAMME

1973 gegründet

Kern des Programms: weltweite wissenschaftliche Zusammenarbeit mit Schwerpunkt auf Nord-Süd-Kooperation; aktuell Fokus auf angewandte Geowissenschaften, vor allem zur Bekämpfung von Naturkatastrophen wie Erdbeben, Erdbeben und Vulkanausbrüchen

2015 Gründung des UNESCO Global Geopark (UGG)-Labels

161 UGGs weltweit, 3 davon in Österreich

In Österreich: Betreuung durch das Geo/Hydro-Sciences Nationalkomitee an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (ÖAW) im Rahmen des Earth System Sciences-Programms

ÖUK Rolle: gemeinsam mit der ÖAW zentrale Ansprechpartnerin der Geoparks

Draava in Kroatien

In all den Jahren keinen Bock geschossen – Günter Köck und „sein“ MAB-Programm

Dr. Günter Köck ist promovierter Biologe. Seit rund 40 Jahren ist er mit zahlreichen Forschungsprojekten im Bereich der Umwelttoxikologie befasst. Seit 1997 verbringt Köck seine Sommer im hohen Norden Kanadas, wo er als Teil einer österreichisch-kanadische Forschungs Kooperation die Auswirkungen von Umweltverschmutzung und Klimaveränderungen auf Fische erforscht und gelegentlich mit Wölfen kämpft. Vielleicht weniger spektakulär, aber nicht minder wichtig ist sein zweites berufliches Standbein: neben der Forschung hat er sich der Koordinierung internationaler Forschungsprogramme verschrieben. Mit März 2022 wird Günter Köck Altersteilzeit antreten und einige seiner Funktionen abgeben. Im folgenden Gespräch zieht er Bilanz über sein berufliches Schaffen für das bzw. im Rahmen des UNESCO Programms „Man and the Biosphere“.

Lieber Günter, du warst 18 Jahre lang als Koordinator der internationalen ÖAW-Forschungsprogramme Earth System Sciences tätig, zwei davon – das Man and the Biosphere-Nationalkomitee und das Nationalkomitee für Geo/Hydrosciences – sind die nationalen Komitees der jeweiligen UNESCO-Programme. Darüber hinaus bist du österreichischer Delegierter für das International Coordinating Council of

UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB-ICC), warst mehrmals Stellvertretender Vorsitzender des UNESCO-MAB-Programmes. Wie kamst du zum ersten Mal mit der UNESCO und der ÖUK in Berührung?

Ich kam eigentlich schon kurz nach dem Antreten meiner Position an der ÖAW im Jahr 2004 mit der UNESCO in Berührung, da sich unter den damals sieben Nationalkomitees (NK) auch drei UNESCO-Programme (MAB, IGCP,

IHP¹) befanden. In diesen Nationalkomitees war natürlich auch die ÖUK vertreten. Als dann im Oktober 2004 das 33. Meeting des MAB International Coordinating Council in Paris auf dem Programm stand, hat mich der damalige NK-Vorsitzende Georg Grabherr, der mich und meine internationale Orientierung durch mein damals schon seit sieben Jahren laufendes Arktis-Projekt kannte, gebeten, das Nationalkomitee in Paris zu vertreten. Ziemlich überraschend wurde Österreich damals ins MAB-Bureau gewählt, wodurch ich stellvertretender Vorsitzender des Programms wurde. Man muss allerdings sagen, dass der Grund für diese Wahl eine Art Belohnung für die Zusage Österreichs war, das Meeting der EuroMAB²-Gruppe im Jahr 2005 im Biosphärenpark Wienerwald auszurichten. Dieses Meeting, bei dessen Organisation und Finanzierung die ÖUK die Führungsrolle innehatte, war ausgesprochen erfolgreich und hat auch die Zusammenarbeit zwischen dem Nationalkomitee und der ÖUK noch reibungsloser gemacht.

Das MAB-Programm der UNESCO widmet sich der Beziehung zwischen dem Menschen und seiner Umwelt. Angesichts der Bedrohungen des Klimawandels ist das Programm heute aktueller denn je. Was macht das MAB-Programm aus? Was ist das Besondere daran, dass du dich so engagierst?

Ich habe mich ja an der Universität Innsbruck bereits viele Jahre intensiv mit der Umweltforschung beschäftigt und erforsche seit 1997 in meinem österreichisch-kanadischen Arktisforschungsprojekt die Einflüsse des Klimawandels auf Gewässerökosysteme. Daher ist mir die Besonderheit des MAB-Programms sofort aufgefallen: Es versucht, die Bedürfnisse der Natur und jene des Menschen unter einen Hut zu bringen.

¹ MAB – Man and the Biosphere; IGCP – International Geoscience Programme; IHP – Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme

² EuroMAB – zweijährliches Treffen der Biosphärenpark-Manager*innen und MAB-Nationalkomitees der Region Europa und Nordamerika

Mit der Unterstützung des österreichischen MAB-Nationalkomitees habe ich mich von Beginn an in den Prozess zur Qualitätssteigerung eingebracht. Dieser Vorgang ging über viele Jahre und wurde erst vor kurzem erfolgreich abgeschlossen. Damit bin ich auch bei einem herausragenden Asset des Programms, nämlich seiner Wandlungsfähigkeit: Es hat sich in den 50 Jahren seines Bestehens immer den globalen Herausforderungen, wie etwa dem Klimawandel, gestellt und wurde ungefähr alle 10 Jahre weiterentwickelt. Damit ist das Programm sicherlich ein Vorzeigeprogramm der UNESCO und seine Existenz in Zeiten, in denen die Beziehung zwischen Mensch und Umwelt zunehmend aus dem Gleichgewicht gerät und Klimakonferenzen von einem Kompromiss zum nächsten eilen, noch nie so notwendig gewesen wie heute.

Als eines der ersten am Programm beteiligten Länder errichtete Österreich sein MAB-Nationalkomitee bereits Ende 1972 an der ÖAW. Und auch international war und ist Österreich stark vertreten. Was bedeutet dieses Programm für Österreich und was Österreich für dieses Programm? Das MAB-Programm bietet für Österreich die Chance, Naturschutz, die Erhaltung der biologischen Diversität und Regionalentwicklung in Einklang zu bringen und damit Nachhaltigkeit in die Tat umzusetzen. Die vier österreichischen Biosphärenparks „Großes Walsertal“, „Salzburger Lungau und Kärntner Nockberge“, „Wienerwald“ und „Unteres Murtal“ sind nicht nur national als Modellregionen für nachhaltige Entwicklung etabliert, sondern spielen auch international eine Vorreiterrolle in der Umsetzung der „Agenda 2030 für nachhaltige Entwicklung“. Besondere Erwähnung verdient hier wohl das Management der Nockberge-Region, das sich seit vielen Jahren intensiv in das MAB-Programm und das Weltnetzwerk der Biosphärenparks einbringt und im September 2022 das

Meeting der EuroMAB-Gruppe ausgerichtet. Außerdem ist der Biosphärenpark „Unteres Murtal“ bemerkenswert, der seit 2021 Teil des weltweit ersten grenzüberschreitenden Biosphärenparks „Mura-Drava-Danube“ ist.

Wenn du auf deine langjährige Tätigkeit zurückblickst: Was waren bisher deine größten Erfolge, woran erinnerst du dich am liebsten? Und was wirst du vielleicht irgendwann vermissen?

Ich möchte hier sagen, dass meine Erfolge ohne das von Anfang an große Vertrauen, das Georg Grabherr in mich gesetzt hat, wohl nicht möglich gewesen wären. Georg wollte das Nationalkomitee modernisieren und neu ausrichten und mir war die internationale Ausrichtung zu schwach. Insofern haben wir beide uns perfekt ergänzt. Auch die Zusammenarbeit mit seinem Nachfolger Arne Arnberger war herausragend. Es ist natürlich schwierig, über eigene Erfolge zu sprechen. Aber es gibt einiges, auf das ich stolz bin. Etwa darauf, dass das österreichische Nationalkomitee und die Biosphärenparks nunmehr stark international ausgerichtet sind und sich in die Arbeit des Programms intensiv einbringen. Wir haben über die Jahre viele Aktivitäten des internationalen MAB-Programms auch finanziell unterstützt und erfolgreiche Forschungsprojekte in anderen Ländern (z.B. Peru) finanziert. Und damit wäre ich beim wohl wichtigsten Punkt, der das Nationalkomitee weltweit ziemlich einzigartig macht, nämlich der Tatsache, dass es von Beginn an mit einem eigenen Forschungsbudget ausgestattet war. Dies hat uns vieles ermöglicht und ich hoffe, dass das auch in Zukunft so bleibt. Das österreichische MAB-Nationalkomitee hat sich in der internationalen Community einen ganz ausgezeichneten Ruf erworben! Tja, was gäbe es noch: vielleicht die beiden von mir initiierten, preisgekrönten Bücher „Planet Austria“ und das „Kochbuch der österreichischen Biosphärenparks“, das in der MAB-Community ebenfalls großes Aufsehen erregt hat. Woran ich

mich auch gerne erinnere, ist beispielsweise, dass mir beim MAB-ICC 2019 zu meinem 60. Geburtstag von den internationalen Kolleg*innen coram publico eine Torte überreicht wurde und mich die österreichische Botschafterin vor der UNESCO zu einem Mittagessen mit prominenten MAB-Weggefährt*innen eingeladen hat.

Ich werde gerne weiterhin für das internationale MAB-Programm tätig sein. Was mir aber wirklich einmal abgehen wird, ist die wunderbare Internationalität des MAB-Programms, die Möglichkeit, die vielen Kulturen und Denkweisen kennenzulernen, diese zu akzeptieren und entsprechend zu handeln. Ja, auf was ich wirklich stolz bin: Ich dürfte in all den Jahren, in denen ich Österreich in Paris vertreten habe, keinen einzigen politischen und/oder fachlichen „Bock geschossen“ haben.

Das Gespräch mit Dr. Günter Köck wird aus Platzgründen hier gekürzt abgedruckt. Das gesamte Interview finden Sie auf www.unesco.at

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DR. GÜNTER KÖCK ist Vize-Vorsitzender und Berichterstatter des internationalen Man and the Biosphere-Koordinationsrates der UNESCO und Mitglied des österreichischen MAB-Nationalkomitees an der ÖAW, für das er bis 2021 18 Jahre lang als Generalsekretär diente. Darüber hinaus ist er Mitglied der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission und des Wissenschaftlichen Beirats des Nationalparks Hohe Tauern sowie Delegierter zum International Scientific Committee for Alpine Research. Weiters ist er einer der Gründungsherausgeber der im Jahr 2009 gegründeten wissenschaftlichen Fachzeitschrift *eco.mont*. Als Arktisforscher ist Köck assoziierter Wissenschaftler am Institut für interdisziplinäre Gebirgsforschung in Innsbruck und Initiator des österreichisch-kanadischen Arktisforschungsprojekts „HighArctic“. In diesem von ihm und Derek Muir (Environment and Climate Change Canada) geleiteten Langzeitprojekt werden seit 1997 jährlich die Einflüsse von Klimaveränderungen auf Fische aus Seen in der kanadischen Arktis untersucht.

KULTUR

Kultur ist die Grundlage für sozialen Zusammenhalt und gesellschaftliche Weiterentwicklung. Ihre vielfältigen Ausdrucksformen – von historischen Bauwerken über lebendige Traditionen hin zu zeitgenössischer Kunst – sind das Fundament für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung unserer Welt. Die UNESCO hat sich der Förderung von Kultur auf allen Ebenen verschrieben: Sie setzt sich weltweit für klare politische und rechtliche Rahmenbedingungen im Kulturbereich ein und unterstützt Mitgliedstaaten ebenso wie lokale, zivilgesellschaftliche Akteur*innen, um das kulturelle Erbe zu schützen und kulturelle Vielfalt zu fördern.

UNESCO-KULTURBEREICHE: Kulturelle Vielfalt | Welterbe | Kulturgüterschutz | Immaterielles Kulturerbe |

Die Arbeitsschwerpunkte der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission im Bereich Kultur orientieren sich an einer aktiven Umsetzung der sieben UNESCO-Konventionen im Kulturbereich. Besondere Aufmerksamkeit gilt der Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen, dem Schutz und Erhalt des materiellen und immateriellen Kulturerbes sowie dem Kulturgüterschutz.

VIELFALT IN KUNST UND KULTUR

schützen und fördern

Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen zu fördern, bedeutet im Sinne des *UNESCO-Übereinkommens zum Schutz und zur Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen* eine Vielfalt des Schaffens, der Herstellung, der Verbreitung, des Vertriebs und der Teilhabe an Kunst und Kultur zu ermöglichen. Der Kern des Übereinkommens ist es, Staaten ein Recht auf eigenständige Kunst- und Kulturpolitik zuzusichern, sodass Kunst und Kultur nicht auf ihren ökonomischen Aspekt reduziert werden.

Mit dem Übereinkommen wurde erstmals in einem internationalen Rechtsinstrument anerkannt, dass kulturelle Güter und Dienstleistungen Träger von Identitäten und Ausdruck von Werten und ästhetischen Positionen sind. Zwar kommt ihnen auch ökonomische Bedeutung als Ware und konsumierbares Produkt zu, ihr Wert erschöpft sich jedoch nicht im finanziell Bezifferbaren. Mit Artikel 16 „Vorzugsbehandlung“ stellt das Übereinkommen globale Ungleichheitsstrukturen und die Benachteiligung des Globalen Südens in den Fokus. Diese Bestimmung verpflichtet den Globalen Norden Maßnahmen zu setzen, die sowohl die Mobilität von Kunst- und Kulturakteur*innen als auch den Austausch von kulturellen Gütern und Dienstleistungen aus dem Globalen Süden unterstützen.

Die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission fungiert als nationale Kontaktstelle für Fragen zur Umsetzung des Übereinkommens in Österreich. Ein zentrales Anliegen der ÖUK ist der Dialog und die Zusammenarbeit mit relevanten Akteur*innen, um förderliche Strukturen und Rahmenbedingungen für kulturelle Vielfalt in Österreich zu gestalten.

Beratende und unterstützende Gremien

Fachbeirat Kulturelle Vielfalt: unterstützt die ÖUK bei der Koordination aller das Übereinkommen betreffenden Belange

ARGE Kulturelle Vielfalt: Dialogplattform zur aktiven Beteiligung der Zivilgesellschaft

Der Kern des Übereinkommens ist es, Staaten ein Recht auf eigenständige Kunst- und Kulturpolitik zuzusichern, sodass Kunst und Kultur nicht auf ihren ökonomischen Aspekt reduziert werden.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 8: Menschenwürdige Arbeit: die soziale und ökonomische Absicherung ist essentiell für Künstler*innen wie auch Kulturarbeiter*innen, um frei künstlerisch und kreativ schaffen zu können. **SDG 10:** Die Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen geht Hand in Hand mit der Verringerung der Ungleichheiten zwischen und in Ländern. **SDG 16** und **SDG 17:** Ein Grundpfeiler der Konvention ist Partizipation und Partnerschaft mit der Zivilgesellschaft – nur so lässt sich eine transparente, partizipative und bedarfsorientierte Politikgestaltung, auch im Kulturbereich, realisieren.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• Forum Fair Culture

Die Veranstaltungsreihe Forum Fair Culture startete als Zusammenarbeit zwischen der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission und kulturen in bewegung im Dezember 2020. Sie öffnete den Raum, die Verpflichtung zur Vorzugsbehandlung im (post-)migrantischen Österreich sowie Querverbindungen zum Themenbereich Anti-Diskriminierung zu diskutieren. Diskursive Formate hinterfragten, was sogenannte „Süd-Perspektiven“ denn überhaupt sind und welche Formen von Diskriminierung, Ausschluss und Rassismus in Österreich wirkmächtig werden. Ziel der Vorzugsbehandlung ist es, das bestehende Ungleichgewicht zwischen dem sogenannten Globalen Norden und Süden auszubalancieren – ein Prozess, der sich in einer globalisierten Gesellschaft nicht nur zwischen Staaten, sondern auch innerhalb von Ländergrenzen entfalten muss. Vorzugsbehandlung – und damit einhergehend eine Entwicklung in Richtung Gerechtigkeit – betrifft demnach auch die Community-Arbeit in Österreich, die es erlaubt, die tatsächliche Inklusivität des Kultursektors genauer zu betrachten.

Die Zusammenarbeit der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission mit kulturen in bewegung ermöglichte den Blick in die Praxis und eine Bestandsaufnahme der aktuellen Verhältnisse. Insgesamt fanden vier Veranstaltungen in unterschiedlichen Live- und Online-Formaten statt. Die wichtigsten Ergebnisse wurden in Form einer Publikation veröffentlicht.

• Klausurtagung ARGE Kulturelle Vielfalt 2021 in Graz

Auf Einladung der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission fand die „Klausurtagung Kulturelle Vielfalt“ 2021 im Forum Stadtpark Graz statt. In einem detaillierten Schlusskommuniqué legten die unterzeichnenden Expert*innen der ARGE Kulturelle Vielfalt ihren Befund über Status Quo und Fortschritt der Umsetzung des UNESCO-Übereinkommens über den Schutz und die Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen vor. Im Zentrum der Diskussionen standen Fragen und Forderungen zur sozialen Absicherung, Diskriminierungskritik, künstlerischer Mobilität und vielen weiteren Themen. „In der gegenwärtigen tiefen Krise sind radikale Prozesse des Umdenkens in Politik und Wirtschaft zur wichtigsten Überlebensfrage geworden. Kulturakteur*innen entwickeln realisierbare Visionen und leben sie bereits. Es ist höchste Zeit, dass sie nicht nur gehört werden, sondern ihnen auch jene Stellung eingeräumt wird, die ihnen aufgrund ihrer Unverzichtbarkeit zukommt. Es sind daher ausreichende Grundlagen zu schaffen, die Kunst- und Kulturakteur*innen ein Auskommen in einem ihre Arbeit wertschätzenden Umfeld ermöglichen“ – so die Präambel des Schlusskommuniqués.

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ÜBEREINKOMMEN über den Schutz und die Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen

2005 von der UNESCO verabschiedet

2006 von Österreich ratifiziert

151 Vertragsparteien (150 Staaten und die Europäische Union)

120 Projekte, die das kulturelle Schaffen strukturell stärken, in

62 Ländern des Globalen Süden durch den „Internationalen Fonds für kulturelle Vielfalt“ ermöglicht

166 nationale Umsetzungsberichte öffentlich zugänglich, darunter

3 Umsetzungsberichte Österreichs (2012, 2016 und 2020)

ÖUK Rolle: Nationale Kontaktstelle zum Übereinkommen

ÖUK Schwerpunkte: Information und Beratung, Dialogforen zur interministeriellen Koordinierung und Einbindung der Zivilgesellschaft, Vertretung Österreichs im Rahmen der UNESCO-Organe zum Übereinkommen, Öffentlichkeitsarbeit

• **Kunstfreiheit: Fellowship kùltùř gemma!**

Mit Start im November 2021 vergab die ÖUK ein sechsmonatiges kùltùř gemma! Fellowship zum Arbeitsschwerpunkt Künstlerische Freiheit. Das Fellowship ist mit 1.300 Euro (Stipendium kùltùř gemma!) monatlich dotiert und bietet einer/einem Kunst- bzw. Kulturakteur*in, die/der sich, den Intentionen von kùltùř gemma! entsprechend, selbst als Migrant*in oder Person of Color definiert, die Möglichkeit, ein Projekt im Bereich Künstlerische Freiheit zu entwickeln. Daria Tchapanova, kùltùř gemma! Fellow, setzte sich in einem Videoprojekt mit künstlerischer Mobilität auseinander mit dem Ziel, Mobilitätsbarrieren durch Stimmen von Künstler*innen und Kulturarbeiter*innen sichtbar zu machen. Denn: Künstlerische Freiheit ist nicht gleich Kunstfreiheit. Sie ist weitreichend und betrifft u.a. auch die Mobilität von Künstler*innen und Kulturarbeiter*innen. Die Realität zeigt jedoch, dass Künstler*innen aus EU-Drittstaaten aufgrund von bürokratischen und strukturellen Herausforderungen Schwierigkeiten haben, ihre Arbeit in Österreich frei auszuüben.

• **Digitale Transformation: Faire Kultur im Netz**

2019 veröffentlichte die UNESCO eine Digital Roadmap zur Umsetzung des *Übereinkommens über den Schutz und die Förderung der Vielfalt kultureller Ausdrucksformen*. Diese dient als Richtwert für die Vertragsstaaten für die Umsetzung der Konvention im digitalen Zeitalter. 2021 führte Dr.ⁱⁿ Laura Wiesböck für die Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission eine Analyse zum Status Quo der Umsetzung in Österreich durch. Die Ergebnisse der Analyse sollen den Ansatz für eine National Roadmap im Sinne der UNESCO-Konvention bilden und wurden im Zuge eines online Expert*innenworkshops am 14. Dezember 2021 zum Thema „Faire digitale Zukunft für Kunst und Kultur“ präsentiert und diskutiert. Die Open Roadmap richtet sich zwar in erster Linie an staatliche Akteur*innen, doch ist es auch wichtig anzuerkennen, dass Expert*innen der Zivilgesellschaft bereits zur Umsetzung beitragen bzw. dass Expert*innen in Zukunft einen wertvollen Beitrag dafür leisten können. Die Zusammenarbeit zwischen Akteur*innen im Kunst- und Kultursektor und aus der Kultur- und Kreativwirtschaft im digitalen Umfeld wurde durch diesen Austausch gestärkt und trägt somit nachhaltig zur Weiterentwicklung von Maßnahmen bei.

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Dekolonialisierung bedeutet Wiederherstellung der Menschlichkeit

Wieso sprechen wir von Dekolonialisierung? Warum brauchen wir dekoloniale Strategien? Ein Gespräch zwischen Sara Hassan und Jumoke Sanwo, Teilnehmer*innen des Forum Fair Culture, gibt Einblick in die Vielschichtigkeit des (Post-)Kolonialen.

Sara: Ich habe den Eindruck, dass der Begriff „Dekolonialisierung“ zu einem regelrechten Trend geworden ist. Plötzlich behaupten alle Institutionen, dass sie dies oder jenes machen, alles ist plötzlich intersektional und dekolonial. Wenn ich solche Behauptungen höre, möchte ich genau hinschauen und die Frage stellen: Was exakt wollt ihr tun? Wollt ihr wirklich und tatsächlich dekolonialisierend arbeiten? Oder wollt ihr nur, dass es so aussieht als ob?

Jumoke: Das ist eine wirklich interessante Frage – wir blicken ja immer aus dem Kontext unserer eigenen

Realitäten auf Dekolonialisierung. Ich beispielsweise lebe in Lagos, in Westafrika. Deshalb hat dieser Begriff für mich eine andere Konnotation als für jemanden, die/der eine völlig andere Realität hat – selbst innerhalb der selben geographischen „Konstruktion“. Zentral ist es daher die Frage zu stellen, was „dekolonial“ eigentlich bedeutet. Um überhaupt in dieses Gespräch einsteigen zu können, müssen wir uns auf gemeinsame Annahmen einigen. Mit welchen Aspekten der Dekolonialisierung wollen wir uns beschäftigen? Du bist in New York, Sara, ich bin in Lagos.

Die Kolonisierung der Welt als Ganzes hatte – und hat – einen tiefgreifenden Einfluss darauf, wie sich Menschen bewegen, denken und sprechen.

Sara: Ja! Diese Ebenen, die du gerade aufgezeigt hast, erlauben uns einen Einblick in die Multitude der kolonialen Praktiken. Das ist es, worum es wirklich geht. Das ist es, was ich Menschen fragen möchte, die behaupten, sie möchten dies oder jenes „dekolonialisieren“: Seid ihr wirklich bereit anzuerkennen, dass die Kolonisierung der Welt einen tiefgreifenden Einfluss darauf hatte – und immer noch hat – wie Menschen sich bewegen, denken und sprechen? Wenn man diese Fragen stellt, macht sich eine gewisse Anspannung bemerkbar. Es wird die Angst bestimmter Institutionen spürbar, wenn sie realisieren, dass am Ende des Tages möglicherweise nicht viel übrigbleibt, wenn sie alle diese Ebenen von imperialistischer Gewalt ansprechen. Wenn sie sich wirklich selbst dekolonialisieren.

Jumoke: Ich finde es großartig, was du gerade gesagt hast. Außerdem finde ich es sehr interessant darüber nachzudenken, wo dieser dringliche Wunsch nach Dekolonialisierung herkommt.

Sara: Ja, wenn wir uns dekolonialen Praktiken und Ansätzen widmen, die aus einem hegemonialen Raum, einem Machtraum, kommen, geht es häufig nicht wirklich darum, der „anderen“ Person zu ermöglichen, der Mensch zu sein, der sie wirklich ist, eine Person mit Handlungsmacht. Innerhalb dieser hegemonialen Praktiken soll das kolonialisierte Subjekt dem Kolonisierenden den Ausweg zeigen.

Die bloße Rückgabe eines Gegenstands löst kein Problem.

Jumoke: Tatsächlich muss die Dekolonialisierung in verschiedenen Schritten verlaufen. Sie muss viele verschiedene Phasen durchlaufen – und hat noch nicht einmal begonnen. Wir sehen aktuell viele Diskurse, auch an Kunst- und Kulturorten. Es gibt etwa diesen

„drive“ Gegenstände zurückzuführen, die (durch den Imperialismus) geplündert wurden. Aber die wirkliche Herausforderung ist: Was ist mit der Kultur „auf dem Kontinent“ geschehen? Was ist das Verhältnis der Menschen zu den Gegenständen, die gestohlen wurden? Einfach nur den Gegenstand als solchen zurückzubringen, löst kein Problem. Es ist ein Akt, der das Gewissen der „Kolonisierer*innen“ beruhigt, aber sehr wenig Bedeutung für die Kolonisierten hat. Ich stehe diesem „drive“ zur Dekolonialisierung sehr skeptisch gegenüber.

Sara: Das ist der Kern des Problems, weil es nichts wiederherstellt, sondern eine Verlängerung der Machtverhältnisse ist. Es muss darüber nachgedacht werden, wie Gerechtigkeit wiederhergestellt werden kann.

Jumoke: Und dann ist da auch der wirtschaftliche Faktor. Die Artefakte generierten Einkommen. Der Wert einiger dieser Artefakte wurde mittlerweile in digitale Ressourcen umgewandelt. Wenn ein Objekt hundert Jahre lang in einem Museum Wertschöpfung generiert hat, welcher Prozentsatz sollte zurückgezahlt werden?

Sara: Das ist ungemein bezeichnend, weil die Artefakte ohne den Prozess, den Weg und den Fluss des Kapitals eigentlich nicht so viel bedeuten. Wenn wir über Dekolonialisierung sprechen, müssen wir über Geld sprechen. Wir müssen über Kapital sprechen.

Jumoke: Wir müssen ernsthafte Gespräche über Entwicklung führen, auch im kulturellen Umfeld, in dem ich sehr involviert bin. Welches ökonomische System beeinflusst aktuell den kulturellen Raum? Die Regierung, lokale Behörden investieren nicht in die Kultur. Was unternimmt die UNESCO hier zum Beispiel? Wir müssen anfangen darüber zu reden, welcher Budgetanteil in den Bereich der kulturellen Entwicklung fließt. Und was ist mit Kulturpolitiken? Ich glaube, das letzte Mal wurde hier (in Lagos, Nigeria) in den 1980ern oder so in diesem Bereich etwas verändert. Wie können wir sicherstellen, dass die

Kulturpolitik up to date bleibt, dass sie die aktuellen Bedürfnisse der Szene adressiert?

Dekolonialisierung des Herzens

Sara: Ich bin sehr beeindruckt von – ich schätze, es ist auch noch meine Generation – jüngeren Aktivist*innen. Sie sind sehr wortgewandt, sehr selbstbewusst, sehr kraftvoll. Aber ich bin manchmal besorgt, dass wir jetzt, wo wir all diese wunderbaren Werkzeuge haben – viele Linsen, viele sehr scharfe Messer –, um durch all diese Ebenen der systemischen Unterdrückung zu schneiden, uns zu wenig der Frage stellen, wie wir diese Werkzeuge nutzen. Vielleicht auch gegeneinander? Wie können wir wirklich Kollektive aufbauen, in denen Gewalt nicht reproduziert wird? Der einzige Ausweg besteht darin, in Kollektiven zu arbeiten und der Idee des Teilens und Eroberns zu widerstehen. Alle sprechen von der Dekolonialisierung des Verstandes, aber manchmal frage ich mich, wie es mit der Dekolonialisierung des Herzens aussieht.

Jumoke: Absolut, ich stimme dir vollkommen zu. Ich denke, im Grunde muss die Existenz der Seele im öffentlichen Diskurs einen Raum bekommen. Wir haben bei Revolving Art Incubator Programme wie „Words as therapy“ (Worte als Therapie), die den Menschen sehr geholfen haben, indem sie Poesie als Mittel zur Heilung und zur Verbindung mit ihrer Menschlichkeit eingesetzt haben. Denn am Ende des Tages muss man erkennen, dass wir zur Menschlichkeit zurückkehren müssen. Das imperiale Projekt hat sich des Kontinents unter anderem dadurch bemächtigt, dass die Menschen als „Wilde“ betrachtet wurden. Es nahm ihnen ihre Menschlichkeit und objektivierte sie. Ist der Globale Norden bereit, sich auf die Menschen im Globalen Süden als Menschen einzulassen? Wenn er dazu bereit ist, ändert sich die Interaktion völlig. Und wir bräuchten nicht einmal lange Gespräche darüber

zu führen, was es bedeutet, zu dekolonialisieren. Was Dekolonialisierung bedeutet, ist die Wiederherstellung der Menschlichkeit im öffentlichen Diskurs im Globalen Norden und Süden. Das ist alles. Das ist ganz einfach.

Die Initiative Forum Fair Culture, ein gemeinsames Projekt von kulturen in bewegung/VIDC und der österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission, eröffnete den Raum, über Machtverhältnisse in der internationalen Kulturpolitik nachzudenken. Die Organisator*innen des Forums haben ein ausführliches Gespräch mit Sara Hassan und Jumoke Sanwo geführt, von dem hier Auszüge abgedruckt werden. Die Langversion des Textes findet sich in der Publikation „Kritische Vielfalt – Reflexionen des Forum Fair Culture“ unter www.unesco.at/publikationen

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JUMOKÉ SANWO ist visual storyteller und Kulturproduzentin aus Lagos, Nigeria. Sie hat einen Bachelor of Arts (B.A.) in Anglistik von der Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-ife in Nigeria. Als Künstlerin arbeitet sie hauptsächlich in den Bereichen Fotografie, Videokunst und virtuelle Realität. Ihre Arbeit reflektiert die Selbstwahrnehmung und die durch Zeit und Raum erfahrene Trennung, während sie sich mit dem Diskurs über Räumlichkeit und Zeitlichkeit in postkolonialen Gesellschaften auseinandersetzt.

IMMATERIELLES KULTURERBE

Kreativität, Identität, Kontinuität

Immaterielles Kulturerbe ist überall. Im Leben vieler Menschen spielt eine Tradition, ein Brauch oder eine Wissensform eine wichtige Rolle. Dazu gehören für manche zum Beispiel: das Traismaurer Krippenspiel, der Manuelle Bilddruck, die Herstellung der Bregenzerwälder Juppe oder das Gautschen. Den genannten Beispielen ist gemeinsam, dass sie Teil des lebendigen Kulturerbes in Österreich sind. Immaterielles Kulturerbe, wie es die UNESCO versteht, umfasst weite Bereiche, darunter kulturelle Praktiken, Rituale, Erfahrungswissen und meisterliches Handwerk. Jeder dieser Bereiche beinhaltet eine Vielfalt an Traditionen, die für die Identität der Ausübenden und die gesamte Gesellschaft von Bedeutung sind. Die *Konvention zur Erhaltung des immateriellen Kulturerbes* (2003), die Österreich 2009 ratifiziert hat, bringt genau diese Vielfalt zum Vorschein. Dabei stehen die Menschen, die das mit den Bräuchen verbundene Wissen tragen, im Mittelpunkt.

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Historische Maltechnik

Das Nationale Verzeichnis des Immateriellen Kulturerbes

Das Nationale Verzeichnis macht die Vielfalt des gelebten kulturellen Erbes sichtbar. Es beschreibt nicht nur den Ablauf oder den Inhalt der Tradition, sondern auch seine Bedeutung für die Identität der Träger*innen, zeigt gelungene Modelle im Umgang mit Ressourcen auf und liefert Anregungen zur nachhaltigen Lebensgestaltung. Das Verzeichnis wurde 2010 eröffnet und trägt mit seinen mittlerweile 147 Einträgen zu einem besseren Verständnis der erstaunlichen Diversität an lebendigem Wissen und Praktiken in Österreich bei.

Ein interdisziplinärer Fachbeirat für das immaterielle Kulturerbe entscheidet regelmäßig über die Aufnahme von Traditionen in das Verzeichnis und über etwaige Nominierungen von nationalen Elementen für eine der drei internationalen UNESCO-Listen.

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Gautschen

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Herstellung der Bregenzerwälder Juppen und das Tragen der Frauentracht

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• Internationale Nominierungen und Aufnahmen

Am 31. März 2021 wurde der UNESCO die Flößerei als Eintragung für die Repräsentative Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes vorgeschlagen. Die Einreichung entstand aus einem internationalen Zusammenschluss der Flößer*innen aus Deutschland, Lettland, Polen, Spanien und Tschechien. Voraussetzung für die Einreichung auf internationaler Ebene ist die entsprechende nationale Listung des Elements in den beteiligten Ländern. In Österreich ist das Wissen um die Flößerei auf der oberen Drau seit 2014 im nationalen Verzeichnis; 150 Flößer*innen, Freiwillige und Vereine sind an der Erhaltung des Kulturerbes beteiligt.

Das Jahr 2021 stand aber auch im Zeichen der Traditionellen Bewässerung. Ausgehend von der Tiroler Rieselbewässerung wird unter der Federführung Österreichs ein Antrag für die Repräsentative Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes vorbereitet. An der multinationalen Einreichung beteiligen sich Träger*innen, Expert*innen und NGOs aus Belgien, Deutschland, Italien, Luxemburg, den Niederlanden und der Schweiz. Zwischen Dezember 2020 und März 2021 fanden regelmäßige Online-Workshops statt, die in einem gemeinsamen Austauschtreffen im Oktober 2021 in Zams, Tirol, kumulierten. Dort wurde gemeinsam an den Bewerbungsunterlagen gearbeitet sowie allen Beteiligten die Tiroler Rieselbewässerung nähergebracht. Die Abgabe der Einreichung ist für März 2022 geplant.

• Aufnahmen in das nationale Verzeichnis

2021 wurde das Verzeichnis des immateriellen Kulturerbes in Österreich um 14 Elemente erweitert, die im Juli im Rahmen der Urkundenverleihung in Obertraun am Hallstättersee präsentiert wurden:

- Alpinistisches Wissen und Können der Berg- & Schiführer*innen (österreichweit)
- Flammen von Keramik (Oberösterreich)
- Frack-Maßschneiderei (österreichweit)
- Garnierspenzer, Hut und Steppmieder (Salzburg)
- Gautschen (österreichweit)
- Historische und dekorative Malerhandwerkstechniken mit traditionellen Materialien (österreichweit)
- Herstellung der Bregenzerwälder Juppen und das Tragen der Frauentracht (Vorarlberg)
- Krippenbrauch in Österreich (österreichweit)
- Manueller Bilddruck (österreichweit)
- Traismaurer Krippenspiel (Niederösterreich)
- Das Trockensteinmauern (österreichweit)
- Südböhmische Blasmusik in Brand-Nagelberg (Niederösterreich)
- Das Wissen der Handwerksmüller*innen (Burgenland, Kärnten, Niederösterreich, Oberösterreich, Salzburg, Steiermark, Tirol, Vorarlberg)
- Anklöpfeln in Stans (Tirol)

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Urkundenverleihung in Obertraun

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Bergführer*innen unterwegs in den Stubaier Alpen

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Frack-Maßschneiderei

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Immaterielles Kulturerbe und die Verringerung der Auswirkungen von Naturkatastrophen (SDG 11.5) Die Weiterentwicklung jahrhundertealten Wissens zum Umgang und zur Einschätzung von Naturgefahren und Gegebenheiten stärkt die Anpassungsfähigkeit gegenüber klimabedingten Gefahren und Naturkatastrophen. Das „Erfahrungswissen im Umgang mit Lawinengefahr“ (Aufnahme in die Repräsentative Liste des Immateriellen Kulturerbes der Menschheit 2018) oder das „Alpinistische Wissen und Können der Berg- und Schiführer*innen“ (aufgenommen 2021) werden seit vielen Generationen mündlich überliefert, weiterentwickelt und heutzutage durch Professionalisierung und wissenschaftliche Forschungen ergänzt. Dieses stets dem Naturwandel angepasste Wissen trägt zum sicheren und nachhaltigen Umgang mit der Natur im Alpenraum bei.

• Schwerpunkt Immaterielles Kulturerbe und Bildung

Die Erhaltung des immateriellen Kulturerbes lebt vom kreativen Prozess der Weitergabe von Generation zu Generation und ist eng mit Bildungs- und Vermittlungsfragen verknüpft.

2021 fand in Kooperation mit der UNESCO, der EU und dem UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet) ein Online-Workshop statt, in dem Bildungsmaterialien für deutschsprachige Pädagog*innen vorgestellt wurden. Diese veranschaulichen, wie man nicht nur über, sondern vor allem mit IKE den Unterricht gestalten und es greifbar machen kann. Auch das österreichische Projekt „*Teaching and learning with living heritage. Design and creation of a „Glöcklerkappe“*“ wurde dabei vorgestellt. Die Präsentation wurde durch einen weiteren Workshop im Herbst ergänzt, welcher Traditionsträger*innen und Lehrpersonen zusammenführte und zum Austausch über mögliche Kooperationen anregen sollte.

Screenshot der Vorstellung des Toolkits der UNESCO für Lehrpersonen

• Staatenbericht

Der sogenannte Staatenbericht ist einer der Schlüsselmechanismen des Übereinkommens, sowohl in Hinblick auf nationale Fortschritte als auch für die internationale Zusammenarbeit. Durch ihn profitieren Staaten und Gemeinschaften von den Erfahrungen anderer Vertragsstaaten und tauschen Informationen über wirksame Erhaltungsmaßnahmen und -strategien aus. Der Bericht vermittelt ein Gesamtbild der vergangenen Jahre und macht die Aktivitäten Österreichs im Sinne der Konvention sichtbar. Es handelt sich, nach 2015, um den 2. österreichischen Staatenbericht für die Konvention von 2003. Er reflektiert die innerstaatliche Umsetzung der Konvention und erarbeitet eine zukunftsorientierte Vorgehensweise. Besonderes Augenmerk wird bei der Erstellung auf den Input und die Rückmeldung der einzelnen Träger*innen und verschiedener Stakeholder auf nationaler, regionaler und lokaler Ebene gelegt. Die ÖUK fungierte hier als koordinierende Stelle.

ÜBEREINKOMMEN zur Erhaltung des immateriellen Kulturerbes

2003	von der UNESCO-Generalkonferenz angenommen
2009	von Österreich ratifiziert
180	Vertragsstaaten
529	Elemente auf der Repräsentativen Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes der Menschheit
71	Elemente auf der Liste des dringend erhaltungsbedürftigen immateriellen Kulturerbes
29	bewährte Programme, Projekte und Tätigkeiten zur Erhaltung des immateriellen Kulturerbes
147	Elemente im Nationalen Verzeichnis des immateriellen Kulturerbes in Österreich

ÖUK Rolle: Bewusstseinsbildung für die Erhaltung, Vermittlung und Förderung des immateriellen Kulturerbes in Österreich, Erstellung des Nationalen Verzeichnisses

ÖUK Themen 2021: Neuaufnahme von 14 Elementen in das Nationale Verzeichnis des IKE; Schwerpunkte: IKE und Bildung; Wissen um Natur und Universum; Internationale Kooperationen

- **Kooperation mit dem Sudan: Digitales Nationales Verzeichnis**
Im Rahmen des UNESCO Projekts *Strengthening national capacities for safeguarding intangible cultural heritage in Sudan* wurde von der ÖUK gemeinsam mit dem UNESCO-Field Office Khartoum und der Sudanesischen UNESCO-Kommission ein digitales Verzeichnis des Immateriellen Kulturerbes des Sudan erstellt. Die ÖUK hat dafür, gemeinsam mit einem Experten, die technischen Grundlagen aufbereitet sowie, in enger Absprache mit nationalen Stakeholdern im Sudan, die redaktionelle Gestaltung betreut.

Sudanesisches Verzeichnis – Website

- **International**
Im Laufe des Jahres 2021 nahm Österreich an einer UNESCO-Arbeitsgruppe zur lang erwarteten Reflexion der internationalen Listen teil. Darin wurden unter anderem Verbesserungen für den Einreichprozess sowie den Prozess zur Entfernung von Elementen von der Liste besprochen sowie die Bewältigung der steigenden Anzahl von Einreichungen für diese Listen diskutiert. Die Ergebnisse wurden während der 16. Sitzung des zwischenstaatlichen Komitees verabschiedet.

Das Wissen und die Praktiken, die sich im Laufe der Zeit angesammelt haben, werden genutzt, um natürliche Ressourcen nachhaltig zu nutzen und die Auswirkungen des Klimawandels zu minimieren. Das immaterielle Kulturerbe kann zum Schutz der biologischen Vielfalt und zur ökologischen Nachhaltigkeit beitragen.

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Traditionelle Bewässerung – eine Praxis die verbindet

Traditionsträger*innen aus Österreich, Belgien, Deutschland, Italien, Luxemburg, den Niederlanden und der Schweiz arbeiteten über das gesamte Jahr hinweg gemeinsam am Antrag für die internationale Repräsentative Liste des Immateriellen Kulturerbes der Menschheit. Was ist aber traditionelle Bewässerung, und warum ist sie nicht nur für die Traditionsträger*innen wichtig, sondern auch für die Region, in der sie ausgeübt wird? Karina Liechi von der Stiftung Landschaftsschutz Schweiz gibt einen Einblick in diese wichtige Form des immateriellen Kulturerbes, das so viele Länder und Menschen miteinander verbindet.

witteren, flüxen, rieseln, wassern, fléizen, bevloeiën, irriguer par ruissellement, wässru...

Die traditionelle Bewässerung ist eine jahrhundertealte Bewässerungsart, die ein optimales Wachstum der Kulturpflanzen anstrebt. Sie beruht in den Ebenen wie auch an Hanglagen auf der gezielten Nutzung der Schwerkraft und auf manuell angelegten Infrastrukturen wie Kanälen und Gräben, um Wasser aus Quellen, Gletschern, Bächen oder Flüssen näher an be-

wirtschaftete Flächen zu bringen. Durch Aufstauung des Wassers wird ein Überlauf geschaffen, womit die landwirtschaftlichen Flächen berie-selt werden können. Gleichzeitig wird auch eine natürliche Bodenbildung und Düngewirkung erzielt. Die Bewässerung ist eine aufwändige, auf großer Erfahrung beruhende Tätigkeit. Im Oberwallis (Schweiz) – beispielsweise – dienen Wasserplatten, Holzbretter und Steinplatten dem Wässerer oder der Wässererin zur Stauung und Lenkung des Wassers, das dann mit der

„Wasserhau“ (Wässerbeil) über die Wiesen „gezogen“ wird¹. Unterhalb der Wiesen muss schließlich das überschüssige „Zettwasser“ wieder weggeleitet werden. Dafür ist ein tiefes Verständnis der Landschaft, der Wetterbedingungen, der Topographie und des Wasserflusses erforderlich.

...und noch viel mehr:

Die Praxis der traditionellen Bewässerung geht über die reine Bereitstellung (Fassung, Weiterleitung und

¹ Schweizer R, Rodewald R, Liechi K, Knoepfel P. 2014. Des systèmes d'irrigation alpins entre gouvernance communautaire et étatique - Alpine Bewässerungssysteme zwischen Genossenschaft und Staat. Zürich/Chur: Rüeegg.

Stauung des Wassers mit Wässerplatte

Aufstauung des Wassers auf der Malser Haide,
Italien

Verteilung) von Wasser hinaus²: Sie ist ein komplexes sozio-ökologisches System, bei welchem Faktoren wie kollektive Organisationsform mit festgelegten Regeln hinsichtlich Zuteilung des Wassers, Rechten und Pflichten sowie die konstante Erneuerung des über Generationen verfeinerten Wissens und die damit einhergehende kulturelle Verankerung in lokalen und regionalen Identitäten und Traditionen ebenso wichtig sind. Große Aufgaben, wie der Bau von Kanälen, werden in der Regel gemeinschaftlich unter den betroffenen Wassernutzenden, welche in Körperschaften zusammengeschlossen sind,

organisiert. Die Wasserzuteilung an die primär landwirtschaftlichen Nutzer*innen erfolgt nach allseits anerkannten, verbrieften Wasserrechten und einem festgelegten Turnus (der sogenannten Kehrordnung; siehe dazu den Auszug aus einer historischen Kehrordnung). Der Unterhalt der Bewässerungsanlagen (Fassung, Kanäle, Verteilungssysteme etc.) erfolgt zumeist in gemeinsamer Arbeit (dem sogenannten Gemeinwerk). Heute sind allerdings auch die Mitarbeit und Unterstützung der öffentlichen Hand und von weiteren Organisationen gefragt und notwendig.

Vorkommen in Europa

Die traditionelle Bewässerung kommt sowohl im Flachland als auch im Gebirge und entsprechend in den meisten Ländern Europas, selbst in Nordeuropa, vor. Es existiert eine sehr hohe Vielfalt an Systemen, von traditionell bis modern, klein- bis großräumig, genutzt und im Zustand des Verfalls. Im Rahmen einer Inventarisierung traditioneller Bewässerungsvorkommen in Europa konnte bisher an 130 Standorten traditionelle Bewässerung als historisch belegt, in Landschafts- und Kulturrelikten erhalten oder als aktuell noch praktizierte Form der Landbewirtschaftung nachgewiesen werden⁴. Wurde sie vor der Erfindung moderner Sprinkleranlagen oder elektrischer Pumpen noch weitflächig eingesetzt, sind heute nur wenige traditionell bewässerte Gebiete erhalten geblieben.

Vielfältige Bedeutungen der traditionellen Bewässerung

Nebst ihrer primären landwirtschaftlichen Bedeutung hat die traditionelle Bewässerung vielfältige weitere Funktionen. Dank dem Bau von Kanälen, Schleusen oder Schöpfprädern und der Stau- oder Hangbewässerung entstand vielerorts ein Mosaik von trockenen und feuchteren Standorten, artenreichen Flächen und damit eine Vielzahl von Lebensräumen und Landschaftsqualitäten. Die Bewässerungslandschaften bieten zudem ein attraktives Landschaftserlebnis und werden entsprechend auch vermehrt touristisch genutzt. In gebirgigen Regionen befeuchten Wasserkanäle den Bergwald und stabilisieren dadurch die Hänge, liefern Wasser zur Waldbrandbekämpfung und dienen durch die Regulierung und Ableitung von Oberflächenwasser der Hochwasserprävention. Die oftmals eigentümlichen Bauwerke der Wasser-

Workshop in Zams im Oktober 2021

² Leibundgut C, Kohn I. 2014. European traditional irrigation in transition part I: Irrigation in times past – a historic land use practice across Europe. *Irrigation and Drainage*, 63(3), 273–93.

³ ⁴ Leibundgut C, Vonderstrass I. 2016. Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe Europas. Langenthal: Merkur.

Auszug aus der historischen Wasserverordnung der neuen Wasserleitung Niwärch, 1381 (Ausserberg, Schweiz)

Die Geteilen (=Mitglieder einer Körperschaft) der neuen Wasserleitung Niwärch beschliessen im Jahre 1381 unter Beisein des Klerikers Nycolinus von Mohlhusen aus der Diözese München folgende Wasserverordnung⁵:

1) Johannes Tufecher am Bort soll an der Wasserleitung das Recht auf einen halben Tag und eine halbe Nacht haben. Die Erben des verstorbenen Johannes Mathien von Baltschieder einen Viertel. Hans, Sohn des verst. Furers am Ranfte, einen Viertel. Petrus am Troyen... (weitere Aufzählung; Turnus von 14 Tagen);

2) Das Wasser soll wie oben verteilt von einem zum anderen weitergehen;

3) Es wurde entschieden, dass bei einem Bruch der Wasserleitung, an welchem Tag und zu welcher Stunde das auch geschieht, der Geteile sein Wasser bekommt, sobald die Leitung wieder hergestellt ist;

4) Wer jetzt oder in Zukunft einen Anteil an der Wasserleitung hat, muss seine Arbeit leisten oder für ein Tagwerk sieben Denare zahlen, nach dem Mass wie es ihn trifft.

Wenn einer die Arbeit nicht leistet (...), dann dürfen die Geteilen den Fehlenden bestrafen, indem sie einen anderen anstellen, ohne dass der Richter oder sonst jemand Einspruch erheben darf;

5) Wenn die Wasserleitung durch höhere Gewalt bricht (...), muss jetzt und in Zukunft jeder Geteile seine Arbeit leisten, nach dem Anteil, den er hat. Sonst muss er für ein Tagwerk zehn Denare zahlen.

zuführung und -verteilung, die auf viel Handarbeit beruhenden traditionellen Bewässerungstechniken und die gemeinschaftliche Verwaltung und Bewirtschaftung mit ihren tradierten Regeln und Bräuchen sind aber auch wertvolle Zeugen einer regional vielfältigen Kulturgeschichte und Baukultur. Die traditionelle Bewässerung hat daher eine wichtige Bedeutung für die regionale Identität und repräsentiert ein lebendiges und wertvolles Kulturerbe⁵.

Schließlich ermöglicht die traditionelle Bewässerungspraxis einen breiten Einbezug auch der nicht-landwirtschaftlichen Bevölkerung: Frauen wie Männer, Kinder, Jugendliche und ganze Familien, Einheimische wie Menschen mit Migrationshintergrund nehmen an freiwilligen Arbeitseinsätzen teil. Zudem ist die traditionelle Bewässerung ein interessantes Studienobjekt und eine Bewässerungsregion auch ein Ort der Bildung für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung.

⁵ Bär R, Liechti K. 2020. Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe mit Zukunft? Naters/Bern: Einblicke-Ausblicke.

⁶ Wasserverordnung – Neuwerk 1381; übersetzt aus dem Lateinischen am 31. Mai 1981 von Emil Schmid, Pfarrer; aus: SAC Ortsgruppe Ausserberg. 1981. 600 Jahre Wasserleitung Niwärch 1381–1981, Ausserberg. Visp: nbv Druck.

Internationale Kooperation und Einreichung bei der UNESCO

Daher haben sich noch aktive Gemeinschaften aus sieben europäischen Ländern für einen gemeinsamen Antrag für die Repräsentative Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes zusammengeschlossen. Bereits seit vielen Jahren gibt es Bestrebungen, noch aktive Wässer*innen und weitere Beteiligte zusammenzubringen und stillgelegte Bewässerungsanlagen zu reaktivieren. Der internationale Austausch hilft dabei, die traditionelle Bewässerung wiederzubeleben, Akteur*innen in ihrer Arbeit zu unterstützen und Wissen kontinuierlich auszubauen. Die internationale Kooperation ermöglichte auch die Initiierung eines Internationalen Zentrums der traditionellen Bewässerung in Europa IZTB, welches im Herbst 2022 in der Schweiz eröffnet werden soll.

Der Antrag mit dem Titel „Traditionelle Bewässerung in Europa: Wissen, Technik und Organisation“ wird im Jahr 2022 bei der UNESCO zur Aufnahme in die Repräsentative Liste des immateriellen Kulturerbes der Menschheit eingereicht. Grundlage des Textes ist unter anderem der Antrag an die UNESCO, an dem eine Vielzahl von Personen aus den beteiligten Ländern mitgearbeitet haben.

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WELTERBE

Bewusstsein für außergewöhnliche universelle Werte schaffen

Die Bewahrung des gemeinsamen Kultur- und Naturerbes der Welt ist seit 1972 das erklärte Ziel des *Übereinkommens zum Schutz des Kultur- und Naturerbes der Welt* (kurz: Welterbekonvention). Dabei zählen neben dem konkreten Schutz der außergewöhnlichen, universellen Werte der mittlerweile 1.154 Welterbestätten auch Vermittlung

und Bewusstseinsbildung zu den Aufgaben und Pflichten der Vertragsstaaten, die die Konvention ratifiziert haben. Österreich hat sich mit der Unterzeichnung des Übereinkommens 1992 dazu verpflichtet, seine einzigartigen Zeugnisse der Kultur- und Naturgeschichte im Sinne der gesamten Menschheit für kommende Generationen zu bewahren.

Die Rolle der Konvention als eines der bedeutendsten internationalen Rechtsinstrumente im Bereich des Kulturgüter- und Naturschutzes spiegelt sich in ihrer beinahe vollständigen universellen Gültigkeit wider: mittlerweile 194 Vertragsstaaten erkennen die im Übereinkommen formulierten Rechte und Pflichten an. Wie wichtig dieses globale Commitment zum kooperativen Schutz des gemeinsamen Erbes ist, wird angesichts der immer zahlreicher werdenden Bedrohungen dieser Kultur- und Naturstätten deutlich. Die greifbar werdenden Folgen der Klimakrise haben ebenso unmittelbare Auswirkungen auf den Erhalt von Welterbestätten, wie sich immer weiter intensivierender wirtschaftlicher Druck.

Wenngleich das Jahr 2021 im Vergleich zum vorangegangenen Jahr in vielerlei Hinsicht Erleichterungen mit sich brachte, waren die auf die globale Gesundheitskrise zurückzuführenden Herausforderungen nach wie vor beträchtlich. Neben wirtschaftlichen Implikationen, die auch unmittelbare Auswirkungen auf den Erhalt von Welterbestätten haben, war auch die Zugänglichkeit zu diesen Kultur- und Naturdenkmälern stark reduziert. Die zahlreichen Initiativen im virtuellen Raum konnten das physische Erleben dieser einzigartigen Orte, das über weite Strecken des Jahres eingeschränkt war, und die damit verbundene Wertebildung nur bedingt ersetzen.

Für Österreich hatte das Jahr allerdings auch erfreuliche Facetten: neben der erfolgreichen Vertiefung der Zusammenarbeit konnte der Kreis der österreichischen Welterbestätten um zwei neue Zugänge erweitert werden. Mit der Aufnahme der „Great Spa Towns of Europe“ sowie des „Donaulimes“ als Teil der „Grenzen des Römischen Reiches“ kann Österreich nun 12 Welterbestätten verzeichnen.

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ÜBEREINKOMMEN zum Schutz des Kultur- und Naturerbes der Welt

- 1972 von der UNESCO verabschiedet
- 1992 von Österreich ratifiziert
- 194 Vertragsstaaten
- 1.154 Welterbestätten weltweit
- 12 Welterbestätten in Österreich

ÖUK Rolle: Geschäftsstelle der Österreichischen Welterbestätten-Konferenz, unterstützende Funktion, Information und Beratung

ÖUK Schwerpunkte: Vernetzung der österreichischen Welterbe-Akteur*innen, Welterbe-Bildung, Bewusstseinsbildung

➤ **Welterbe Donaulimes:** Das sogenannte „Heidentor“ in Carnuntum (NÖ) zählt zu den besterhaltenen antiken Baudenkmalern in Österreich und zeugt von der Bedeutung der antiken Stadt.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 11: Zur Nachhaltigkeit von Städten und Siedlungen leistet die Welterbekonvention einen Beitrag, indem sie dazu auffordert, die Anstrengungen zum Schutz und zur Wahrung des Weltkultur und -naturerbes zu verstärken (Unterziel 11.4).

SDG 13: Der Schutz von Kulturerbe trägt dazu bei, die Widerstandskraft und die Anpassungsfähigkeit gegenüber klimabedingten Gefahren und Naturkatastrophen zu stärken (Unterziel 13.1).

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• 1. Österreichischer Welterbetag

Auf Initiative der ÖUK und per Beschluss der Österreichischen Welterbestätten-Konferenz wurde am 18. April 2021 zum ersten Mal der gemeinsame „Österreichische Welterbetag“ begangen. In Anlehnung an den „International Day of Monuments and Sites“ bzw. den „International World Heritage Day“, soll der „Österreichische Welterbetag“ als gemeinsamer Aktionstag der Österreichischen Welterbestätten zur Bewusstseinsbildung für die außergewöhnlichen universellen Werte des Welterbes in Österreich und weltweit beitragen. Eine eigens für den Welterbetag eingerichtete Website (www.welterbetag.at) fungiert als gemeinsamer Webauftritt der Österreichischen Welterbestätten. Unter dem Motto „Welterbe ist mehr...“ sollen im Rahmen spezieller Veranstaltungen und Aktionen ungewohnte Blicke auf Altbekanntes ermöglicht, neue Perspektiven eröffnet und ein Eindruck von der Arbeit und den Bemühungen zum Schutz und Erhalt dieser einzigartigen Orte vermittelt werden. Wenngleich das geplante Programm aufgrund der pandemischen Situation zu großen Teilen nicht realisiert werden konnte, hat die breite mediale Resonanz auf den Tag das Interesse am Thema UNESCO-Welterbe eindrucksvoll veranschaulicht.

Nähere Informationen unter:
www.welterbetag.at

• 44. (erweiterte) Sitzung des Welterbekomitees (Fuzhou/China; online)

Vom 16.–31. Juli 2021 konnte – nach einjähriger, pandemiebedingter Pause – das Welterbe-Komitee wieder zusammentreten. Die Sitzung, die ursprünglich im Sommer 2020 in Fuzhou stattfinden hätte sollen, wurde nun unter dem Vorsitz Chinas zum ersten Mal virtuell abgehalten. Lediglich einige wenige Vertreter*innen des UNESCO-Sekretariats waren physisch vor Ort anwesend. Für Österreich war die Sitzung in mehrerlei Hinsicht von großem Interesse. Nach der erfolgreichen Einschreibung der „Great Spa Towns of Europe“ mit Baden bei Wien konnte auch der langjährige Nominierungsprozess des „Donaulimes“ positiv abgeschlossen werden. Hinsichtlich der Welterbestätte

„Historisches Zentrum von Wien“, die sich seit 2017 auf der Liste des gefährdeten Welterbes befindet, konnte mit der positiven Bestätigung des „Desired State of Conservation (DSOCR)“ durch das Komitee ein wichtiger Schritt getan werden.

• 16. Österreichische Welterbestätten-Konferenz (Schönbrunn)

Die Österreichische Welterbestätten-Konferenz ist das wichtigste nationale Forum für die Zusammenarbeit der mittlerweile 12 österreichischen Welterbestätten.

Von 13.–14. Oktober 2021 fand die im Vorjahr abgesagte 16. Österreichische Welterbestätten-Konferenz in Kooperation mit der Welterbestätte „Schloss und Gärten von Schönbrunn“ statt. Unter dem Thema „Mehr als Denkmal: Denkmalschutz und -pflege im Kontext der UNESCO-Welterbekonvention“ konnten wesentliche Diskussionen zu den Themenkomplexen der Bau- und Garten-denkmalspflege, aber auch zum Umgang mit Pufferzonenmanagement geführt werden. Im Rahmen eines abschließenden Podiumsgesprächs wurden Handlungsnotwendigkeiten für den erfolgreichen Schutz des Welterbes in Zukunft benannt.

Podiumsgespräch

Wesentlich für die serielle Welterbestätte sind die historischen Badeanlagen, etwa hier das ehemalige Josefsbad in Baden

Baden als Teil des UNESCO-Welterbes Great Spa Towns of Europe

Am 24. Juli 2021 wurden die Great Spa Towns of Europe (GSTE) in die Liste des UNESCO-Welterbes eingetragen. Für viele überraschend, erhielt Österreich dadurch eine weitere Welterbestätte: Baden bei Wien.

Der Weg zum Welterbe

Ende der 1990er Jahre äußerten mehrere Kurstädte beinahe gleichzeitig den Wunsch in die UNESCO-Liste aufgenommen zu werden. Das Welterbezentrum Paris riet zu einer seriellen Nominierung. 2012 erstellte ICOMOS Deutschland eine

thematische Studie¹, in der die Chancen für eine Nominierung des Kurstadtphänomens positiv bewertet wurden. Die beteiligten Staaten und Städte setzten für die Entwicklung der Nominierungsunterlagen, einer gemeinsamen Struktur der seriellen Stätte sowie der Koordinierung des Prozesses mehrere Arbeitsgruppen auf multinationaler und multikommunaler Ebene ein: Die International Steering Group und International Working Group mit Vertreter*innen der Ministerien und Wissenschaftler*innen aus den Staaten, die Mayor Steering Group der politischen Städtevertreter*innen und die Site Manager Group mit Expert*innen aus den Kurstädten. Koordiniert wurde der Prozess durch ein britisch besetztes Generalsekretariat. Als Lead Partner der Nominierung fungierte die Tschechische Republik.

2013 meldete das UNESCO-Welterbe Referat der Republik Österreich u.a. die Stadt Baden bei Wien als mögliche Teilnehmerin für die GSTE. 2014 und 2015 erarbeitete die International Working Group Auswahl- und Abgrenzungskriterien für eine

Teilnahme von Kurstädten an der Nominierung der GSTE, an deren Ende eine Beschränkung auf die nunmehr in die Liste des UNESCO-Welterbes eingetragenen Komponenten stand. 2016 bis 2018 wurden die Grenzen der Properties und Pufferzonen definiert, das Nominierungsdossier verfasst, thematische Karten und Atlanten erstellt, Property und Local Management Pläne entwickelt und die Kooperation der Städte auf tragfähige Fundamente gestellt. Im Jänner 2019 wurden alle Unterlagen dem Welterbezentrum in Paris übergeben und in der Folge von ICOMOS geprüft.

Anerkennung der GSTE als UNESCO-Welterbe

Durch den Pandemie-bedingten Ausfall der 44. Sitzung des Welterbe-Komitees 2020 verzögerte sich die Entscheidung des Welterbekomitees um ein Jahr. Am 24. Juli 2021 wurde der Outstanding Universal Value der GSTE anerkannt: Die Great Spa Towns of Europe sind ein außergewöhnliches Zeugnis des europäischen Kurphänomens, das von der Zeit um 1700 bis in die 1930er Jahre seinen höchsten Ausdruck fand. Diese transnationale serielle „Stätte“ umfasst elf Kurstädte in sieben Ländern: Baden bei Wien (AT); Spa (BE); Karlovy Vary, Františkovy Lázně und Mariánské Lázně (CZ); Vichy (FR), Bad Ems, Baden-Baden und Bad Kissingen (DE); Montecatini Terme (IT); und City of Bath (UK). Die Serie besteht aus den modernsten, dynamischsten und internationalsten Beispielen unter hunderten Kurstädten, die ebenfalls zum europäischen Kurphänomen beigetragen haben.

Obwohl jede Kurstadt anders strukturiert ist, haben alle Städte gemeinsam, dass sie sich um Mineralwasserquellen herum entwickelt haben, die Katalysator für ein räumliches Organisationsmodell wurden, das Heil-, Therapie-, Erholungs- und Sozialfunktionen gewidmet ist. Ensembles von Kurgebäuden umfassen Bäder, Brunnenhallen, Trinkhallen, Anlagen für die

¹ ICOMOS, Nationalkomitee der Bundesrepublik Deutschland: Europäische Kurstädte und Modebäder des 19. Jahrhunderts; ICOMOS Deutschland Hefte LI 1. Auflage Stuttgart 2012.

Kurbehandlungen und Kolonnaden, durch welche die Wasserressourcen nutzbar gemacht und deren praktische Nutzung zum Baden und Trinken ermöglicht wurden. Externe und interne Kurbehandlungen („taking the cure“) wurden durch Bewegungs- und gesellschaftliche Aktivitäten ergänzt, die Einrichtungen wie Versammlungsräume, Casinos, Theater, Hotels, Villen und zugehörige Infrastrukturen (von Wasserleitungssystemen und Salzproduktionsanlagen bis hin zu Eisenbahnen und Standseilbahnen) erforderten.

Alle Einrichtungen sind in einen städtebaulichen Gesamtkontext integriert, der ein sorgfältig verwaltetes Erholungs- und Therapieumfeld aus Parks, Gärten, Promenaden, Sportanlagen und Wäldern umfasst. Gebäude und Räume verbinden sich visuell und physisch mit der sie umgebenden Landschaft, die regelmäßig zur sportlichen Betätigung als Beitrag zur Kurtherapie, zur Entspannung und zum Vergnügen genutzt wird.

Lokales Management GSTE

Baden bei Wien

Baden hat eine lange Tradition des Schutzes seines bauhistorischen Erbes. Die Aufnahme in die Liste des Welt-erbes bringt für den sorgsam Umgang mit dem Erbe zwar eine höhere moralische Verpflichtung, aber kaum Notwendigkeit für eine Justierung von Regulativen zum Schutz der historischen Kurstadt. Welterbe ist eine Querschnittsmaterie. Dem entsprechend sieht der Lokale Managementplan eine Befassung aller Ebenen von städtischer Zivilgesellschaft, Politik und Verwaltung vor. Der Bürgermeister ist Vertreter der Stadt im GSTE Management Board und steht auch dem lokalen Welterbe-Management vor. Für die operative Umsetzung sind eine Lokale Site Managerin und der für UNESCO-Welterbefragen gewählte Stadtrat zuständig. Eine lokale Steuerungsgruppe aus Gemeindepolitik, -verwaltung, Stakeholdern und Mitgliedern des Welterbe-

Nicht nur die Bade- und Kuranlagen prägen die Stadtbilder der „Great Spa Towns of Europe“, sondern auch eine umfangreiche kulturelle Infrastruktur, z.B. Theater

© Stadt Baden/Fürnkranz

Fachbeirats wird das Bewusstseins um Verantwortung für das Welterbe bei Gesellschaft und Entscheidungsträger*innen vertiefen. Letzterer Beirat besteht aus Expert*innen zu den für den OUV relevanten Themenkreisen. Strukturen für eine breite Einbindung von Bevölkerung und Stakeholdern in das Welterbemanagement werden aufgebaut.

... not a monument, but a whole philosophy

Acht Jahre enge Zusammenarbeit haben die Vertreter*innen der elf Städte über alle Sprach- und Landesgrenzen hinweg zu einer aktiven, zukunftsorientierten Gemeinschaft zusammengeschweißt. Das Management wird einerseits von den nationalstaatlichen Vertreter*innen begleitet, andererseits besteht eine komplexe Struktur der Liga der elf GSTE-Städte, an deren Spitze deren demokratisch gewählte Bürgermeister*innen stehen. Generalsekretariat und elf lokale Sitemanagements sind mit Monitoring, Berichterstattung und Umsetzung der Managementpläne beauftragt. Programme zur Zusammenarbeit haben sich in den Bereichen Tourismus, Kurmedizin, Kultur- und Jugendaustausch rasch entwickelt. Andere Projektideen werden geprüft.

Die Kooperation der Local Site Manager*innen wird vertieft. Zu Fragen

des Monitorings, der Erforschung der kurstädtischen Stadt- und Naturlandschaft, Abstimmung der Managementziele werden laufend Sitzungen und Online-Workshops abgehalten.

Die GSTE mit ihren elf lebendigen Kurstädten sind ein komplexes, außergewöhnliches Welterbe, aber auch ein herausragendes Beispiel für europäischen Geist und interkommunale Zusammenarbeit über nationalstaatliche Grenzen hinweg. Es ist ein kraftvoller Städtebund entstanden, der seine gemeinsamen Interessen und sein gemeinsames Erbe zu bewahren und für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung zu vertreten weiß.

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HANS HORNYIK ist seit 1980 im technischen Dienst des Landes Niederösterreich, derzeit im Bereich Baukultur und UNESCO-Welterbestätten, tätig. Von 1985 bis 1999 studierte er nebenberuflich Kommunikationswissenschaft und Sinologie in Wien und Taipei. Seit 2000 ist er Gemeinderat der Stadt Baden und seit 2005 Stadtrat (2005 bis 2010 Baustadtrat, 2010 bis 2020 Kulturstadtrat, seit 2020 Planungsstadtrat). Seit 2013 ist er zudem UNESCO-Welterbebeauftragter der Stadt Baden.

KULTURGÜTERSCHUTZ

Zeugnisse der Vergangenheit in die Zukunft tragen

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ÜBEREINKOMMEN über Maßnahmen zum Verbot und zur Verhütung der unzulässigen Einfuhr, Ausfuhr und Übereignung von Kulturgut

1970	von der UNESCO verabschiedet
2015	von Österreich ratifiziert
141	Vertragsstaaten

HAAGER KONVENTION zum Schutz von Kulturgut bei bewaffneten Konflikten

1954	in Den Haag verabschiedet, 1999 zweites, erweitertes Protokoll
1964	von Österreich ratifiziert
133	Vertragsstaaten

ÖUK Rolle: unterstützende Funktion, Beratung und Öffentlichkeitsarbeit; Gründungs- und Vorstandsmitglied von Blue Shield Austria

ÖUK Schwerpunkte: Unterstützung bei der Umsetzung, Mitarbeit im Kulturgut-Panel, Bewusstseinsbildung

Angefangen mit der *Haager Konvention zum Schutz von Kulturgut bei bewaffneten Konflikten* wurden seit 1954 vier völkerrechtliche Übereinkommen von der UNESCO verabschiedet, die den Schutz von beweglichen und unbeweglichen Kulturgütern zum Ziel haben. Insbesondere das *Übereinkommen über Maßnahmen zum Verbot und zur Verhütung der unzulässigen Einfuhr, Ausfuhr und Übereignung von Kulturgut*, das 2020 sein 50-jähriges Bestehen feierte, steht angesichts der globalen Auswirkungen illegalen Kulturguthandels zunehmend im Fokus.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• Kulturgüterschutzpanel

Um die verschiedenen Akteur*innen zu vernetzen, die auf nationaler Ebene mit Teilaspekten des Kulturgüterschutzes, insbesondere im Rahmen des *Übereinkommens über Maßnahmen zum Verbot und zur Verhütung der unzulässigen Einfuhr, Ausfuhr und Übereignung von Kulturgut* (1970), befasst sind, wurde das Kulturgüterschutzpanel des Bundesministeriums für Inneres (BMI) ins Leben gerufen. Auch 2021 hat sich die ÖUK, gemeinsam mit den wesentlichen Institutionen, allen voran dem Bundesministerium für Kunst, Kultur, Öffentlichen Dienst und Sport (BMKÖS), dem Bundesdenkmalamt (BDA), ICOM Austria, Blue Shield Austria, an diesem Forum beteiligt, um die Umsetzung des Übereinkommens zu fördern.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 13: Kulturgüterschutz korreliert direkt mit der Stärkung der Widerstandskraft und Anpassungsfähigkeit gegenüber klimabedingten Gefahren und Naturkatastrophen (Unterziel 13.1).

SDG 16: Die Umsetzung des UNESCO-Übereinkommens unterstützt die Wiedererlangung und Rückgabe gestohlener Vermögenswerte, speziell Kulturgüter, bekämpft somit organisierte Kriminalität und hilft bei der Reduktion illegaler Finanzströme (Unterziele 16.4).

KOMMUNIKATION UND INFORMATION

Die UNESCO fördert im Bereich Kommunikation und Information die Entwicklung von modernen Wissensgesellschaften, indem sie sich für die Meinungs- und Pressefreiheit, den Ausbau unabhängiger Medien sowie für den Zugang zu Wissen und Information für alle einsetzt. Die nachhaltige Sicherung und Zugänglichmachung von Dokumenten aller Art – Bücher, Handschriften, Fotos, Filme und Tonträger – ist hierfür wesentlich und Schwerpunkt des Memory of the World-Programms der UNESCO.

DOKUMENTENERBE / MEMORY OF THE WORLD- PROGRAMM

Eine wesentliche Voraussetzung für den Zugang zu Information ist die Bewahrung von Dokumenten. Als Informationsträger sichern Dokumente Wissenstransfer, ermöglichen Kommunikation und bilden die Basis unserer Erkenntnisse über historische Prozesse und Vergangenheiten. Dabei kommt den wichtigen Schriftstücken der Geschichte ebenso zentrale Bedeutung zu wie Dokumenten des täglichen Lebens. Sie alle bilden die Grundlage unserer Wissens- und Informationsgesellschaft.

Die Herausforderungen im Erhalt sind dabei mannigfaltig: neben den klassischen Problemen des physischen Verfalls sind mittlerweile auch

MEMORY OF THE WORLD-PROGRAMM

Bewahrung und Zugang zu dokumentarischem Erbe

1992 wurde das Programm gegründet

2014 erste Aufnahmen in das Nationale Memory of the World-Register, mittlerweile **59** Einträge, Verabschiedung der Empfehlung

427 Einträge in das Internationale Memory of the World-Register

15 davon aus Österreich

59 Aufnahmen in das österreichische Dokumentenregister

ÖUK Rolle: Sekretariat für das Nationalkomitee, Erstellung des Nationalen Registers, Bewusstseinsbildung.

ÖUK Schwerpunkte: Betreuung des Nationalkomitees, Übermittlung der internationalen Nominierungen, Führung und Betreuung des nationalen Registers.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 4: Eine inklusive, chancengerechte und qualitativ hochwertige Bildung kann nur gewährleistet werden, wenn Wissen und Information nachhaltig bewahrt und weitergegeben werden. Der demokratische Zugang zu Wissen und Information kommt der Gleichstellung der Geschlechter zugute (**SDG 5**) und trägt dazu bei, Ungleichheiten in und zwischen Ländern zu verringern. **SDG 9:** Der Zugang zu Wissen und Information fördert darüber hinaus wissenschaftliche und technische Innovation.

Fragestellungen der digitalen Aufbewahrung und Haltbarkeit von höchster Relevanz. Wie etwa stellen wir den Transfer von Informationen sicher, die auf Datenträgern gesichert sind, für die es keine Abspiel- oder Auslesegeräte mehr gibt?

Das 1992 gegründete „Memory of the World“-Programm der UNESCO nimmt sich ebenjener Thematiken an, die sich mit dem Dokumentenerhalt auseinandersetzen und fördert, im Rahmen des Internationalen Registers, die Sichtbarmachung des Dokumentenerbes der Menschheit. Auf nationaler Ebene befasst sich das „Memory of the World“-Nationalkomitee, das als Fachbeirat der ÖUK fungiert, mit dem Themenkomplex und führt das nationale Register „Memory of Austria“. Dieses umfasst für Österreich bedeutende Dokumentenbestände und macht sie dadurch sichtbar.

Insbesondere die Beilegung eines jahrelangen Konfliktes auf internationaler Ebene, der zum Stillstand des internationalen Registers und in weiterer Folge der nationalen Register geführt hatte, stellt ein wesentliches Ereignis des Jahres 2021 für das Programm dar.

AUSGEWÄHLTE AKTIVITÄTEN 2021

• Arbeitsgruppe zur Neustrukturierung des Fachbeirates/Nationalkomitees

Das Nationalkomitee für Memory of the World ist seit 2011 als eigenständiger Fachbeirat in der Österreichischen UNESCO-Kommission verankert und umfasst neben Expert*innen aus dem Bereich der Archivistik, Geschichte und des Dokumentenerhalts auch Vertreter*innen relevanter Institutionen und Ministerien. Um auf aktuelle Fragestellungen entsprechend zu reagieren, wurde 2021 eine Arbeitsgruppe eingerichtet, die unter Einbeziehung externer Expert*innen Empfehlungen zu einer inhaltlichen Neuausrichtung sowie personellen Erweiterung erarbeitet. Insbesondere die verstärkte Einbindung von Akteur*innen auf regionaler Ebene sowie die Berücksichtigung der Themenbereiche Digitalisierung/Digital Humanities und Restaurierung wurden seitens der Arbeitsgruppe angeregt und in weiterer Folge durch eine Neustrukturierung und Erweiterung des Fachbeirates/Nationalkomitees umgesetzt.

Schlussdokument des Wiener Kongresses 1815

Augsburger Bekenntnis („Confessio Augustana“) 1530

„Man wird nicht berühmt damit“ – Das UNESCO-Memory of the World-Programm im Gespräch

Dr. Dietrich Schüller übergibt nach langjährigem Vorsitz die Leitung des Memory of the World-Nationalkomitees an Mag. Thomas Just. Im Gespräch mit der ÖUK geben die beiden Einblick in ihren persönlichen Zugang zum Thema Dokumentenerbe.

Herr Dr. Schüller, Sie begleiten das Programm „Memory of the World“ (MoW) seit vielen Jahren, ja Jahrzehnten. Wie kam es, dass Sie mit dem Programm in Berührung kamen?

Ich war Mitglied des Fachbeirates Kultur- und Kommunikationsforschung unter dem Vorsitz von Kurt Blaukopf, der auch Exekutivratsmitglied der UNESCO war. Seit 1989 vertrete ich Österreich als Experte in der Generalkonferenz. Zuvor war ich in der „International Association of Sound und Audiovisual Archives“ sehr aktiv an der Gründung eines Technischen Komitees beteiligt. So kam ich in Berührung mit dem 1992 gegründeten Memory of the World-Programm. „Digitalisierung“ war damals ein viel zitiertes Schlagwort. Dabei ging es in den frühen 1990er Jahren noch nicht so sehr um „born-digital documents“, sondern zunächst um die Erleichterung des Zuganges zu besonders wertvollen, meist fragilen Dokumenten, zu denen

man sonst keinen Zugang hatte. Ich habe dann in der UNESCO-Generalkonferenz 1993 etwas aufmüpfig ein umfassenderes Konzept gefordert: Wir brauchen Digitalisierung nicht nur zur Erleichterung des Zugangs, sondern vor allem zur langfristigen Bewahrung von audiovisuellen Dokumenten. Für diese Dokumente war bereits damals klar: Digitalisierung ist die einzige Möglichkeit, sie über die Runden zu bekommen. Bei ihnen tritt das digitale Surrogat an die Stelle des Originals, weil weder Original noch Abspielmaschinen à la longue bewahrbar sind. Dies führte zur Einladung, eine Arbeitsgruppe, das Technical Subcommittee für MoW, zu gründen, das bis heute als „Preservation Subcommittee“ existiert. 2015 wurde ich dann auch als Mitglied in das „International Advisory Committee“ berufen.

Herr Mag. Just, zwei Jahrzehnte später wurden Sie Mitglied des

Fachbeirates für MoW. In Ihrer Funktion als Leiter des Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchives sind Sie tagtäglich mit dem Thema Dokumentenerhalt befasst. Welche Relevanz hat das Programm aus Ihrer Sicht?

Just: Archive in einem Land wie Österreich haben ja das Glück, relativ gut überliefert zu sein. Bei diesem großen Altbestand stehen wir vor der Herausforderung, dass wir diesen in die digitale Welt bringen müssen, zum einen, weil dieser Content nachgefragt wird. Das wollen wir ja auch, weil wir sonst an Relevanz verlieren würden und diese Relevanz für uns sehr wichtig ist, damit unsere vorgesetzten Ministerien auch realisieren, dass wir nicht nur bei Jubiläen herangezogen werden, sondern dass es um viel mehr geht.

Zum anderen, wie Dietrich Schüller schon gesagt hat, sichern wir auch. Und da ist die Digitalisierung im Bereich des Dokumentenerbes eine

Tonaufnahmen Österreichischer Dialekte 1951–1983

Möglichkeit. Nun produzieren wir lange schon nur mehr digitale Daten. Die Bedeutung des österreichischen Archivwesens liegt aber vor allem in der österreichischen Geschichte. Und hier gibt es einfach so viel Material, dass man digitalisieren muss. Hier ist dann so ein Fachbeirat wichtig, der sich als Mahner verstehen sollte – der darauf achtet, dass diese Daten bewahrt und in die neue Zeit transformiert werden.

Das MoW-Programm hat im Laufe seiner Existenz einige Veränderungen durchlaufen und war auch mit Herausforderungen konfrontiert, nicht zuletzt aufgrund der internationalen Schwierigkeiten, die zur Stilllegung des Registers geführt haben. Wie beurteilen Sie die Entwicklung des Programms?

Schüller: Jetzt muss ich vorsichtig sein. Es gibt ein Grundproblem, nämlich die Überbetonung des Registers gegenüber dem eigentlichen Programm. Und ich traue mich das auch ganz laut zu sagen, weil ich selbst einer war, der – Mitte der 1990er – vehement für das internationale Register und für die Auszeichnung besonderer Dokumente plädiert hat. Ich erinnere mich an eine lange Debatte. Es hat eigentlich nur einen Opponenten gegeben, das war der Generalsekretär des International Council of Archives...

Just: ...das wird Albada gewesen sein – Joan van Albada

Schüller: Richtig. Und es ist letztlich zu einer intensiven Diskussion geworden, in dem sich die Befürworter*innen des Registers durchgesetzt haben. Albada sagte, eine Hierarchisierung von Dokumenten sei unmöglich: der Notizzettel sei ja genauso wichtig wie die Goldene

Und es gibt da eben kein wichtigeres und kein unwichtigeres Dokument: der Meldezettel ist genauso wichtig wie die Goldene Bulle.

Bulle. Die Mehrheit war hingegen der Ansicht, das Register stelle ein unverzichtbares Instrument zur Förderung des Dokumentenerhalts dar. Er aber meinte, es gäbe keine Dokumente, die „besser“ oder „schlechter“ seien. Seit 1997 nun, wo die ersten Aufnahmen in das internationale Register erfolgt sind, hat sich dieses als Blockbuster erwiesen, und hat damit den eigentlichen Sinn des Memory of the World-Programms verdeckt, nämlich die Mitgliedsstaaten zu stärken, ihren Dokumentenbestand zu bewahren, zu erweitern und dafür zu

sorgen, dass jedes Dokument für alle zugänglich bleibt. Und es gibt da eben kein wichtigeres und kein unwichtigeres Dokument: der Meldezettel ist genauso wichtig wie die Goldene Bulle.

Im Kern des Programms steht also der Schutz aller Dokumente, nicht das Register – Herr Mag. Just, Sie übernehmen jetzt die Staffel als Vorsitzender und leiten in Ihrer Haupttätigkeit eine bedeutende Institution in diesem Bereich. Was sind denn im Schutz und in der Bewahrung unseres Dokumentenerbes die Herausforderungen aber auch Chancen, die jetzt auf uns zukommen werden?

Just: Das ist eine leichte und eine schwierige Frage gleichzeitig. Das eine ist, dass die Dokumente, die wir heute produzieren, viel fragiler sind als jene, die wir seit 1000 Jahren in unseren Speichern haben. Die digitalen Dokumente brauchen wahrscheinlich mehr Zuwendung und Pflege als etwa eine Pergamenturkunde – bei der wissen wir, wie die Aufbewahrung funktioniert, beim digitalen Objekt glauben wir nur, es zu wissen. Das andere ist, bei der Politik durchzudringen und das Bewusstsein zu schärfen – nicht nur dafür, dass dieses Register eine schöne Sache ist, sondern, dass auch der Meldezettel eine schöne Sache ist. Vielleicht sollten wir einmal einen Meldezettel auf die Liste bringen – um zu zeigen, dass auch ein unscheinbares Objekt so spannend sein und unglaubliche Informationen tragen kann. Ein Ziel des Fachbeirates wird sein müssen, das nationale Register weiterzubringen und mehr Öffentlichkeit dafür zu generieren. In den Bundesländern, zum Beispiel, gibt es wirklich tolle Objekte. Es spielt sich ja nicht alles in Wien ab!

Herr Dr. Schüller, Sie geben den Vorsitz ab, bleiben dem Fachbeirat aber dankenswerterweise noch weiterhin erhalten. Basierend auf Ihrer langjährigen Erfahrung: wo steuert das Programm national wie international hin?

Schüller: Wohin es steuern wird, das wird man jetzt erst sehen. Es hat international einen vierjährigen Reformprozess durchlaufen, der im Wesentlichen dem Register gegolten hat. Ausgelöst wurde das durch Nominierungen, die zur Offenlegung von beispielsweise Kriegsverbrechen eingebracht wurden, die aber für die betroffenen Staaten inakzeptabel waren. Das hat bis zu deutlichen finanziellen Drohungen geführt. Das MoW-Programm war dabei, die UNESCO durch die Unruhe – ich drücke mich hier sehr neutral aus –, die dadurch geschaffen wurde, zu schädigen¹.

Wie wird sich das Programm entwickeln? Wir wissen es im Moment noch nicht. Wenn es gut weitergeht, dann wird das Register ruhig laufen und keinen substanziellen Streit mehr hervorrufen. Ich selbst bin noch bis 2023 Mitglied des International Advisory Committee und propagiere sehr stark als eine meiner letzten Anstrengungen, wesentlich mehr Aufmerksamkeit auf die Basisschulung zum Dokumentenerhalt zu legen. Es geht doch letztlich darum: wie hebe ich z.B. ein Tonband auf? Es muss digitalisiert werden, sonst geht sein Inhalt verloren, weil wir keine Geräte mehr haben! Ich brauche mich über die Papyrussammlungen – wenn ich sie auf Temperatur halte und gegen Luftfeuchtigkeit bzw. Insektenfraß schütze – wenig zu kümmern. Aber dazwischen gibt es tausend Schattierungen. Darin sehe ich persönlich die größten Aufgaben – ich hoffe, dass es möglich sein wird, diesen nicht sehr attraktiven Dingen besser nachzugehen. Man wird nicht berühmt damit...

Just (lacht): ...und man macht sich unbeliebt dabei.

Herr Mag. Just, abschließend nun: Was kommt Ihnen in den Sinn, wenn Sie den Namen Dietrich Schüller hören?

Just: Da denke ich an einen sehr engagierten, hilfsbereiten Menschen, der jahrzehntelang der Motor dieses

Fachbeirates und auch für das ganze Programm hier in Österreich gewesen ist. Und du hast ja für uns alle große Fußstapfen gesetzt, in die wir alle ein bisschen hineintapsen, das darf man schon sagen.

Schüller: Ich bin einfach ein emotionaler Mensch, der nicht gerne schweigt. Und offenkundig war das nicht ganz unerfolgreich in der Zeit, in der ich mich der Sache gewidmet habe.

Just: Aber das Reden ist ja auch in dieser Sache das Entscheidende. Wir können die Anliegen, die wir haben – Kulturgüterschutz, Dokumentenschutz – nicht vertreten, wenn wir nicht dar-

Wenn ich etwa daran denke, dass man heute Familienforschung bequem von zu Hause aus am Computer machen kann, [...] ist das ein Beispiel dafür, wie Kulturgüterschutz, wie Digitalisierung, so funktioniert hat, dass es sofort bei den Menschen landet.

über sprechen. Dietrich Schüller hat das Zeit seines Lebens gut gemacht: er hat viel darüber gesprochen und dadurch viel erreicht. Und das sollten wir auch weiterhin machen. Österreich ist in einigen Bereichen ein Vorreiter gewesen. Wenn ich etwa daran denke, dass man heute Familienforschung bequem von zu Hause aus am Computer machen kann, indem man sich diese ganzen kirchlichen Matriken im Internet anschaut, ist das ein Beispiel dafür, wie Kulturgüterschutz, wie Digitalisierung, so funktioniert hat, dass es sofort bei den Menschen landet. Wenn ich mir die Goldene Bulle im Netz anschauen kann, ist das zwar recht schön, aber wenn ich meine Verwandten suchen kann, dann habe ich gleich eine ganz andere Verbindung zu diesem Thema.

Herr Dr. Schüller: Was wünschen Sie sich für das Programm und für den Fachbeirat?

Ich freue mich vor allem über eines: wir haben einen Verjüngungsprozess durchgemacht und eine Diversifikation der Mitglieder, auch eine topografische. Ich bin sehr zuversichtlich, dass dies zu einer intensivierten Weiterführung des Programms beiträgt und es gelingt, die Sichtbarkeit zu erhöhen. Es ist wirklich wichtig, dass die Mitglieder selbst aktiv im Geschehen stehen, während wir in letzter Zeit schon einen Überhang an „Weisen“ gehabt hatten. Nun können Weise durchaus Sinn machen, aber sie können nicht der Motor sein. Insofern habe ich überhaupt keinen Zweifel, dass unter Thomas Just und dem jetzt aufgefrischten Fachbeirat eine neue Dynamik entsteht, die man auch wirklich nützen kann, um die für unsere Aufgaben nötigen Mittel zu akquirieren.

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DR. DIETRICH SCHÜLLER studierte 1957–1959 Technische Physik an der Technischen Hochschule (heute TU) in Wien; sodann Studienwechsel: Ethnologie und Vergleichende Musikwissenschaft, Universität Wien, Promotion zum Doktor der Philosophie 1970. Er stand von 1972–2008 dem Phonogrammarchiv an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften als Direktor vor. Zudem war und ist er Mitglied in zahlreichen nationalen wie internationalen Gremien, Autor von rund 200 Publikationen mit den Schwerpunkten Schallaufnahme als wissenschaftliche Quelle, Phonographische Feldforschung sowie Lagerung, Konservierung und Restaurierung von audiovisuellen Dokumenten; umfassende Lehr-, Forschungs- und Beratungstätigkeit in den genannten Feldern und darüber hinaus. **MAG. THOMAS JUST** studierte Geschichte in Wien. Er ist Mitglied des Instituts für Österreichische Geschichtsforschung. Nach Tätigkeiten im Wiener Stadt- und Landesarchiv, bei der Wiener Stadtarchäologie und im ORF ist er seit 2001 Mitarbeiter des Österreichischen Staatsarchivs. Seit 2009 leitet er als Direktor die Abteilung Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv.

¹ Siehe dazu auch den Beitrag von Botschafterin Claudia Reinprecht im ÖUK-Jahrbuch 2020, abrufbar unter www.unesco.at.

MEDIEN- UND PRESSEFREIHEIT

Die UNESCO ist die wichtigste UN-Organisation mit einem Mandat zur Förderung der freien Meinungsäußerung. Dabei sind die Pressefreiheit und die Sicherheit von Journalist*innen ebenso zentrale Aspekte wie die Gleichstellung der Geschlechter in der Medienlandschaft. Außerdem betreibt die UNESCO Initiativen zur Medien- und Informationskompetenz und zur Journalist*innen-ausbildung und unterstützt spezifische Medienprojekte durch das Internationale Programm für die Entwicklung der Kommunikation (IPDC). So leistet die Organisation einen Beitrag zum Aufbau inklusiver Wissensgesellschaften, die sich durch Zugang zu Information und (digitalen) Technologien für alle Menschen auszeichnen. Eine wesentliche Rolle spielen dafür unter anderem auch die ethische Entwicklung und Nutzung neuer Technologien, die einen stetig wachsenden Einfluss auf Gesellschaften ausüben. So kann beispielsweise der Einsatz von Algorithmen die Meinungsfreiheit beeinträchtigen und die Verbreitung von Falsch- und Desinformation erleichtern. Solche irreführenden oder falschen Informationen gefährden nicht zuletzt demokratische Prozesse und untergraben den gesellschaftlichen Zusammenhalt. Eine freie, unabhängige und pluralistische Medienlandschaft in Print, Rundfunk und digital kann dem entgegen-treten und zu Frieden, Nachhaltigkeit, Armutsbekämpfung und Menschenrechten beitragen.

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Eine wesentliche Rolle spielen [...] unter anderem auch die ethische Entwicklung und Nutzung neuer Technologien, die einen stetig wachsenden Einfluss auf Gesellschaften ausüben.

Bezug zu den UN-Zielen für nachhaltige Entwicklung / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Für den Bereich Pressefreiheit sind vor allem Aspekte des **SDG 16** relevant: Korruption und Bestechung in allen ihren Formen erheblich reduzieren / Leistungsfähige, rechenschaftspflichtige und transparente Institutionen auf allen Ebenen aufbauen / den öffentlichen Zugang zu Informationen gewährleisten und die Grundfreiheiten schützen, im Einklang mit den nationalen Rechtsvorschriften und völkerrechtlichen Übereinkünften.

Sicherheit von Journalist*innen

Die Förderung der Sicherheit von Journalist*innen ist zentrales Element der Arbeit der UNESCO im Bereich Pressefreiheit. Im Durchschnitt wird weltweit alle fünf Tage ein*e Journalist*in in Zusammenhang mit der Berufsausübung getötet. Aber auch Entführungen, Belästigungen, Einschüchterungen, widerrechtliche und willkürliche Inhaftierungen zählen zu den schwerwiegenden Problemen, mit denen die Berufsgruppe überall auf der Welt regelmäßig konfrontiert ist. Dabei ist besonders auffällig, dass gegen Journalist*innen begangene Verbrechen häufig unbestraft bleiben. Die UNESCO trägt zur Sichtbarmachung dieser Situation bei, in dem seit 1997 der*die jeweils amtierenden Generaldirektor*in jeden Mord an einer*m Journalist*in öffentlich in einer Stellungnahme verurteilt. Seit 2008 wird außerdem alle zwei Jahre ein Bericht über die Sicherheit von Journalist*innen für den Zwischenstaatlichen Rat des Internationalen Programms für die Entwicklung der Kommunikation (IPDC) veröffentlicht.

UNESCO/Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom-Preis

Der mit 25.000 USD dotierte Preis honoriert außergewöhnliche Beiträge zur Verteidigung, Wahrung und Verbreitung der Pressefreiheit. Er ist nach dem kolumbianischen Journalisten Guillermo Cano Isaza benannt, der 1986 vor dem Gebäude seiner Zeitung „El Espectador“ in Bogotá, Kolumbien, ermordet wurde. Der Preis wird von der Guillermo Cano Isaza-Stiftung (Kolumbien), der Helsingin Sanomat-Stiftung (Finnland) sowie dem Namibia Media Trust gesponsort.

2021 wurde der UNESCO/Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom-Preis, auf Empfehlung einer internationalen Expert*innen-Jury, an die philippinische Investigativ-Journalistin und Medienmanagerin Maria Ressa verliehen. Der Preis geht damit an eine Journalistin aus einer Region, die besonders stark von Gewalt gegen Journalist*innen betroffen ist: laut UNESCO-Monitoring wurden auf den Philippinen seit 1993 112 Journalist*innen ermordet.

Maria Ressa war während ihrer langjährigen Karriere unter anderem als leitende Investigativreporterin für CNN im asiatischen Raum tätig und leitete die Abteilung Aktuelles des philippinischen TV- und Online-Networks ABS-CBN. Außerdem engagierte sie sich in zahlreichen internationalen Initiativen für die Wahrung der Pressefreiheit. In den letzten Jahren wurde sie zum Ziel von

Online-Angriffen sowie rechtlichen Verfolgungen, insbesondere in Zusammenhang mit ihrer Tätigkeit als Geschäftsführerin und Chefredakteurin des philippinischen Online-Nachrichtenportals „Rappler“. Sie und ihre Geschäftspartner wurden der Steuerhinterziehung sowie der Nicht-Vorlage von Steuerunterlagen beschuldigt, Vorwürfe, die sie stets bestritten hatten und die möglicherweise in Zusammenhang mit einem kritischen Beitrag über einen philippinischen Geschäftsmann stehen. Gleichzeitig wurde sie zum Ziel einer Hass-Kampagne, an deren Höhepunkt sie via Facebook durchschnittlich über 90 Hass-Nachrichten pro Stunde erhielt.

Ressa wurde in der Vergangenheit bereits mit zahlreichen Preisen ausgezeichnet, u.a. mit dem Golden Pen of Freedom Award des Weltverbandes der Zeitungen (2018), dem Gwen-Ifill-Preis für Pressefreiheit, verliehen vom Komitee zum Schutz von Journalist*innen (ebenfalls 2018), sowie dem Tucholsky-Preis der schwedischen Sektion von P.E.N. (2020). Im Jahr 2021 erhielt sie zudem, gemeinsam mit dem russischen Journalisten Dmitir Muratow, den Friedensnobelpreis.

Maria Ressa 2015

ANHANG

DIE ÖSTERREICHISCHE UNESCO-KOMMISSION (ÖÜK)

Gemäß § 2 der Statuten des Vereins „Österreichische UNESCO-Kommission“ erfüllt die ÖÜK die Aufgaben einer Nationalkommission nach Artikel VII der Verfassung der Organisation der Vereinten Nationen für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Kultur (UNESCO). Die Tätigkeit des Vereins ist gemeinnütziger Natur und nicht auf Gewinn ausgerichtet.

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Fachbeirat „Immaterielles Kulturerbe“

Fachbeirat „Informationsbewahrung /
Memory of the World Nationalkomitee“

UNESCO-WELTERBESTÄTTEN IN ÖSTERREICH

- 1996 **Historisches Zentrum der Stadt Salzburg**
- 1996 **Schloss und Gärten von Schönbrunn**
- 1997 **Kulturlandschaft Hallstatt-Dachstein/Salzkammergut**
- 1998 **Semmeringebahn**
- 1999 **Stadt Graz - Historisches Zentrum und**
- 2010 **Schloss Eggenberg**
- 2000 **Kulturlandschaft Wachau**
- 2001 **Historisches Zentrum von Wien**
- 2001 **Kulturlandschaft Fertő/Neusiedler See** (gemeinsam mit Ungarn)
- 2011 **Prähistorische Pfahlbauten um die Alpen** (gemeinsam mit Deutschland, Frankreich, Italien, Slowenien, Schweiz)
- 2017 **Alte Buchenwälder und Buchenurwälder der Karpaten und anderer Regionen Europas** (gemeinsam mit Albanien, Belgien, Bulgarien, Kroatien, Italien, Österreich, Rumänien, Slowenien, Spanien und Ukraine) in Österreich im Wildnisgebiet Dürrenstein/NÖ sowie Gebieten im Nationalpark Kalkalpen/OÖ)
- 2021 **Great Spa Towns of Europe** (gemeinsam mit Belgien, Deutschland, Frankreich, Großbritannien, Italien und Tschechien)
- 2021 **Grenzen des Römischen Reiches – Donaulimes (Westlicher Abschnitt)** (gemeinsam mit Deutschland und Slowakei)
- ### BIOSPÄRENPARKS IN ÖSTERREICH
- 2000 **Großes Walsertal**, Vorarlberg
- 2005 **Wienerwald**, Wien/Niederösterreich
- 2012 **Salzburger Lungau und Kärntner Nockberge**, Salzburg/Kärnten
- 2019 **Unteres Murtal**, Steiermark, Weltweit erster „5-Länder-Biosphärenpark“ (Österreich, Slowenien, Kroatien, Ungarn und Serbien)

UNESCO-GEOPARKS IN ÖSTERREICH

2004 **Steirische Eisenwurzten**

2013 **Karawanken**
(gemeinsam mit Slowenien)

2014 **Erz der Alpen**

EINTRAGUNGEN IN DIE REPRÄSENTATIVE LISTE DES IMMATERIELLEN KULTURERBES DER MENSCHHEIT

2012 **Falknerei** (multinationale Einreichung mit insgesamt 24 Staaten)

2012 **Fasnacht Imst – Schemenlaufen**

2015 **Klassische Reitkunst und die Hohe Schule der Spanischen Hofreitschule**

2017 **Handblaudruck in Europa**
(multinationale Einreichung mit Deutschland, Slowakei, Tschechien und Ungarn)

2017 **Erfahrungswissen im Umgang mit Lawinengefahr**
(bilaterale Einreichung mit der Schweiz)

2019 **Transhumanz**
(multinationale Einreichung mit Griechenland und Italien)

EINTRAGUNGEN IN DAS INTERNATIONALE IKE-REGISTER GUTER PRAXISBEISPIELE

2016 **Regional Centres for Craftsmanship: a strategy for safeguarding the cultural heritage of traditional handicraft**

2020 **Craft techniques and customary practices of cathedral workshops, or Bauhütten, in Europe, know-how, transmission, development of knowledge and innovation**

UNESCO-„CREATIVE CITIES“ IN ÖSTERREICH

2011 **Graz – „City of Design“**

2014 **Linz – „City of Media Arts“**

EINTRÄGE IN DAS MEMORY OF THE WORLD REGISTER

1997 **Wiener Dioscurides Manuskript**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

1997 **Schlussakte des Wiener Kongresses 1815**, Österreichisches Staatsarchiv

1999 **Historische Sammlung (1899 – 1950)**
Phonogrammarchiv der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften

2001 **Papyrussammlung (Kollektion Erzherzog Rainer)**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

2001 **Schubertsammlung**
Wiener Stadt- und Landesbibliothek

2003 **Atlas Blaeu-Van der Hem**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

2005 **Brahms Sammlung**
Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde in Wien

2005 **Gotische Baurisse**, Kupferstichkabinett der Akademie der Bildenden Künste

2005 **Bibliotheca Corviniana**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek (gemeinsam mit Ungarn, Belgien, Deutschland, Frankreich und Italien)

2007 **Tabula Peutingeriana**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

2011 **Arnold Schönberg-Nachlass**
Arnold Schönberg Center

2011 **Mainzer Psalter**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

2013 **Die Goldene Bulle**
Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek (gemeinsam mit Deutschland)

2017 **Philosophischer Nachlass von Ludwig Wittgenstein**
Österreichische Nationalbibliothek (gemeinsam mit Großbritannien, Kanada und den Niederlanden)

2017 **Historische Dokumente zum Bau der Semmeringebahn**
Technisches Museum

UNESCO-LEHRSTÜHLE

UNESCO-Lehrstuhl für Interkulturellen und Interreligiösen Dialog für Südosteuropa, etabliert 2007, Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz, Katholisch-Theologische Fakultät | Lehrstuhlinhaber: Univ.-Prof. DDr. Pablo ARGÁRATE

UNESCO-Lehrstuhl Peace Studies, etabliert 2008, Universität Innsbruck | Lehrstuhlinhaber: Univ.-Prof. DDr. Wolfgang DIETRICH

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**Austrian Commission
for UNESCO**

Annual Report 2021

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Austrian Commission for UNESCO

Annual Report 2021

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Österreichische
UNESCO-Kommission
Austrian Commission
for UNESCO

FOREWORD

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Patrizia Jankovic, Secretary-General

2021, much like the year that preceded it, was still characterised quite strongly by pandemic-related restrictions: it remained the case that more than a few events could “only” be held in digital formats, while working in “remote mode” finally became normal. Even so, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO (ÖUK) can look back upon a successful year. The contributions on the following pages serve to highlight our wide array of activities:

The presentation of the new Global Education Monitoring Report (entitled “Non-State Actors in Education: Who Chooses? Who Loses?”) traced an arc between the Global South and the Global North and was once again the object of international attention. The UNESCO Associated Schools Conference offered a variety-packed programme whose theme was “Futures of Education”, and the ÖUK’s new initiative to offer schools various workshops on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals generated a great deal of resonance among school students and teachers alike.

This year once again saw numerous outstanding contributors to basic research awarded UNESCO-L’ORÉAL Austria Fellowships as part of the “For Women in Science” initiative. Our science activities also featured the establishment of the “UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Futures Design” at the University of Art and Design Linz.

In the realm of culture, Austria’s National Point of Contact to the *UNESCO Convention on the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* opened up a new thematic emphasis on the issue of preferential treatment in (post-)migrant Austria as well as antidiscrimination in (international) cultural policy with the event series “Forum Fair Culture”.

18 April 2021 witnessed the observance of Austria’s first World Heritage Day, a day of action involving all Austrian World Heritage sites that calls attention to the outstanding universal value of World Heritage in Austria and worldwide. On the international level, the past year also witnessed successful inscription of “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (including the town of Baden, just south of Vienna) as well as the positive conclusion of the multi-year nomination process for “Frontiers of the Roman Empire – The Danube Limes (Western Segment)”. In terms of intangible cultural heritage, the focus in 2021 was on traditional irrigation methods: starting from the National Inventory element “Meadow Irrigation in Tyrol”, Austria coordinated the preparatory work for a multinational nomination to the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

These successes have only been possible thanks to good cooperation on the part of all those involved—and I would like to extend special thanks to all ÖUK employees and to the ÖUK Executive Committee and Board for their great dedication and tireless efforts as well as to those federal ministries that have long provided us with support.

Patrizia Jankovic

Sabine Haag, President

Today UNESCO is more important than ever as a forum of global intellectual cooperation, with the COVID-19 pandemic having played no small role in making clear that the challenges of our present era can only be overcome cooperatively and multilaterally.

Part of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO's work is to implement the goals of UNESCO in Austria. Our other focus is on working together with the competent Austrian ministries in order to anchor Austrian positions, concerns, and projects within UNESCO.

Every two years, representatives of UNESCO's member states gather as the General Conference, UNESCO's supreme decision-making and monitoring body. November 2021 once again saw Austria represented in Paris by the competent federal ministries and the Austrian Commission for UNESCO along with experts from the arts, culture, education, and science. We are also especially proud that this 41st General Conference of UNESCO saw Austria elected to be part of UNESCO's Executive Board, the institution's most important executive body, for the fourth time.

Austria is represented not only there but also on numerous further UNESCO committees and boards, such as currently on the International Coordinating Council of UNESCO's "Man and the Biosphere" (MAB) Programme, the Intergovernmental Council of the "Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme" (IHP), and the Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions—to name just a few. Common to the ÖUK's involvement with all of the abovementioned groups is the significant contribution it makes to the

coordination of Austrian expertise in the interest of more solidly undergirding the substantive discussion. In turn, the participation of Austrian experts in international programmes ends up internationalising the associated Austrian debates more or less as a matter of course. An example of such cross-pollination in this Annual Report would be the interview with Günter Köck regarding his many years of work for the MAB Programme.

Our collaboration with Dr. Köck and the Austrian Academy of Sciences is just one of numerous instances in which the ÖUK relies on expert knowledge from the sciences, the arts, and the cultural and educational realms in its activities. Highly regarded experts currently work as part of six advisory committees that advise and inform the ÖUK as well as assess the implementation of UNESCO's goals in Austria. I would like to extend my thanks to them here for their always-beneficial collaboration and our numerous fruitful discussions!

We would also like to most cordially thank all of our partner organizations and sponsors, especially those from the competent federal ministries, for their support and partnership!

Sabine Haag

Open Science & Artificial Intelligence – Two Forward-Looking UNESCO Recommendations

At its 41st meeting in November 2021, the General Conference of UNESCO adopted a recommendation on the topic of open science as well as a widely-noted recommendation regarding the ethics of artificial intelligence (AI). Dr. Stefan Hanslik, head of the Technical Sciences Department at Austria's Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, points out the significance of both UNESCO instruments in terms of the development of corresponding measures and policies in Austria and introduces Austria's current position.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science – A Further Step in the Right Direction

The vision of open science is to make scientific processes more open and effective and to harness scientific excellence as well as innovative and applied research in order to take on current and future societal, socioeconomic, and ecological challenges. Open science is an important tool in efforts to make significant advances toward overcoming present and future societal challenges. With the preparation of a standard-setting international instrument in the form of a “Recommendation on Open Science”, UNESCO took a crucial step in the interest of guiding and governing the multi-layered global open science movement for the benefit of all. Together with the objectives of the EU in the field of research and data policy, this recommendation formed the basis for the development of an Austrian policy (in the sense of a common orientation) on Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Developing open, transparent, and inclusive science and promoting the fair handling of research processes and their results is an Austrian priority. Open Science was hence also included in the Federal Government's strategy for research, technology, and innovation (RTI Strategy 2030) in the form of a clear commitment to “Horizon Europe” and Austria's active participation in the European Research Area (ERA).

As a result, intense effort was devoted to the development of an Austrian policy on Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud. Alongside the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF), this

process also involved the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (BMK) and the Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs (BMDW). These efforts revealed

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the great relevance of proactive participation in the process of implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), a World Wide Web for FAIR research data and services intended to keep research data as free, accessible, and open as possible.

In a timely manner and corresponding to the UNESCO activities, February 2022 saw the “Open Science Policy Austria” adopted on the occasion of a joint Ministerial Council presentation by the three Austrian ministries with primary competency regarding the Open Science movement: the BMBWF, BMDW, and BMK. By implementing UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science, Austria is actively promoting the development of an open, transparent, and inclusive environment for science and hence also the fair handling of research processes and their results on the national level.

Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence – An Important Prerequisite for Dealing with AI

In light of how rapid technological developments such as the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) are already having deep-reaching effects on our societies, this UNESCO recommendation represents an important prerequisite for dealing with artificial intelligence in a global context. There can be no doubt that the question of which skills and parameters the human world needs to develop in order to continue evolving peacefully in an increasingly automated world will be growing enormously in its significance.

In knowledge societies, artificial intelligence can be employed in areas such as teaching and learning in order to render these processes interactive and personalized, thus helping to enhance the quality of teaching and learning as well as the variety of teaching methods. AI must and will be part of activities such as education and further training in the STEM field as well as in teacher

training in order to ensure that state-of-the-art education is of high quality.

Artificial intelligence can be of great benefit to marginalized groups such as children, youth, and adults living in rural areas or crisis regions as well as people with disabilities insofar as they have access to new technologies. Granting such access and taking the necessary steps to eradicate the digital gap are significant prerequisites.

By implementing UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science, Austria is actively promoting the development of an open, transparent, and inclusive environment for science and hence also the fair handling of research processes and their results on the national level.

As AI technologies are not neutral, and as AI is currently blind to the consequences of its application, Austria emphatically supports UNESCO’s commitment to artificial intelligence and especially its focus on the ethical dimension thereof. “Responsible Science” as a concept for bringing together scientific excellence and social relevance can contribute significantly to raising awareness of the potential challenges and risks entailed by this new, emerging technology.

Human analysis as well as strict control of AI-based decisions must be ensured: AI cannot and must not replace natural intelligence; instead, it must serve humankind in specific domains and with expertise as well as human oversight. For this and other reasons, we need to more strongly involve people in the process of developing AI and the framework surrounding it irrespective of gender, descent, worldview, age, sexual orientation, or special needs.

Only an approach based on human rights, ethics, and scientific integrity can

provide a framework that will enable both the successful use of artificial intelligence and the protection and consideration of each individual’s personal rights and needs as well as the assurance of fairness and transparency in all societal areas.

In sum, Austria considers it to be of great importance to work on a national AI Framework as well as to agree on a standard-setting international instrument concerning the ethics of artificial intelligence such as the one adopted by UNESCO.

© Hanslik

STEFAN HANSLIK holds a doctorate in biology and genetics. He heads the Technical Sciences Department at the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research. He represents Austria in numerous international bodies including various HORIZON Europe programme committees, the OECD’s Working Group on Biotechnology, and the Council of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility.

EDUCATION

With its adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the international community of states emphasised the central role to be played by education in implementing the Agenda's 17 Sustainable Development Goals. In this respect, it is key to anchor sustainability in educational systems worldwide and to drive forward the 17 SDGs' implementation.

UNESCO'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES

Towards a Fairer World for All

To shape peaceful, just, and sustainable futures, education itself needs to be transformed.

This is the demand asserted by the Global Report of the *International Commission on the Futures of Education*, entitled “Reimagining Our Futures Together: A New Social Contract for Education”. This report asks what role education can play in shaping our world and our common future with an eye to 2050 and beyond. The presented recommendations are the outcome of a two-year global process of engagement and collaboration. The report is devoted to topics such as reshaping spaces of learning, decolonialising curricula, and the significance of social and emotional learning, and it addresses real and growing fears of climate change, of crises such as COVID-19, of fake news and the digital divide. Education—the way in which we organise teaching and learning throughout our lives—plays a fundamental role in shaping human societies. It connects us with the world and with one another, shows us new possibilities, and reinforces our abilities to engage in dialogue and take action.

Education Agenda – No One Shall Be Left Behind

While the expansion of educational systems has opened up new opportunities for numerous people, the quality of the education available to many is lacking. The way in which education is organised worldwide is currently inadequate to the mission of ensuring fair and peaceful societies, a healthy planet, and shared progress that benefits all. In actual fact, several difficulties in this respect can be attributed to the way in which education is provided. The enormous transformative potentials of digital technologies need to be used, while more active civic involvement and the growing sphere of activism that opposes discrimination and injustice need to be integrated into educational activities in order to strengthen education as a public concern and an element of the common good.

Education and the SDGs

The Global Education 2030 Agenda is derived from the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which was adopted by the United Nations in September 2015. Education plays a central role in the successful implementation of all 17 Sustainable Development Goals, also having a Sustainable Development Goal of its own that aims to “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030. And UNESCO, as the only specialized agency of the United Nations with a mandate to cover all aspects of education, is leading the way in implementing this goal's various targets.

SGD 4 – Quality Education

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030.

4.1. By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable, and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes.

4.2. By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care-, and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education.

4.3. By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university.

4.4. By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurship.

4.5. By 2030, eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, and children in vulnerable situations.

4.6. By 2030, ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults achieve literacy and numeracy.

4.7. By 2030, ensure all learners acquire knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

The Austrian Commission for UNESCO assumes support and advisory functions that serve the various protagonists working to implement international educational programmes in Austria. In doing so, it orients itself toward the various current working emphases of UNESCO as a whole and in particular toward the Global Education 2030 Agenda.

• Presentation of UNESCO's 2021/22 Global Education Monitoring Report

Ever since the United Nations' adoption of the 17 Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report (GEM Report) has been shedding light on worldwide progress as well as the development of education policy in the individual countries in the interest of achieving SDG 4. This report serves to monitor, document, and analyse implementation of the Education 2030 agenda as well as to formulate recommendations that help better facilitate its implementation. The 2021/22 report is entitled "Non-State Actors in Education: Who Chooses? Who Loses?" and was published in December 2021. In this edition, UNESCO demands better oversight of private educational institutions in order to reduce inequalities and calls upon member states to set quality standards for state and non-state institutions: to reinforce efforts toward free primary and secondary schooling, to bring together stakeholders from diverse areas of the educational field, to strengthen the capacity of the state to monitor compliance with and enforce regulations, and above all, to protect education from narrow vested interests.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Education and the SDGs Education sits at the core of the 2030 Agenda. It plays a central role in the successful implementation of all 17 Sustainable Development Goals, and it also has its own goal, SDG 4, which aims to: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030.”

- **Advisory Panel on Global Citizenship Education, Global Learning, Education for Sustainable Development**

The Advisory Panel on Transformative Education/ Global Citizenship Education, which was established at the Austrian Commission for UNESCO in March 2017, devotes itself to monitoring and accompanying the national implementation of SDG 4, in particular SDG 4.7. In 2021, this body added Dr. Gerhard Bisovsky, at the time Secretary-General of the Association of Austrian Adult Education Centres, as its newest member.

- **The Youth Representative of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO**

In the interest of amplifying young people’s voices, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO created the two-year position of “Youth Representative” in 2019. This individual acts as a representative of the ÖUK’s youth-relevant positions in the outside world and works together with the ÖUK Secretariat to realise UNESCO-relevant youth activities. In 2021, Maria Blomenhofer took over this honorary post, which she will hold until mid-2023.

- **“Turning Point”: Education for the SDGs**

“Turning Point: Youth for Sustainable Development” is an event series of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO’s Youth Representative. It brings together young people in order to discuss urgent problems of our time.

25th and 26th January witnessed the online workshop “Your Rights – Your World!” It was organised in combination with the project “Know Your Rights” and offered around 140 young people between the ages of 14 and 25 the opportunity to engage in exchange on the topics of human rights and sustainability, learning more about the complex ways in which human rights and protecting the climate and the environment interrelate.

Is privatisation a solution or a symptom?

The Global Education Monitoring Report 2021/22, entitled "Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses?" addresses the question of the impact of (increasing) privatization in the education sector.

To bridge the gap between the Global North and the Global South with regard to non-state actors in education, Dr. Maria Ron-Balsera, TaxEd Alliance Coordinator, uses a study conducted in Ghana, Kenya and Uganda to explain the situation and challenges of those countries.

In 2015 governments around the world committed to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all', with the leading principle of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development to 'leave no one behind'. The effects of COVID-19 threaten to derail the progress made in these two decades, resulting in hundreds of million people falling back into extreme poverty, and a growing backlog in the implementation of the 2030 agenda. Due to the way the COVID-19 pandemic was managed, on top of years of austerity policies, education systems face a devastating crisis in public financing, and uncertainty over the quality of learning available when children return to education.

Many voices are pushing for stronger partnerships with private actors. However, the negative effects on equity and other areas of the increasing privatisation of education is becoming a central concern for education, development and human rights scholars and practitioners. The GEM Report for 2021/22 rallying call: Who chooses, who loses? Is very telling of the impact of the increasing privatisation of education, with growing evidence in terms of exclusion, segmentation, segregation, inequality of opportunities, stigmatisation of public education, diversion of essential funds, lowering teaching standards, narrowing

of the curriculum, etc. which the GEMR partly analyses.

The Abidjan principles on the human rights obligations of States to provide public education and to regulate private involvement in education were adopted in 2019. They provide rigorous guidelines to assess the role of private providers and consolidate international legislation into a single document, underlining governments' responsi-

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lities to respect, protect and fulfil the right to education. Principle 25 refers to the state's obligation to prevent or redress direct or indirect discrimination in or through education, for example, including systemic disparities in educational opportunities or outcomes, highlighting socio-economic disadvantage. Principle 48 affirms that private actors can supplement, but not supplant or replace state provision of education, and that they cannot create any adverse

systematic impact, such as creating or entrenching educational disparities.

Our study in Ghana, Kenya and Uganda and the collaborative research in Malawi, Mozambique, Nigeria and Tanzania used these Principles to understand the impact of privatisation on the right to education. They concluded:

- These states are not meeting their obligations to provide free and quality education and to adequately regulate private providers of education
- Private providers are supplanting rather than supplementing public education
- The financial allocations for public education provision are inadequate
- Privatisation is creating and exacerbating social inequalities
- Ideological arguments are used to support the agenda, rather than evidence, which remain inconclusive about the advantages of private providers

Therefore, privatisation is not a solution, but rather a symptom of the lack of availability and quality of public education. This is partly the result of the chronic inadequate financing of education. As our research shows, many countries fail to allocate their maximum available resources and often taken retrogressive steps, lowering the education budget without justification. These countries have staggering losses

¹ Funded by GPE-EOL, the TaxEd Alliance connects Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) stakeholders working on tax issues with those working on education to create an effective transnational CSO response. Bringing together ActionAid, Education International, the Global Campaign for Education, Tax Justice Network, the Global Alliance for Tax Justice and its regional networks Tax And Fiscal Justice Asia and Tax Justice Network - Africa.

Financing the future: Education financing and tax incentives

Country	Education as share of national budget	Tax/GDP	Estimated annual revenue foregone from tax incentives	20 percent of this sum would amount to	This money could pay for
Nepal	14.1% (2018)	18% (13% indirect, 5% direct taxes) (2017)	\$1.68 billion	\$336.6 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for all the out-of-school places for children left out of primary and lower-secondary school • The basic salary for 5,000 primary and 5,000 lower secondary teachers • Free school meals for 600,000 children • Expanding the annual scholarship for vulnerable groups to an additional 1 million young people • The estimated annual financing gap (US\$81 million in 2021) in the Nepalese School Sector Development Plan (SSDP) mid-term review
Senegal	22.1% (2020)	16.8% (11,7% indirect, 5,1% direct taxes) (2020)	\$1.19 billion	\$238 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for all around half (350,000) of the primary aged children currently out-of-school • 10,000 teachers (of the 35,000 gap required to be filled by 2030) • Double the number of children who receive a free school meal annually
Zambia	12.4% (2020)	16.7% (9% indirect, 7,7% direct taxes) (2019)	\$406 million	\$81.2 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for 350,000 children in primary school (around 2/3rds of the current out-of-school primary school children) • 4,000 extra primary school teachers (the estimated current primary school teacher gap) • Free school meals for 1/2 million children annually
Ghana	18.6% (2018)	12% (5,8% indirect, 6,5% direct taxes) (2019)	\$1.2 billion	\$240 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A place in a primary school for the 319,000 out-of-school children • An extra 10,000 qualified teachers • Free school meals for 1 year for 557,892 children
Uganda	11.2% (2018)	11.5% (7,4% indirect, 1,4% direct taxes) (2019)	\$272 million	\$54.4 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A place in a primary school for the 477,000 out-of-school children • An extra 20,000 qualified teachers • Free school meals for 1 year for 412,047 children

to tax incentives that can be seen in the table below.

In 2016 the Education Commission calculated that 97% of the estimated financing gap in education should be coming from domestic sources, and 3% from international assistance. Unfortunately, despite the small proportion, international assistance continues to dominate the debate and not enough attention is paid to how to raise the majority of the funds in a sustainable way that encourages sustainable

economic growth, strengthens governance, protects the environment and complies with human rights. Progressive tax reform can address all of these and should be at the centre of plans to finance the SDGs.

The Incheon Declaration recommended a minimum allocation of 15–20% of the government budget to education, with low-income countries requiring a minimum of 20%. For too many years the education community has been fixated on the share of the

budget competing with other priorities such as health, without understanding the dynamics that underpin the size of the government budget. To adequately finance education to achieve SDG4 and for countries to fulfil their obligations towards the right to education, they need to increase the **4Ss**:

1. **Share** of the budget to a minimum of 20%;
2. the **Size** of the budget by increasing the tax/GDP through progressive tax reform;

3. the **Sensitivity** of the budget, by ensuring that the budget allocation follows an equity criteria;
4. and the **Scrutiny** of the budget, by ensuring transparency, participation, efficiency, and accountability.

Without getting technical, the most democratic and sustainable way to increase the size of the budget is through progressive taxation. Progressive taxation or tax justice, promotes the **4Rs**: **R**evenue, generating sustainable funds for public services such as education; **R**edistribution, to curb vertical and horizontal inequalities (those between individuals and those between groups); **R**epricing, to limit public “bads” such as tobacco consumption or carbon emissions; **R**epresentation, to build healthier democratic processes, recognising that higher reliance of government spending

If we are serious about achieving SDG4, we need to focus on sustainable domestic resource mobilisation, both increasing revenue and reducing revenue loss through illicit financial flows and corruption.

on tax revenues is strongly linked to higher quality of governance and political representation.

The table above illustrates the current education financing linking it to the revenue lost to tax incentives in five countries. These countries vary in terms of the share of the government budget allocated to education, with Senegal going over the recommended 20% (although data from other sources also has Ghana surpassing the 20% benchmark), with Nepal, and particularly Zambia and Uganda chronically allocating shamefully low shares to education. Although advocacy to ensure that countries reach or maintain an adequate share of the budget is vital, if we are serious about education financing,

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we need to look at the size of the government budget, which is intimately linked to the tax to GDP ratio. The table shows that none of the five countries reach even the low bar of a 20% tax to GDP ratio (contrasting with the 41.3% average in the European Union, accounting for 89.3 % of total government revenue in 2020). Not only these 5 countries have low tax to GDP ratios, particularly Uganda or Ghana, but also, many of them show an overdependence on indirect taxation (such as VAT or sales taxes) which tend to be more regressive, as is the case for Nepal and Senegal. Tax incentives have been used to attract foreign direct investment, although there is much research showing that more often than not, they are unnecessary, and the IMF now consider most forms of tax incentive to be harmful to the economy. The table provides estimates in terms of the revenue losses to these harmful tax incentives and what 20% of that amount could have provided for in terms of education inputs. The TaxEd Alliance partners in these countries are engaging with their respective governments to address these issues, proposing progressive tax reforms to fill the education financing gap.

When government revenue falls short there are increases in the proportion of education spending borne by households, which now reaches 38% in low-income countries (EFW, 2021). This is a profoundly regressive way of financing education, which exacerbates gender and other social inequalities, widening vertical and horizontal inequalities, within and between countries. Considering that the abolition

of school fees in the early 2000s was pivotal to gains in school enrolment and achieving gender parity in many countries, the growing discourse on ‘affordability’ leading to more costs passed on to families, is deeply problematic and can undo the progress we have achieved in the last couple of decades. If we are serious about achieving SDG4, we need to focus on sustainable domestic resource mobilisation, both increasing revenue and reducing revenue loss through illicit financial flows and corruption. Countries must fulfil their obligations to provide free public education of the highest attainable quality by increasing the size, share, sensitivity, and scrutiny of the budget, to give the necessary resources to public schools, and to adequately regulate private providers.

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MARIA RON-BALSERA finished her PhD in Education from Bielefeld University (Germany) in 2014, with a Marie Curie Fellowship. She also holds an MSc in Human Rights from the London School of Economics and an LLM in Human Rights from Universidad Carlos III in Madrid. She has done research at the Institute of Education (UCL) as a visiting research associate, and at UC Berkeley through a research exchange program. She is currently working as the Tax and Education Alliance Coordinator, a transnational partnership that brings together ActionAid, Education International, Global Campaign for Education, Tax Justice Network and the Global Alliance for Tax Justice.

UNESCO ASSOCIATED SCHOOLS IN AUSTRIA

“Learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, learning to live together”

UNESCO Associated Schools comprise a world-wide network of over 11,500 educational institutions in 182 countries. The 96 Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools are part of this international network and contribute to the preservation of peace and security by acquainting young people with the concepts of understanding, tolerance, and friendship between all nations and peoples at the earliest possible age.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **UNESCO Associated Schools / 2021 Conference**

Since 1997, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO has been organising annual networking meetings for all of the Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools' contact persons.

These annual conferences make a significant contribution to further training, faculty networking, and the exchange of ideas. In workshops and lectures, on field trips, and via project-based exchange, the UNESCO Associated Schools' contact persons can acquire new knowledge and skills as well as encourage each other to take on challenging in-class projects specially designed for children and adolescents. 13th and 14th October 2021 saw the annual conference once again held virtually. The theme of this year's conference was “Futures of Education”, in keeping with the projection report: “Reimagining Our Futures Together: A New Social Contract for Education”. The focuses of this conference were of a substantive and structural nature: in terms of substance, there were workshops on intangible cultural heritage and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Structurally, deep insights were provided into the educational work of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and its entire range of activities including an outlook featuring future projects for Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools. Finally, the “Market of Possibilities”

offered teachers an opportunity to engage in virtual exchange. This event was participated in by representatives of 75 schools.

- **The Magazine FORUM**

The annually published periodical FORUM shows the wide variety of approaches and the great creativity and dedication brought to bear by Austria's UNESCO Associated Schools in their implementation of UNESCO's guiding principles and their respective annual themes. The current issue of FORUM (vol. 33/2021) is entitled Futures of Education.

Contributions from 50 UNESCO Associated Schools document the diversity of the topics with which their students dealt practically in class during the 2020/2021 academic year. The fundamental emphasis lay on the SDGs, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, meaning that the schools went in depth on biodiversity, sustainability, and climate change but also dealt to an increased degree with topics such as civil courage, integration, peace education, and human rights due to the special conditions of virtual and hybrid teaching associated with the ongoing pandemic. For example, there were several online remedial tutoring projects by and for students as well as donation drives and assistance projects for people living in precarious circumstances. And fully in keeping with the “Futures of Education” theme of the abovementioned projection report published by UNESCO, there were also participative workshops and projects that gave students the opportunity to help actively shape their everyday lives at school, the actual rooms and places where they learn, and even individual lessons. A further important theme of the report is that of teaching about the use of digital tools in a way that enables students to acquire the relevant technical skills as well as the critical spirit and distance needed to use them in ways that make sense.

UNESCO-SCHULEN

Founded by UNESCO in **1953**

Over **11,500** educational institutions in **182** countries

Austria has participated since **1957**, with schools of all types in all **9** federal provinces

96 UNESCO associated schools,
20 candidate schools

Guiding principles: learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, learning to live together

Themes: peace and human rights education, global citizenship education, education for sustainable development, cultural education, Sustainable Development Goals

Role of the ÖUK: national coordination of advising, project initiation, informational activities, and cooperation; one three-day conference annually; FORUM magazine, website

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/:

Central informational website with a list

of all Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools, current events, projects, and projects

• Cultural Education

2019 witnessed the Europe-wide initiation of the UNESCO-EU pilot project "Teaching and Learning with Living Heritage" in cooperation with ten UNESCO Associated Schools, including one from Austria. The ÖUK introduced this project at the annual UNESCO Associated Schools Conference, which took place virtually from 13 to 14 October. November 2021 then saw the ÖUK's intangible cultural heritage and education staff organise a networking meeting between the various bearers of intangible cultural heritage and the contact persons of Austria's UNESCO Associated Schools that was enthusiastically received both by the bearers and by the schools' contact persons. This project is being continued in the 2022 calendar year, during which it will be implemented Austria-wide by UNESCO facilitators.

Further information:

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/lehr-und-lernmaterial/immaterielles-kulturerbe

• SDG Workshops

Due to the great success of "Turning Point. Youth for Sustainable Development", the event series by and for young people in Austria, and due to the great demand coming from schools, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO is expanding its offerings of SDG workshops tailored specifically to the country's UNESCO Associated Schools. Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools will have the opportunity to book online workshops given by SDG experts with various thematic emphases. The broad diversity of available content is suitable for integration into various school subjects.

The participating students, aged 14 to 19, can deal in depth with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from various perspectives in order to expand their knowledge while also getting a feel for the SDGs' multifaceted nature and transdisciplinary applicability. These workshops are interactive and encourage students to deal independently with this complex theme.

SCIENCE

Science embodies the cornerstone of modern, enlightened, democratic societies. Scientific research allows us to identify societal developments and challenges as well as to arrive at answers to the questions of our times. Science is a fundamentally international undertaking; no state is capable of advancing research in isolation. At UNESCO, all Member States work together to strengthen scientific research worldwide amidst the tension between scientific freedom and social responsibility. UNESCO promotes global research on the urgent questions of humankind and supports people in putting knowledge to use in order to build just and inclusive societies.

THE UNESCO SCIENCE PROGRAMMES

The UNESCO Science Programmes

UNESCO's science-related thematic focuses include climate change and the preservation of biodiversity, the advancement of knowledge pertaining to the protection of oceans and coasts, and ensuring the availability of drinking water.

Exemplary here are the longstanding UNESCO programmes Man and the Biosphere (MAB), the Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP), and the International Geoscience Programme (IGCP), all three of which are devoted to researching and protecting the living environment of human beings.

In Austria, these programmes are overseen by the MAB and Geo/Hydro Sciences National Committees at the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

• Man and the Biosphere

The UNESCO programme Man and the Biosphere (MAB) develops the scientific and practical fundamentals upon which the natural basis of our existence as well as biodiversity can be preserved for the long term. The objective here is sustainable development of the relationship between humankind and the environment: achieving a balance between the protection of biological diversity, the promotion of economic and social development, and the preservation of our respective cultural values. This programme's World Network of Biosphere Reserves currently encompasses 727 biosphere reserves in 131 countries. In Austria, four biosphere reserves (Wienerwald, Großes Walsertal, Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, and Unteres Murtal) have been established so far.

Austria is also a highly active participant in the MAB Programme's international decision-making bodies and committees. Austria's Dr. Günter Köck of the Austrian Academy of Sciences currently represents the "Europe and North America" region in the MAB Bureau. Köck, as Austria's delegate to the UNESCO-MAB programme's International Coordinating Council, was also elected in the autumn of 2020 to serve a fourth term as vice-chair of this body and hence of the programme.

• IHP (Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme) and IGCP (International Geoscience Programme)

UNESCO's Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP) is the only intergovernmental programme in the UN system devoted to hydrological research and water management as well as capacity-building in this field. This programme's underlying aim is to support an interdisciplinary and integrated approach to dealing with watersheds and aquifer management that also accounts for the social

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MAB – MAN AND THE BIOSPHERE

The first intergovernmental environmental programme devoted to the **relationship between human beings and their environment** and to the sustainable use of natural resources

Global network of UNESCO biosphere reserves—model regions that work to achieve harmony between the protection of nature, the preservation of biological diversity, and regional development.

4 biosphere reserves in Austria: Großes Walsertal, Wienerwald, Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, Unteres Murtal

Implementation in Austria by the **MAB National Committee**

Role of the ÖUK: information platform for the programme, public relations work

Further information on the "Man and the Biosphere Programme":

dimension of water resources and both supports and helps develop international hydrological and limnological research.

The International Geoscience Programme (IGCP), founded in 1973, supports geoscientific cooperative projects with research focuses that are precisely defined by UNESCO. These projects include the UNESCO Global Geoparks, of which Austria can boast three: Styrian Eisenwurzen, Ore of the Alps, and the transnational geopark Karawanken/Karavanke.

- **UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme**

The UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme, established in 1992, provides important impulses that are intended to anchor UNESCO's concerns at institutions of higher learning. It supports such institutions' research and educational activities as well as their further development by forming university networks and promoting transnational cooperation between institutions.

This programme can now boast a worldwide pool of over 700 participating institutions, ten of which are in Austria.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **4 UNESCO-L'ORÉAL Scholarships in Austria**

The World needs Science – Science needs Women

A central aim of UNESCO's science programmes is to strengthen the role of women in science, particularly in the life sciences. The "L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Initiative" is part of these efforts. Every year, the L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Awards Ceremony at UNESCO's headquarters in Paris sees five prizes worth € 100,000 each as well as fifteen "L'Oréal-UNESCO Rising Talents" scholarships awarded to outstanding woman scientists.

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2021's scholarship recipients and congratulatory speakers: Kerstin Rastädter, Sabine Haag, Monika Malik, Martin Netzer, Alice Laciny, Wioletta Rosolowska, Anna Bregler, Helmut Denk (from l. to r.)

This cooperative relationship also extends to the national level: since 2007, L'Oréal Austria—in cooperation with the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the Austrian Academy of Sciences and with support from the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)—has been awarding four annual scholarships worth € 25,000 each to outstanding young women scientists in Austria. They may be applied for by women who pursue research in the natural sciences, mathematics, and/or medicine.

These scholarships aim to recognise, support, and encourage young women by helping to create role models. They additionally serve to make the general public aware of excellent scientific achievements while also showing them the female face of research.

IHP – INTERNATIONAL HYDROLOGICAL PROGRAMME

1975: first multilateral programme for water research and water management – International Hydrological Programme (IHP)

8th IHP, 2014–2021: in its 8th phase, the IHP is devoted to improving water quality while taking into account local, regional, and global challenges

The core of this programme: sustainable water management, promotion and development of international water research, and global networking

Part of the **2030 Agenda**

Role of the ÖUK: information platform for the programme, public relations work

Further information on the 8th phase of implementation:

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The SDGs and Science UNESCO's science programmes make a significant contribution to all of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The natural sciences, technology, and innovation play particularly central roles here, while the social sciences and humanities make their own contributions toward these goals' achievement by bolstering our understanding of current challenges.

UNESCO's natural science programmes make their largest contributions toward the achievement of **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production), **SDG 15** (Life on Land), and **SDG 13** (Climate Action). The organisation's social sciences and humanities programmes most strongly support the realisation of **SDG 16** (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). All science programmes also make contributions to the realisation of **SDG 5** (Gender Equality) and **SDG 17** (Partnerships for the Goals).

Recipients in 2021:

- Dr. Anna Breger, applied mathematician, University of Vienna
- Alice Laciny, PhD, zoologist, Konrad Lorenz Institute for Evolution and Cognition Research
- Monika Malik, MSc, pharmacist, University of Vienna
- Dipl.-Ing.in Kerstin Rastädter, biotechnologist, TU Wien

The scholarship recipients were formally honoured at a ceremony held in the Großer Festsaal at the Austrian Academy of Sciences on 27th October. Dr. Anton Zeilinger, in his opening address, stressed the importance of female role models in science and research. Thereafter, L'ORÉAL Austria's CEO and Country General Manager Wioletta Rosolowska emphasised the great importance of these scholarships to L'ORÉAL. Dr. Sabine Haag, president of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO, spoke of the significance of women in science and research when it comes to looking for innovative solutions for urgent present-day problems that concern us globally. Federal Minister Dr. Heinz Faßmann was represented at this event by Secretary General Martin Netzer, who pointed out the challenges faced by female researchers due to the current situation and spoke to the importance of far-reaching structural measures aimed at achieving gender justice at university-level educational and research institutions.

• UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme

In 2021, the "UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Future Design" was established at the University of Art and Design Linz as the tenth such professorial chair in Austria. The chairholder is Univ.-Prof. Dr. Michael Shamiyeh. The chair enables research on new social techniques and abilities pertaining to innovation and leadership that make it possible to open up alternative perspectives, patterns of thought, and patterns of perception. In this regard, a highly important point is action research on present-day processes of transformation in organisations as well as the analytical reappraisal of historical examples.

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IGCP – INTERNATIONAL GEOSCIENCE PROGRAMME

Founded in **1973**

The core of this programme: worldwide scientific collaboration with an emphasis on North-South collaboration; currently focused on applied geosciences, above all with an eye to dealing with natural disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, and volcano eruptions

UNESCO Global Geopark (UGG) label established in **2015**

161 UGGs worldwide, of which **3** are in Austria

In Austria: overseen by the Geo/Hydro Sciences National Committees at the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW) as part of its Earth System Sciences Programme

Role of the ÖUK: central point of contact for the geoparks together with the ÖAW

The Drava in Croatia

So Many Years Without a Major Misstep – Günter Köck and “his” MAB Programme

Biologist Günter Köck can boast around four decades of involvement in a great number of research projects in the field of environmental toxicology. And since 1997, Köck has been spending his summers in the far northern reaches of Canada, where he investigates the effects of environmental pollution and climate change on fish and occasionally also battles wolves as part of an Austrian-Canadian Arctic research project. Less spectacular, perhaps, but no less important is Köck's second area of professional activity: alongside his research, he has dedicated himself to the coordination of international research programmes. March 2022 saw Köck relinquish some of his functions as he entered semi-retirement. In the following conversation, he takes stock of his professional work within and specifically on behalf of UNESCO's “Man and the Biosphere” Programme.

Günter, you worked for 18 years at the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW) as coordinator of its Earth System Science programme's international thematic orientations, as part of which the Man and the Biosphere National Committee and the National Committee for Geo-/Hydrosciences double as the national committees of their respective UNESCO programmes. You're also

Austria's delegate to the International Coordinating Council of UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB-ICC) and have served several times as the UNESCO MAB Programme's deputy chair. When did you first come into contact with UNESCO and the ÖUK?

It was actually right after I'd assumed my position at the ÖAW in 2004 that I encountered UNESCO, since the seven

national committees we were running at the time included three UNESCO programmes (MAB, IGCP, IHP¹). The ÖUK was, obviously, represented on these national committees. As the 33rd meeting of the MAB International Coordinating Council in Paris in October 2004 drew near, the national committee's then-chair Georg Grabherr—who knew me and my international orientation on account of my Arctic project, which had already been running for seven years by that point—asked me to represent the national committee in Paris. A bit surprisingly, that meeting saw Austria elected to join the MAB Bureau—and I became a vice-chair of the programme. It should be said, though, that this election was a way of saying thank-you to Austria for its willingness to host the meeting of the EuroMAB² group at the Wienerwald Biosphere Reserve in 2005. That meeting, whose organisation and financing was led by the ÖUK, was a huge success and resulted in even more seamless collaboration between the National Committee and the ÖUK.

UNESCO's MAB Programme focuses on the relationship between human beings and their environment. And in view of the threats posed by climate change, this programme is now more relevant than ever. But what sets the MAB programme apart? What's special enough for you to have dedicated so much effort to it?

I've already spent many years deeply involved in environmental research at the University of Innsbruck, and I've been investigating how climate change influences aquatic ecosystems since 1997 as part of my Austrian-Canadian research project in the Arctic. All this explains why I immediately recognised how special the MAB Programme is: it attempts to reconcile the needs of nature and of human beings.

¹ MAB – Man and the Biosphere; IGCP – International Geoscience Programme; IHP – Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme

² EuroMAB – a group comprised of the biosphere reserve managers and MAB national committees of the “Europe and North America” region that meets biannually

With support from the Austrian MAB National Committee, I got involved in the quality improvement process right at the beginning. This process ran for many years and was only just recently concluded, to no small success. Which brings me to one of this programme's outstanding assets: its ability to transform: Over the 50 years of its existence so far, the programme has never shied away from global challenges such as climate change, and it's been given refinements and adaptations about every 10 years. Thanks to this, it's definitely among UNESCO's premier programmes—and amidst an increasingly imbalanced relationship between human beings and the environment, with climate conferences racing from one compromise to the next, it's never been as necessary as it is today.

Austria, as one of the first countries to have taken part in this programme, set up its MAB National Committee at the ÖAW all the way back in 1972, and Austria has continued to be quite present internationally. What does the programme mean to Austria, and what does Austria mean to the programme?

The MAB Programme offers Austria the opportunity to bring environmental protection, the preservation of biodiversity, and regional development into harmony—putting sustainability into actual practice. The four Austrian biosphere reserves—“Großes Walsertal”, “Salzburger Lungau und Kärntner Nockberge”, “Wienerwald”, and “Unteres Murtal”—are not only established nationally as model regions for sustainable development but also play a pioneering international role in their implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Special mention here is certainly deserved by the management of the Nockberge region, who've been quite deeply involved in the MAB Programme and the World Network of Biosphere Reserves for many years now and will be hosting the EuroMAB Group meeting in September

2022. Also noteworthy is the biosphere reserve Unteres Murtal, which has been part of the world's first trans-border biosphere reserve “Mura-Drava-Danube” since 2021.

Looking back upon your many years' worth of activities: What have been your greatest successes to date? What are your favourite memories? And what will you perhaps end up missing someday?

I'd like to say here that my successes would almost certainly not have been possible without the great trust that Georg Grabherr placed in me from the very beginning. Georg wanted to modernise and reorient the National Committee, I thought that its international orientation was too weak, and we therefore complemented each other perfectly. The experience of working together with his successor Arne Arnberger was likewise outstanding. Speaking about one's own successes is a bit difficult, of course, but there are a few things I'm really proud of. Like the fact that Austria's National Committee and its biosphere reserves now feature a strong international orientation and are quite actively involved in the work of the programme at large. And we've also provided financial support to many activities of the international MAB Programme over the years, funding successful research projects in other countries (such as Peru). Which brings me to what's probably the most important point, to what makes our National Committee fairly unique worldwide: the fact that it had its own research budget from the very beginning. That enabled us to do a whole lot of things, and I hope it will stay that way in the future, as well. The Austrian MAB National Committee has built an outstanding reputation for itself in the international community! And what else? Perhaps the two prizewinning books that I initiated, Planet Austria and the Kochbuch der österreichischen Biosphärenparks [Cookbook of the Austrian Biosphere Reserves], which also attracted quite

a bit of attention in the MAB community. And an example of a fond memory would be of how my international colleagues presented me with a cake for my 60th birthday in front of the audience at the MAB-ICC 2019, and of how the Austrian ambassador to UNESCO took me to lunch with prominent MAB collaborators.

I'll enjoy continuing my work for the international MAB Programme for the time being. But one thing I truly will miss someday is the MAB Programme's wonderful internationality, with its opportunities to get to know so many cultures and ways of thinking, to accept them, and to act accordingly. And something I'm really proud of is that throughout all those years during which I represented Austria in Paris, I managed to commit not a single major political or scientific misstep.

This conversation with Dr. Günter Köck has been condensed to save space. The full interview can be found at www.unesco.at.

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GÜNTER KÖCK is a vice-chair of the MAB Bureau and the rapporteur to the International Man and the Biosphere Coordinating Council of UNESCO as well as a member of the Austrian MAB National Committee at the ÖAW, which he chaired for 18 years. He is also a member of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the Scientific Council of the Hohe Tauern National Park as well as a delegate to the International Scientific Committee for Alpine Research. Furthermore, he is among the founding editors of the scientific journal *eco.mont*, which was established in 2009. As an Arctic researcher, Köck is an associated scientist at the Institute for Interdisciplinary Mountain Research in Innsbruck and an initiator of the Austrian-Canadian Arctic research project “HighArctic”. This long-term project, led by Köck and Derek Muir (Environment and Climate Change Canada), has been studying the influences of changes to the climate on fish from lakes in the Canadian Arctic since 1997.

CULTURE

Culture is the basis of social cohesion and societal advancement. Its diverse forms of expression—from historical architecture to living traditions and on to contemporary art—are fundamental to the sustainable development of our world. UNESCO has dedicated itself to the furtherance of culture on all levels: it works worldwide to promote clear political conditions and legal frameworks for activities in the cultural field, providing support to Member States as well as local civil society protagonists in order to protect cultural heritage and support cultural diversity.

UNESCO'S CULTURAL FOCUSES: CULTURAL DIVERSITY | WORLD HERITAGE | PROTECTION OF CULTURAL PROPERTY | INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE | The working emphases of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO in the cultural field are oriented toward active implementation of UNESCO's seven culture-related conventions. Special attention is paid to promoting the diversity of cultural expressions, to the protection and safeguarding of tangible and intangible cultural heritage, and to the protection of cultural property.

PROTECTING AND PROMOTING DIVERSITY in the Arts and Culture

The *UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* promotes the diversity of cultural expressions as the facilitation of diverse modes of creation, production, dissemination, and distribution of as well as participation in the arts and culture. The core purpose of the Convention is to ensure states the right to independent arts and cultural policy so that the arts and culture shall not be reduced to their economic aspects.

This Convention is the first international legal instrument to recognise that cultural goods and services function as bearers of identity and expressions of values and aesthetic positions. Though they do also carry economic significance as wares and consumable products, their value is not limited to that which can be expressed in financial terms.

In its Article 16, "Preferential Treatment for Developing Countries", the Convention places global structures of inequality and the disadvantaging of the Global South firmly in focus. This provision obligates the Global North to implement measures that support both the mobility of arts and cultural professionals as well as the exchange of cultural goods and services from the Global South.

The Austrian Commission for UNESCO serves as a National Point of Contact for questions regarding the Convention's implementation in Austria. A central concern of the ÖUK is dialogue and cooperation with relevant stakeholders in order to shape favourable structures and overall conditions for cultural diversity in Austria.

Advising and Supporting Bodies

Advisory Panel on Cultural Diversity: supports the ÖUK in the coordination of all matters pertaining to the Convention.

Working Group on Cultural Diversity: dialogue platform for the active involvement of civil society.

The core purpose of the Convention is to ensure states the right to independent arts and cultural policy so that the arts and culture shall not be reduced to their economic aspects.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 8: Decent Work: social and economic security is essential for both artists and cultural workers in order that they may engage in free artistic and creative work. **SDG 10:** Promoting the diversity of cultural expressions goes hand in hand with reducing inequality within and among countries. **SDG 16** and **SDG 17:** A fundamental pillar of the Convention is participation by and partnership with civil society; only in this manner—in the cultural field, as elsewhere—can policies be shaped in a way that is transparent, participative, and needs-oriented.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **Forum Fair Culture**

The event series *Forum Fair Culture* was launched in December 2020 as a collaborative effort between the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the organisation “kulturen in bewegung”. It opened up space to discuss the obligation to afford preferential treatment in (post-)migrant Austria as well as interconnections with the thematic area of antidiscrimination. Discursive formats questioned what “southern perspectives” actually are, as well as which forms of discrimination, exclusion, and racism play influential roles in Austria. The purpose of preferential treatment is to balance out the existing imbalance between the so-called Global North and South—a process that, in a globalised society, needs to unfold not only between states but also within national borders. Accordingly, preferential treatment—and, associated therewith, development toward greater justice—also applies to community work in Austria, which makes it possible to more closely examine the cultural sector’s actual inclusiveness. The Austrian Commission for UNESCO’s collaboration with “kulturen

in bewegung” made it possible to gain insights into actual practice and take stock of the present situation. A total of four events were held in various live and online formats. The most important findings were published in the form of a booklet.

- **2021 Closed Conference of the Working Group on Cultural Diversity in Graz**

2021 saw the Austrian Commission for UNESCO host a renewed edition of the Closed Conference on Cultural Diversity at Forum Stadtpark in Graz. In a detailed Final Communiqué, the undersigned experts of the Working Group on Cultural Diversity presented their findings concerning the current state of and progress made in implementing the *UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions*. The discussions centred on questions and demands pertaining to the social and economic situation of cultural workers, critiques of discrimination, artistic mobility, and numerous further topics. “In the current deep-reaching crisis, it is radical processes of reconsideration in the political and economic sectors that have become most crucial to survival. Protagonists from the cultural sector are developing feasible visions and indeed already living them. It is high time that such individuals are not only heard but also afforded the standing that they deserve on account of their indispensability. It is hence imperative that a sufficient basis be created upon which arts and cultural professionals can survive in an environment that values their work,” states the preamble of the Final Communiqué.

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CONVENTION on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions

2005 adopted by UNESCO

2006 ratified by Austria

151 States Parties (150 states plus the European Union)

120 projects for the structural reinforcement of cultural creation supported in

62 countries in the Global South by the "International Fund for Cultural Diversity"

166 periodic, publicly available national reports on implementation, including

3 Austrian implementation reports (2012, 2016 and 2020)

Role of the ÖUK: maintaining the Convention's Austrian Point of Contact

ÖUK Priorities: informing and advising, dialogue forums for inter-ministerial coordination and the involvement of civil society, representation of Austria in UNESCO governing bodies on the Convention, public relations work

• Artistic Freedom: The kùltür gemma! Fellowship

Beginning in November 2021, the ÖUK hosted a latest recipient of the six-month kùltür gemma! Fellowship for work on the topic of artistic freedom. This fellowship is worth € 1,300 per month. In keeping with the intentions of kùltür gemma!, it offers an arts or cultural professional who defines him/herself as a migrant or a person of colour the opportunity to develop a project having to do with the theme of artistic freedom. kùltür gemma! fellow Daria Tchapanova used a video project to address the topic of artistic mobility with the objective of using artists' and cultural workers' voices to render barriers to mobility visible. After all: artistic freedom does not necessarily equal freedom of art. The former is far-reaching and also has to do with the mobility of artists and cultural workers. Reality, however, shows that artists from non-EU countries classified as "third country nationals" have difficulty pursuing their work freely in Austria due to bureaucratic and structural challenges.

• Digital Transformations: Fair Culture on the Internet

In 2019, UNESCO published an Open Roadmap for the Implementation of the *Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* in the Digital Environment. This roadmap serves the Parties to the Convention as a benchmark for the Convention's implementation in the digital era. In 2021, furthermore, Laura Wiesböck conducted an analysis on the state of its implementation in Austria for the Austrian Commission for UNESCO. The findings from her analysis, intended to provide the starting point for a National Roadmap in the spirit of the UNESCO Convention, were presented and discussed on 14 December 2021 as part of an expert workshop on the topic of a "Fair Digital Future for the Arts and Culture". The Open Roadmap is aimed primarily at state protagonists, but it is also important to recognise that experts from civil society are already contributing to implementation and that such experts can make a valuable contribution in this regard in the future. Collaboration in the digital environment between protagonists from both the arts and cultural sector and the cultural and creative industry was bolstered by this exchange, thus making a lasting contribution to the further development of measures.

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What it means to decolonize is to restore humanity

Why do we speak of decoloniality? Why do we need decolonial strategies? A conversation between Sara Hassan and Jumoke Sanwo, participants in the Forum Fair Culture, gives insight into the many layers of (post)coloniality

Sara: I have the impression that the term “decolonialization” has become such a trend. All of a sudden, every institution claims to practice it, and everything is intersectional and decolonial. When I hear that claim, I want to dig into that and ask: What is it precisely that you want to do? Do you actually want to work decolonially? Or do you just want to make it look like you do?

Jumoke: That is a really interesting question – we look at decolonization

from the context of our realities. For example, I live in the city of Lagos, West Africa. So therefore, that terminology has a different connotation for me versus somebody else who has a completely different reality. Even within the same geographical construct. The essence is to question what decolonial means. To even begin to have this conversation we must begin from the same premise. What aspect of decolonization are we engaging with? You are in New York, Sara, I am in Lagos.

Colonization of the world at large meant that it had a profound — and still has — a profound influence in how people move, think, and speak.

Sara: Yes! All these layers that you just laid open allow an insight into the multitude of colonial practices. This is what it is truly about. This is what I want to ask people who express that they want to “decolonize” this, that, and the third: Are you truly willing to acknowledge that colonization of the world at large meant that it had a profound — and still has — a profound influence in how people move, think, and speak? When you ask these kinds of questions, the air in the room is getting a little tense, because an anxiety of certain institutions emerges, when realizing that if they sift through all of these layers of imperial violence, at the end of the day there might not be much left. If they really decolonize themselves.

Jumoke: I loved what you just said. Very interesting is also the idea of the urgency to decolonize – where is the urgency coming from?

Sara: Yes. When engaging in decolonial practices and approaches, when it is coming from a hegemonial space, from a space of power, it is often not so much about allowing “the other” person to be the human they are and a person with agency. Within these hegemonial practices the colonized subject is asked to show the colonizer the way out.

Bringing back the artefact in itself does not actually solve anything.

Jumoke: The reality of decolonization is that there are certain steps that need to take place. It has to go through many different stages, and it has not even started. We have all of these conversations ongoing, even in cultural spaces. There is now a drive to repatriate the items that were looted during the imperial project. But the real challenge is, what has happened to culture on the continent? What is the people’s relationship to the artefacts that were taken? Bringing back

the artefact in itself does not actually solve anything. It is an act that would soothe the consciousness of the colonizers, but it has very little impact on the colonized. I am very skeptical about this whole drive for decolonization.

Sara: That is the center of the problem, because it does not restore anything, but it is a prolongation of existing power relationships. You need to start thinking about how justice can be restored.

Jumoke: There is also the economic factor. The artefacts generated income. The value of some of these artefacts have now been transformed into digital assets. If an object has been at a museum for hundreds of years generating revenue, what percentage of the total revenue are you repaying back?

Sara: This is very telling, because the artefacts without the process, the trail and the flow of capital do not mean so much. When we are talking about decolonization, we need to talk money. We need to talk capital.

Jumoke: We want to have true conversations about development, also in cultural spaces, which is a space that I am very much involved in. What sort of economic system is currently affecting the cultural space? The government, local authorities are not investing in culture. What is UNESCO doing about this for example? We have to begin having conversations about the budget ratio that actually goes to cultural development. What about the cultural policy? I think the last update that was done here (in Lagos, Nigeria) was probably in the 1980s or thereabout. How do we ensure that cultural policies are up to date, facing the present and current needs of the community?

Decolonization of the heart

Sara: I am very impressed by, – I guess it is also still my generation – younger activists. They are very articulate, very self-aware, very powerful. But I am sometimes worried that now that we have all these amazing tools, many lenses, many very sharp knives to cut

through all of these levels of systemic oppression, how do we use these tools? Maybe also with each other? How can we truly build collectives where violence is not reproduced? The only way out is to work in collectives and to resist the idea of divide and conquer. Everybody is talking about decolonization of the mind, but sometimes I feel like, what about decolonization of the heart?

Jumoke: Absolutely, I completely agree with you. I think basically what needs to be introduced is the existence of the soul in general in public discourse.

We have programs at Revolving Art Incubator like “Words as therapy”, that have helped people significantly, using poetry as a way of healing, connecting to the core of their humanity. Because at the end of the day you realize, we need to go back to humanity. One of the ways that the imperial project took hold of the continent was the fact that people were considered savages. It took away their humanity and objectified them. Is the North willing to engage with people in the Global South as humans? If they are willing to do that, the interaction changes completely. And we would not even need to have long conversations about what it means to decolonize. What it means to decolonize is to restore humanity to public discourse in the Global North and South. That is all, that is what it means. Just very simple.

The Forum Fair Culture initiative, a joint project of *kulturen in bewegung/VIDC* and the Austrian Commission for UNESCO, opened the space to reflect on power relations in international cultural politics. The organizers of the forum conducted an extensive conversation with Sara Hassan and Jumoke Sanwo, excerpts of which are printed here. The long version of the text can be found in the publication “Critical Diversity - Reflections of the Forum Fair Culture” at www.unesco.at/publikationen.

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SARA HASSAN is a publicist, moderator, podcaster. She has been working in the field of political communication since 2012, most recently specifically at the intersection of political education and knowledge transfer. Hassan produces podcasts with an explicitly anti-racist, intersectional-feminist approach. She is co-author of the 2020 book “Grauzonen gibt es nicht,” a text about abuse of power and how we can recognize the first signs of it. She lived in Brussels for five years, worked there among others for the European Parliament and then started her own business. Today she works as a moderator and gives lectures on the abuse of power.

JUMOKE SANWO is a visual storyteller and cultural producer from Lagos, Nigeria. She holds a Bachelor of Arts (B.A) in English Studies from the Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-ife in Nigeria. As an artist, she works primarily in Photography, Video Art and Virtual Reality. Her work reflects on self-perception and separation experienced through time and space, while rethinking and engaging the discourse on spatiality and temporality in postcolonial societies.

INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE

Creativity, Identity, Continuity

Intangible cultural heritage is everywhere. In many people's lives, some tradition, custom, and/or form of knowledge plays an important role. For some, this may be something like the Traismauer Nativity Play, Manual Graphic Printing, Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen*, or *Gautschen*. These examples have in common their status as part of the intangible cultural heritage to be found in Austria. "Intangible Cultural Heritage" as defined by UNESCO encompasses numerous areas including cultural practices, rituals, experiential knowledge, and masterful craftsmanship. Each such area contains a diversity of traditions that are important to the identities of their practitioners as well as to society at large. The *Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage* (2003), which Austria ratified in 2009, brings precisely this diversity to light. Here, the central focus is on those people who carry forward the knowledge associated with such practices.

© Hans P. Wieland

Historical and Decorative Painting Techniques Using Traditional Materials

The Austrian National Inventory of the Intangible Cultural Heritage

The National Inventory makes the diversity of living cultural heritage visible. It describes not only traditions' processes and content but also traditions' significance to the identity of their bearers, it highlights successful models of dealing with resources, and it provides impulses for sustainable living. The National Inventory was established in 2010, and its currently 147 entries contribute to a better understanding of the astounding diversity of living knowledge and practices to be found in Austria.

An interdisciplinary Advisory Panel on Intangible Cultural Heritage makes regular decisions regarding traditions' inscription on the Austrian Inventory and any nominations of national elements for one of UNESCO's three international lists.

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Gautschen

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Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen* and Wearing of Women's Traditional Dress

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• International Nominations and Incriptions

On 31 March 2021, Timber Rafting was nominated for inscription on UNESCO's Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. This nomination arose on the basis of international cooperation between timber rafters in Germany, Latvia, Poland, Spain, and the Czech Republic. A prerequisite for this nomination's submission at the international level is the national listing of a corresponding element in each of the participating countries. In Austria, "Knowledge of Timber Rafting on the Upper Drava" has been part of the National Inventory since 2014, with this element of cultural heritage being upheld by 150 rafters, volunteers, and associations.

2021 also featured a focus on traditional irrigation methods. Starting from the element "Meadow Irrigation in Tyrol", Austria coordinated the preparation of a nomination for the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. This multi-national nomination was joined by in by bearers, experts, and NGOs from Belgium, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland. Between December 2020 and March 2021, a series of regular online workshops were held that culminated in a combined meeting for exchange in Zams, Tyrol in October of 2021. There, the participants collaborated on preparing the nomination file and were also introduced to the Tyrolean method of meadow irrigation. Submission of this nomination is planned for March 2022.

• New Admissions to the National Inventory

In 2021, the National Inventory of the Intangible Cultural Heritage in Austria was expanded by 14 traditions that were presented publicly as part of the conferral of certificates held in the village of Obertraun by the Hallstättersee.

- Knowledge of Alpinism and Skills of Mountain and Ski Guides (Austria-wide)
- Traditional Craftsmanship in Gmunden: Pottery Flaming (Upper Austria)
- The Custom Tailoring of Men's Full Evening Dress (Austria-wide)
- *Garnierspenzer*, Hat, and *Steppmieder* (Salzburg)
- *Gautschen* (Austria-wide)
- Historical and Decorative Painting Techniques Using Traditional Materials (Austria-wide)
- Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen* and Wearing of Women's Traditional Dress (Vorarlberg)
- Nativity Scene Traditions in Austria (Austria-wide)
- Manual Graphic Printing (Austria-wide)
- The Traismauer Nativity Play (Lower Austria)
- Dry Stone Walling (Austria-wide)
- South Bohemian Brass Band Music in Brand-Nagelberg (Lower Austria)
- The Knowledge of Artisanal Millers (Burgenland, Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Salzburg, Styria, Tyrol, Vorarlberg)
- *Anklöpfeln* (Knocking on Doors) in Stans (Tyrol)

© Max Mayrhofer

Conferral of Certificates in Obertraun

© alpsoul / Johannes Mair

Mountain guides at work in the Stubai Alps

© Knize&Comp

The Custom Tailoring of Men's Full Evening Dress

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Intangible Cultural Heritage and Reducing the Effects of Natural Disasters (SDG 11.5) The further development of centuries-old knowledge about dealing with and assessing natural hazards and conditions strengthens the ability to adapt in response to climate-related hazards and natural disasters. “Avalanche Risk Management” (inscription on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, 2018) and “Knowledge of Alpinism and Skills of Mountain and Ski Guides (admitted to the National Inventory in 2021) have been handed down orally and developed further over numerous generations, and they are now also being added to via professionalisation and scientific research. This knowledge, constantly adapted to a changing natural environment, contributes to the ability to deal safely and sustainably with nature in the Alpine region.

- **A Focus on Intangible Cultural Heritage and Education**

The safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage lives from the creative process of transmission from one generation to the next, and it is closely linked with matters of education and outreach.

2021 saw an online workshop held in cooperation with UNESCO, the EU, and the UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet) that introduced educational materials for German-speaking educators. These materials demonstrate how one can go beyond just teaching about ICH to render it graspable by using ICH itself. This workshop also introduced the Austrian project “Teaching and Learning with Living Heritage. Design and Creation of a ‘Glöcklerkappe’”. This presentation was complemented by an additional workshop, held during the autumn, that brought together tradition bearers and teaching personnel for the purpose of exchange concerning possible cooperative efforts.

Screenshot from the introduction of UNESCO’s toolkit for teachers

- **Periodic Report**

The so-called Periodic Report is one of the Convention’s key mechanisms in terms of both national progress and international cooperation. It allows states and communities to benefit from the experiences of other States Parties and to exchange information on effective safeguarding measures and strategies. This report conveys an overall impression of the past few years and highlights Austria’s activities as they relate to the Convention. The present Periodic Report is Austria’s second report concerning the 2003 Convention (the first of which was published in 2015). It reflects the Convention’s implementation to date and lays out a forward-looking way in which to continue. In its report, special attention was paid to the input and feedback of the individual bearers and the various stakeholders on the national, regional, and local levels. Here, the ÖUK functions as a point of coordination.

CONVENTION for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage

- 2003** adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO

- 2009** ratified by Austria

- 180** States Parties

- 529** elements on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity

- 71** elements on the List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Need of Urgent Safeguarding

- 29** proven programmes, projects, and activities aimed at safeguarding intangible cultural heritage

- 147** traditions in the National Inventory of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Austria

Role of the ÖUK: awareness-raising in the interest of safeguarding, conveying, and supporting intangible cultural heritage in Austria; compilation of the National Inventory

Topics for the ÖUK in 2021: inscription of 14 further traditions on the Austrian National Inventory of ICH; emphases: ICH and education; knowledge concerning nature and the universe; international cooperation

• Cooperation with Sudan: Digital National Inventory

The UNESCO project *Strengthening National Capacities for Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage in Sudan* saw the ÖUK, the UNESCO field office in Khartoum, and the Sudanese National Commission for UNESCO collaborate to compile a digital inventory of the intangible cultural heritage of Sudan. The ÖUK prepared the technical foundation for this and also worked closely with national stakeholders in Sudan to guide the project editorially.

Digital inventory of the intangible cultural heritage of Sudan – Website

• International

During 2021, Austria took part in a UNESCO Working Group convened in order to engage in some long-awaited reflection on the international lists. This included discussion of improvements to both the nomination process and the process for removing elements from the international lists as well as discussion of proposals for dealing with the rising number of nominations to all three lists. The discussion outcomes were adopted at the 16th meeting of the Intergovernmental Committee.

The knowledge and practices that have accumulated over time are employed in order to use natural resources sustainably and minimise the effects of climate change. Intangible cultural heritage can contribute to the protection of biological diversity and to ecological sustainability.

© Albert Janssen

Traditional Irrigation in Europe – A Practice that Brings People Together

One of 2021's main themes in the area of intangible cultural heritage was that of traditional irrigation methods. Bearers of relevant traditions from Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland worked together throughout the year to prepare the according nomination to the international Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. But what is traditional irrigation, and why is it important not only to those who practice it but also to the regions where it is practiced? Karina Liechti of the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) provides a glimpse into this important form of intangible cultural heritage, which is held in common by so many countries and people.

witteren, flüxen, rieseln, wassern, fléizen, bevroeien, irriguer par ruissellement, wässru...

The traditional irrigation of interest here is a centuries-old way of bringing water to cultivated plants in the interest of their optimum growth. Practised on both flat and sloping land, it is based on the deliberate use of gravity and on hand-built infrastructure such

as canals and ditches designed to bring water from springs, glaciers, streams, and rivers closer to areas under cultivation. Damming up the water creates spill-over that can then be used to irrigate agricultural land. At the same time, this serves to build up and fertilise soil in a natural manner. This type of irrigation is an elaborate activity based on a huge amount of experience. In Upper Valais (Switzerland),

for example, irrigators use *Wässerplatten* [watering boards], water irons, and slabs of stone to dam up and direct water, which is then “drawn” across the meadows with a *Wasserhau* [watering axe]¹. Then, beneath the meadows, the excess *Zettwasser* has to be guided away. Accomplishing this requires a deep understanding of the landscape, weather conditions, the topography, and the flow of water.

¹ Schweizer R, Rodewald R, Liechti K, Knoepfel P. 2014. Des systèmes d'irrigation alpins entre gouvernance communautaire et étatique – Alpine Bewässerungssysteme zwischen Genossenschaft und Staat. Zurich/Chur: Rüeegg.

Impoundment of water with a watering board

Impoundment of water on the Mals Heath, Italy

...and a whole lot more:

The practice of traditional irrigation goes far beyond simply the provision (i.e., the capture, redirection, and distribution) of water²: it is a complex socio-ecological system in which factors such as a collective form of organisation with established rules concerning the allocation of water, rights, and obligations as well as the constant renewal of knowledge refined over generations and the associated cultural anchoring in local and regional identities and traditions enjoy equal priority. Major tasks

such as the construction of canals are typically organised collaboratively by the affected water-users, who are united in water cooperatives. The allocation of water to the primarily agricultural users is done according to recognised, documented water rights and an established rotation (the so-called *Kehrordnung*; on this, see the excerpt from a historical *Kehrordnung*). Maintenance of the irrigation facilities (water intakes, canals, distribution systems, etc.) is done mostly as a group (and hence referred to as *Gemeinwerk*, or “common work”)³. Today, however, the involvement and

support of public authorities and further organisations is desired and indeed necessary.

Presence in Europe

Traditional irrigation is done in both flat and mountainous areas and is hence present in most European countries, even in Northern Europe. There exists an extremely wide diversity of systems, from traditional to modern, from small to vast, and from vital to deteriorating. As part of a project to inventory traditionally irrigated sites in Europe, it has so far been possible to identify 130 locations where traditional irrigation is documented historically, preserved in the form of landscape relics and cultural relics, or still practiced as a way of working the land⁴. While traditional irrigation was widely employed prior to the invention of modern sprinkler systems and electrical pumps, only a few traditionally irrigated areas have remained so to this day.

The Diverse Functions of Traditional Irrigation

Alongside its primary agricultural significance, traditional irrigation performs a variety of additional functions. Thanks to the construction of canals, locks, and/or water wheels and to slope irrigation, many places saw the emergence of a mosaic of drier and moister sites, areas of high species diversity, and hence a multitude of habitats and landscape qualities. Irrigated landscapes are also viewed as attractive and are hence playing an increasingly prominent role in tourism. In mountainous regions, canals carrying water bring moisture to mountain forests and thereby stabilise the slopes, provide water with which to fight forest fires, and help prevent floods by enabling surface water to be regulated and diverted. Furthermore, often peculiar structures used to feed

Workshop in Zams, October 2021

² Leibundgut C, Kohn I. 2014. “European traditional irrigation in transition part I: Irrigation in times past – a historic land use practice across Europe.” *Irrigation and Drainage*, 63(3), 273–93.

³ ⁴ Leibundgut C, Vonderstrass I. 2016. *Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe Europas*. Langenthal: Merkur.

Excerpt from the historical water regulations of the Niwärch Water Canal, 1381 (Ausserberg, Switzerland)

The cooperative members of the new water canal Niwärch, in the presence of the cleric Nycolinus von Mohlhussen of the Diocese of Munich, conclude the following water regulations⁵:

- 1) Johannes Tufecher am Bort is to have the right to the water canal of half a day and half a night. The heirs of the deceased Johannes Mathien von Baltschieder one quarter. Hans, son of the deceased Furer am Ranfte, one quarter. Petrus am Troyen... (list continues; 14-day rotation);
- 2) The water is to go from one to the other, distributed as above;
- 3) It has been decided that if a break in the water canal should occur, no matter on what day or at what hour this may happen, the entitled member shall receive his water as soon as the canal has been repaired;
- 4) He who has a share in this water canal now or in the future must perform his work or pay seven dinars for a day's work in accordance with the magnitude of his obligation. If one should fail to perform his work (...), then the members of the cooperative are entitled to punish the delinquent by replacing him with another with no possibility of objection by the judge or any other;
- 5) Should a break in the water canal occur due to force majeure (...), now or in the future, each member must perform his work in accordance with the share that he holds. He must otherwise pay ten dinars per day's work.

and distribute water, manual labour-intensive traditional irrigation techniques, and common management and use according to longstanding rules and customs are valuable witnesses to a regionally diverse cultural history and building culture. Traditional irrigation is hence of great importance to regional identity, representing a lively and valuable aspect of cultural heritage⁵. Finally, practices of traditional irrigation

provide opportunities for the broad involvement of the non-agrarian population, as well: women and men, children, adolescents, and entire families, people with local roots and migratory backgrounds alike, volunteer to participate in the necessary maintenance work. What's more, traditional irrigation is an interesting object of study—and a traditionally irrigated region is also a place of education for sustainable development.

⁵ Bär R, Liechti K. 2020. Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe mit Zukunft? Naters/Bern: Einblicke-Ausblicke.

⁶ Wasserverordnung – Neuwerk 1381; übersetzt aus dem Lateinischen am 31. Mai 1981 von Emil Schmid, Pfarrer; aus: SAC Ortsgruppe Ausserberg. 1981. 600 Jahre Wasserleitung Niwärch 1381–1981, Ausserberg. Visp: nbv Druck.

International Cooperation and Submission to UNESCO

For all of these reasons, still-active communities from seven European countries came together to submit a multilateral nomination for the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. For many years, now, there have been efforts to bring together still-active irrigators and other involved protagonists as well as to reactivate disused irrigation systems. The international exchange that this entails helps to revitalise traditional irrigation, to support protagonists in their work, and to continually augment knowledge. The attendant international cooperation has also made it possible to set up an International Centre for Traditional Irrigation as Cultural Heritage of Europe (IZTB), which is to open in Switzerland in the autumn of 2022.

The nomination, entitled "Traditional Irrigation in Europe: Knowledge, Technique, and Organisation" will be submitted to UNESCO for inscription on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2022. The text above is based in part on the nomination submitted to UNESCO, to which a multitude of individuals from the participating countries have contributed.

© C. Rytter

KARINA LIECHTI studied geography at the University of Bern. She now works as a project head at the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) and as a researcher at the Centre for Development and Environment (CDE) at the University of Bern. Her work focuses on commons, landscape change, and societal transformation processes.

WORLD HERITAGE

Raising Awareness of Outstanding Universal Value

Since 1972, safeguarding the world's common cultural and natural heritage has been the stated objective of the *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World's Cultural and Natural Heritage* (commonly known as the *World Heritage Convention*). Alongside the concrete protection of what are by now 1,154 world heritage sites of

outstanding universal value, this also includes communication and awareness-raising with regard to the responsibilities and obligations of the States Parties that have ratified the Convention. Austria, by ratifying the Convention in 1992, committed to preserving its unique witnesses to cultural and natural history for future generations in the interest of all of humanity.

The role of the Convention, as one of the most important international legal instruments where the protection of cultural property and nature are concerned, is reflected in its near-complete, universal validity: by now, over 194 States Parties have come to recognise the rights and obligations formulated therein. The importance of this global commitment to cooperatively protect our common heritage is made clear by the increasingly numerous threats to these cultural and natural sites. The consequences of the climate crisis, which are by now becoming quite palpable, affect the preservation of world heritage sites just as directly as do continually intensifying economic pressures.

Even if 2021 brought with it numerous instances of relief compared with the previous year, the challenges stemming from the ongoing global health crisis remained considerable. Alongside economic implications that, among other things, have immediate effects on the preservation of World Heritage sites, the accessibility of these cultural and natural monuments was likewise severely reduced. The numerous initiatives undertaken in the virtual realm were only partly capable of replacing the physical experience of these unique places (which was limited for considerable portions of the year) and the associated manifestation of their value.

For Austria, however, this year also included some welcome aspects: alongside successful efforts to deepen cooperation between the Austrian World Heritage sites, the number of these sites increased by two: with the inscription of "Great Spa Towns of Europe" and of "Danube Limes (Western Segment)" as part of the multinational site "Frontiers of the Roman Empire", Austria can now boast 12 World Heritage sites.

© R. Kuhnbe-Strack

CONVENTION Concerning the Protection of the World's Cultural and Natural Heritage

- 1972 adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO
- 1992 ratified by Austria
- 194 States Parties
- 1,154 World Heritage sites worldwide
- 12 World Heritage sites in Austria

Role of the ÖUK: coordinating office of the Austrian World Heritage Site Conference, support, information, and advising

ÖUK priorities: networking of Austrian World Heritage-related entities, World Heritage education, awareness-raising

➤ **Danube Limes World Heritage:** the so-called "Heathens' Gate" (Heidentor) in Carnuntum, Lower Austria numbers among Austria's best-preserved architectural monuments from antiquity and attests to the significance of this ancient city

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 11: The World Heritage Convention contributes to cities' and human settlements' sustainability by calling for the strengthening of efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage (Target 11.4). **SDG 13:** The protection of cultural heritage contributes to strengthening resilience and the capacity to adapt to climate-related hazards and natural disasters (Target 13.1).

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• 1. Austrian World Heritage Day

At the initiative of the ÖUK and based on a resolution of the Austrian World Heritage Site Conference, 18 April 2021 saw all of the Austrian sites observe of Austria's first World Heritage Day. Taking after the "International Day of Monuments and Sites" and "International World Heritage Day", the "Austrian World Heritage Day"—a shared day of action organised by the Austrian World Heritage sites—is intended to draw attention to and raise awareness of the exceptional universal value of World Heritage in Austria and worldwide. A website created expressly for World Heritage Day (www.welterbetag.at) now functions as a common web presence of the Austrian World Heritage sites. In keeping with the motto "World Heritage is more...", special events and activities will aim to provide unaccustomed views of the familiar, open up new perspectives, and convey an impression of the work and effort that go into protecting and preserving these unique places. Even if 2021's planned Austrian World Heritage Day programme had to go largely unrealised due to the pandemic situation, this day's broad resonance in the media impressively demonstrated the existing interest in the topic of UNESCO World Heritage.

Further information:
www.welterbetag.at

• Extended 44th Session of the World Heritage Committee (Fuzhou, China; online)

From 16 to 31 July 2021, the World Heritage Committee came together once more after a one-year hiatus due to the pandemic. This session, originally scheduled for the summer of 2020 in Fuzhou, was chaired by China and held virtually for the first time. Physically present on location were only a very small number of individuals representing the UNESCO Secretariat. This session was of interest to Austria for multiple reasons. Following the successful inscription of "Great Spa Towns of Europe" (which includes the town of Baden, just south of Vienna), the long-running nomination process for "Frontiers of the Roman Empire – Danube Limes (Western Segment)" was likewise brought to a positive conclusion. Regarding the World Heritage site

"Historic Centre of Vienna", which has been on the List of World Heritage in Danger since 2017, the Committee's positive confirmation of the "Desired State of Conservation" (DSOCR) represented an important step.

• 16th Austrian World Heritage Site Conference (Schönbrunn)

The Austrian World Heritage Site Conference is the most important national forum for cooperation between what are now twelve Austrian World Heritage sites.

From 13 to 14 October 2021, the 16th Austrian World Heritage Site Conference—which had been postponed from the year before—was held in cooperation with the World Heritage site "Palace and Gardens of Schönbrunn". With its theme of "More than a Monument: Monument Protection and Care in the Context of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention", the conference facilitated important discussions addressing the thematic complexes around caring for architectural and horticultural monuments and the handling of buffer zone management. A concluding panel discussion specified types of action that need to be taken in order to successfully protect World Heritage in the future.

Panel discussion

© Stadt Baden/Fürnkranz

Significant elements of this serial World Heritage site are historic baths, such as the former Josefsbad in Baden

Baden as Part of the UNESCO World Heritage Site “The Great Spa Towns of Europe”

On 24 July 2021, “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (GSTE) were inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. And with that, Austria—in what was a surprise to many—became home to a new World Heritage location: the town of Baden, just south of Vienna.

The Path to World Heritage

On 24 July 2021, “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (GSTE) were inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. And with that, Austria—in what was a surprise to many—became home to a new World Heritage location: the town of Baden, just south of Vienna. It was around the end of the 1990s that a number of spa towns simultaneously

voiced the desire to be inscribed on the UNESCO List. The World Heritage Centre in Paris advised them to attempt a serial nomination. In 2012, ICOMOS Germany compiled a thematic study¹ that came to positive conclusions regarding the spa town phenomenon’s potential for successful nomination. For the development of the nomination documents and a common structure for the serial sites as well as for the purpose of coordinating the process, the participating states and cities then set up multiple working groups on the multinational and multicommunal levels: the International Steering Group and the International Working Group with ministry representatives and academics from the various states, the Mayor Steering Group consisting of municipal-level political representatives, and the Site Manager Group with experts from the various spa towns. The overall process was coordinated by a Secretariat-General staffed by Great Britain. The Lead Partner in this nomination process was the Czech Republic.

In 2013, the UNESCO World Heritage Focal Point of the Republic of Austria listed the City of Baden near Vienna, among other places, as a possible candidate for GSTE. 2014 and 2015 saw the International Working Group

develop selection and elimination criteria for the participation of spa towns in the GSTE nomination that ultimately resulted in the list of components since entered into the UNESCO World Heritage List. Between 2016 and 2018, the property borders and buffer zones were defined, the nomination dossier was authored, thematic maps and atlases were compiled, property and local management plans were developed, and cooperation between the various towns was placed on solid foundations. January 2019 then saw all documents submitted to the World Heritage Centre in Paris, after which they were inspected by ICOMOS.

Recognition of GSTE as UNESCO World Heritage

With the pandemic having forced 2020’s planned 44th Meeting of the World Heritage Committee to be cancelled, the Committee’s decision came only a year later. It was thus that on 24 July 2021, the “outstanding universal value” of the GSTE was officially recognised:

The Great Spa Towns of Europe embody an exceptional testament to the European spa phenomenon that experienced its heyday between ca. 1700 and the 1930s. This transnational serial “site” encompasses eleven spa towns in seven countries: Baden bei Wien (AT); Spa (BE); Karlovy Vary, Františkovy Lázně and Mariánské Lázně (CZ); Vichy (FR); Bad Ems, Baden-Baden, and Bad Kissingen (DE); Montecatini Terme (IT); and the City of Bath (UK). This series of towns comprises the most modern, most dynamic, and most international among the hundreds of spa towns that contributed to this European cultural phenomenon.

Although every spa town is structured differently, all such towns have in common their development around mineral water springs that catalysed a spatial model of organisation devoted to healing, therapeutic, recuperative, and social functions. Ensembles of spa buildings include bathhouses, pump rooms,

¹ ICOMOS, National Committee of the Federal Republic of Germany: Europäische Kurstädte und Modebäder des 19. Jahrhunderts; ICOMOS Deutschland Hefte LII 1. Auflage Stuttgart 2012.

drinking halls, facilities for therapeutic treatments, and colonnades and galleries designed to harness the natural mineral water resources and to allow their practical use for bathing and drinking. External and internal treatments (“taking the cure”) were complemented by physical exercise and social activities necessitating facilities like assembly halls, casinos, theatres, hotels, villas, and their attendant infrastructure (ranging from water distribution systems and salt production facilities to railways and funiculars).

All of these facilities are integrated into an overall context of urban planning that encompasses a carefully managed recreational and therapeutic environment comprised of parks, gardens, promenades, athletic facilities, and woods. Buildings and rooms connect visually and physically with the surrounding landscape, which is used regularly for athletic activities that contribute to therapeutic treatments, relaxation, and general enjoyment.

GSTE Local Management, Baden bei Wien

Baden has a long tradition of safeguarding its architectural heritage. And while its inscription on the World Heritage list does further heighten the moral obligation to treat this heritage with care, it entails hardly any need to adjust the regulations that already protect this historic spa town. World Heritage is cross-cutting material. In keeping with this fact, the local management plan envisions the involvement of all levels of Baden’s civil society, political decision-making, and administration. The mayor represents Baden on the GSTE Management Board and also heads local World Heritage site management. Operative implementation is the responsibility of a local site manager and the executive city councillor chosen to handle World Heritage issues. A local steering committee consisting of municipal politicians and administrators, stakeholders, and members of the

© Stadt Baden/Fürnkranz

The urban architecture of the “Great Spa Towns of Europe” is characterised not only by bath and spa facilities, but also by extensive cultural infrastructure such as theatres

Expert Panel on World Heritage will work to further deepen the sense of responsibility for this World Heritage among decision-makers and society at large. Said Expert Panel consists of individuals specialised in the thematic areas relevant to the site’s “outstanding universal value” (OUV). And furthermore, structures are to be created that enable broad involvement of the local populace and stakeholders in World Heritage management.

... not a monument, but a whole philosophy

Eight years of close collaboration have welded the eleven cities’ representatives into an active, forward-looking community that transcends linguistic boundaries and national borders. Management is accompanied by national state representatives as well as by a complex structure representing the eleven GSTE cities and presided over by these cities’ democratically elected mayors. The aforementioned secretariat-general and eleven local site management organisations are charged with monitoring, reporting on, and implementing the management plans. Cooperative programmes have been quick to develop in the areas of tourism, spa medicine, and cultural and youth exchange. Other project ideas are currently being examined.

Cooperation between the local site

managers is being deepened. On questions having to do with monitoring, researching the spa towns’ urban and natural landscapes, and the harmonisation of management objectives, meetings and online workshops are being held on an ongoing basis.

The GSTE, comprising eleven lively spa towns, represent a complex and exceptional piece of world heritage but also an outstanding example of the European spirit and intermunicipal cooperation across national borders. It has given rise to a strong league of cities that is willing and able to ensure its common interests and common heritage and to promote sustainable development.

© Stadtgemeinde Baden

HANS HORNYIK has worked as a civil servant for the Province of Lower Austria since 1980; his work currently involves both the Building Culture and UNESCO World Heritage sites. Hornyik studied communication science and sinology in Vienna and in Taipei from 1985 to 1999. He has been a city councillor of the City of Baden since 2000 and an executive city councillor since 2005 (with responsibility for building from 2005 to 2010, for culture from 2010 to 2020, and for planning since 2020). He has also been the City of Baden’s “UNESCO World Heritage” appointee since 2013.

PROTECTION OF CULTURAL PROPERTY

Bringing Witnesses to the Past into the Future

© Zach Plank / unsplash

CONVENTION on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property

1970 adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO

2015 ratified by Austria

141 States Parties

THE HAGUE CONVENTION for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict

1954 adopted in The Hague; expanded by the Second Protocol in 1999

1964 ratified by Austria

133 States Parties

Role of the ÖUK: provision of support, advising and public relations work; founding member and board member of Blue Shield Austria

ÖUK priorities: support of implementation, participation in the Cultural Property Panel, awareness-raising activities

Beginning with the *Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict*, the period since 1954 has seen UNESCO adopt four conventions under international law aimed at protecting movable and immovable cultural property. In particular, the *Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property*, which celebrated 50 years of existence in 2020, is now increasingly in focus due to the global effects of the illicit cultural property trade.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• Cultural Property Panel

It was in order to network the various protagonists who deal with aspects of protecting cultural property at the national level, especially in the context of the Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property (1970), that Austria's Federal Ministry Of The Interior (BMI) formed its Cultural Property Panel. 2021 once again saw the ÖUK participate in this forum together with other relevant institutions—above all the Federal Ministry of Arts and Culture, Civil Service and Sport (BMKÖS), the Austrian Federal Office for the Care of Monuments (BDA), ICOM Austria, and Blue Shield Austria—in order to support the Convention's implementation.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 13: The protection of cultural property correlates directly with strengthening the resilience and the capacity to adapt to climate-related hazards and natural disasters (Target 13.1). **SDG 16:** The implementation of the UNESCO Convention supports the recovery and return of stolen assets, in particular cultural property, and thus combats organised crime and helps to reduce illicit financial flows (Target 16.4).

COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION

In its efforts pertaining to Communication and Information, UNESCO promotes the development of modern knowledge societies by working to support freedom of opinion and freedom of the press, the development of independent media, and universal access to knowledge and information. In doing so, sustainably preserving and providing access to documents of all kinds—books, manuscripts, photos, films, and audio media—is essential and hence the focus of UNESCO’s Memory of the World programme.

DOCUMENTARY HERITAGE / MEMORY OF THE WORLD PROGRAMME

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 4: Inclusive and equitable quality education can be ensured only if knowledge and information are sustainably preserved and passed on. Democratic access to knowledge and information contributes to gender equality (**SDG 5**) and to the reduction of inequality within and among countries (**SDG 10**). **SDG 9:** Access to knowledge and information also serves to foster scientific and technical innovation.

An important precondition for access to information is the preservation of documents. As carriers of information, documents ensure knowledge transfer, facilitate communication, and form the basis of what we know about historical processes and pasts. In doing so, history's important written works and documents of everyday life are of equally central significance. All of them contribute to the foundation upon which our knowledge and information society stands.

The challenges involved in their preservation are manifold: in addition to the classic problems of physical deterioration, questions of digital storage and preservability are now likewise of the highest relevance. How, for example, do we

ensure the transfer of information stored on data media for which playing and/or reading devices no longer exist?

UNESCO's "Memory of the World" programme, founded in 1992, deals with precisely those themes that are relevant to the preservation of documents—and its International Register helps make visible the documentary heritage of humanity. At the national level, the "Memory of the World" National Committee, which also serves the Austrian Commission for UNESCO as the Advisory Panel on Information Preservation, deals with this complex of themes and maintains the national register "Memory of Austria". This register encompasses and serves to make visible documentary holdings that are of significance to Austria.

A particularly important event for the programme in 2021 was the resolution of a multi-year conflict at the international level that had led to a halt on activities regarding the international register and, consequently, Austria's national register.

MEMORY OF THE WORLD PROGRAMME

Preservation of and Access to Documentary Heritage

1992 programme founded

2014 Initial inscriptions on Austria's National Memory of the World Register; now 59 entries

427 inscriptions on the International Memory of the World Register

15 of these from Austria

59 inscriptions on the Austrian National Register

Role of the ÖUK: administrative support of the National Committee, compilation of the National Register, awareness-raising.

ÖUK priorities: support of the National Committee, submission of international nominations, keeping and maintaining Austria's National Register

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **Working Group on Restructuring the Advisory Panel on Information Preservation / Memory of the World National Committee**

Since 2011, the Memory of the World National Committee has been anchored at the Austrian Commission for UNESCO as an independent advisory panel. Alongside experts from the realms of archiving, history, and document preservation, it also includes representatives of relevant institutions and ministries. In order to react appropriately to current issues and questions, 2021 saw a working group set up that has since been collaborating with outside experts in the development of recommendations for a substantive reorientation as well as an expansion in terms of personnel. This working group has so far urged that regional-level protagonists be involved to a greater extent and that consideration be given to the thematic areas of digitisation and digital humanities as well as restoration, recommendations that were subsequently realised via the restructuring and expansion of the Advisory Panel / National Committee.

Final document of the Congress of Vienna, 1815

Augsburg Confession ("Confessio Augustana"), 1530

"It won't make you famous" – A Conversation on UNESCO's Memory of the World Programme

After many years leading the Memory of the World National Committee, Dr. Dietrich Schüller is handing over its chairmanship to Thomas Just. In this conversation with the ÖUK, the two provide a look at their personal approaches to the topic of documentary heritage.

Dr. Schüller, you've been accompanying the "Memory of the World" (MoW) programme for many years, now—decades, in fact. How did you first encounter the programme?

I was a member of the Advisory Panel on Cultural and Communication Research under the chairmanship of Kurt Blaukopf, who was also a member of the UNESCO Executive Board. I've also been representing Austria in the General Conference as an expert since 1989. Before that, I'd been very actively involved in the establishment of the Technical Committee at the International Association of Sound and Audiovisual Archives. It was in the context of all this that I encountered the Memory of the World Programme, which was founded in 1992. "Digitisation" was already an oft-used buzzword in the early 1990s. But back then, it wasn't yet so much about "born-digital documents"—it was more about providing easy access

to especially valuable and for the most part fragile documents that were inaccessible otherwise. But at the General Conference of UNESCO in 1993, I somewhat rebelliously demanded a more comprehensive concept, saying that we need digitisation not only to ease access but also—and above all—in order to preserve audiovisual documents over the long term. As far as such documents go, it was clear even back then: digitisation is the only way in which they can be preserved for posterity. With documents of the sort, it's the case that the digital surrogate must take the place of the original because neither the original nor the player devices can be preserved in the long run. This led to the invitation to form a working group, the Technical Subcommittee for MoW, which is now called the Preservation Subcommittee. And in 2015, I was also made a member of the International Advisory Committee.

Mr. Just, it was two decades later that you became a member of the MoW National Committee. In your function as Director of the Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv at the Austrian State Archives, you deal with the topic of document preservation on a daily basis. How is this UNESCO programme relevant from your perspective?

Just: Archives in countries like Austria are of course fortunate to have relatively rich holdings. But with our large volume of old materials, we do face the challenge of bringing it all into the digital world—because, for one thing, this content is in demand. And we also want to do so because we'd otherwise become less relevant—and this relevance is very important to us, since it makes the ministries to which we report aware of how we're actually about a whole lot more than just important anniversaries. The other reason is that, as Dietrich

Audio recordings documenting Austrian dialects, 1951–1983

Schüller said, it's our job to preserve things. And in the context of documentary heritage, digitisation is among the options for doing so. Now it's indeed the case that we've long been producing exclusively digital data. But the significance of Austria's archives lies above all in Austria's history, in connection with which there's just so much material that needs to be digitised. So in this respect, it's important to have an Advisory Panel like ours that acts to warn—with an eye to ensuring that this information is preserved and transformed for a new era.

The MoW Programme has gone through several changes over the course of its existence and has also been pitted against challenges, not least due to the international difficulties that brought its Register to a standstill. What do you think about how the programme's developed?

Schüller: I've got to be careful, here. There exists a fundamental problem, namely overemphasis of the Register compared with the actual programme. And I have no qualms about saying this quite loudly, because I was among those who were calling vehemently for the international register and for the recognition of special documents during the mid-1990s. I remember there being a long debate, but only one true opponent: the Secretary-General of the International Council of Archives...

Just: ...That will have been Albada—Joan van Albada.

Schüller: Right. And it turned into a vigorous discussion that ultimately saw the Register's proponents prevail. Albada's stance was that it's impossible to put documents in a hierarchy: a note on a slip of paper, he said, was just as important as the Golden Bull. The majority, on the other hand, viewed a Register as being an indispensable tool for encouraging documents' preservation. But Albada insisted that there

And there literally doesn't exist any document that one could consider more important or less important: the certificate of registration is indeed just as important as the Golden Bull.

were no documents that were "better" or "worse". In any case, the International Register has been a blockbuster ever since its initial inscriptions in 1997—thereby papering over the true purpose of the Memory of the World Programme, which is to encourage States Parties to preserve and expand their holdings of documents and ensure that every document remains accessible to everyone. And there literally doesn't exist any document that one could consider

more important or less important: the certificate of registration is indeed just as important as the Golden Bull.

So the core of this programme is the safeguarding of all documents and not the Register. Mr. Just, you've now assumed the position of chair, and your main job is as the head of an important institution in the field. What are the challenges—as well as the opportunities—that lie ahead when it comes to protecting and preserving our documentary heritage?

Just: This is a question that's both easy and difficult. The one thing is that the documents we produce today are way more fragile than those we've already been holding for a thousand years. Digital documents probably need more attention and care than, say, a parchment document; we know how to store the latter, but in the case of the digital document, we only think we know how. The other thing is getting through to policymakers and raising their awareness—not only of how this Register is a great thing, but also about how even a resident registration certificate is a great thing. Perhaps we should put such a certificate on the list someday—to show how even an inconspicuous object can be so interesting and unbelievably revealing in terms of the information it contains. One essential goal of the Advisory Panel will need to be to advance the National Register and generate more public attention for it. And out in the Austrian provinces, for instance, there are some really great objects. Not everything happens in Vienna, after all!

Dr. Schüller, you're stepping down as chair of the National Committee—but you will, thankfully, be remaining a member. Based on your many years of experience: where do you think the programme is headed, both nationally and internationally?

Schüller: It's only starting now that we'll be getting an inkling of where things will go. On the international level, we've

been through a four-year reform process that had to do mainly with the Register. It was touched off by nominations that were made with the purpose of revealing such things as war crimes but were unacceptable for the states thus addressed. This led to things including clear financial threats. To put it very neutrally: the MoW Programme was beginning to do damage to UNESCO because of the disquiet thus caused¹.

How will the programme develop? At present, we can't yet say. If things continue going well, then the Register will run on quietly and no longer evoke substantial conflict. I'll still be a member of the International Advisory Committee until 2023, and as one of my final efforts there, I'm pushing very hard to have significantly more attention paid to basic training in the preservation of documents. It ultimately comes down to: How do I keep something like an audio-tape? It needs to be digitised; otherwise, its content will be lost because we won't have any more player devices! On the other hand, I don't need to worry much about the papyrus collections if I keep them at their proper temperature and protect them against humidity, hungry insects, etc. In between, there are a thousand different shades of nuance. It's there that I, personally, perceive to be the greatest amount of necessary work—and I hope that it will be possible to tackle these none-too-attractive things in a more thorough manner. It won't make you famous...

Just (laughing): ...but it will end up making you pretty unpopular along the way.

Mr. Just, in closing: What pops into your head when you hear the name Dietrich Schüller?

Just: I think of a very dedicated person who's eager to be of help and who's been the motor behind this Advisory Panel as well as the entire programme here in Austria for several decades.

And I think it's quite safe to say that you've created some huge boots for us all to fill, in which we're now attempting to take some baby steps.

Schüller: I'm just an emotional person who doesn't like holding his tongue. And it appears as if that combination hasn't been entirely unsuccessful over my years of dealing with these topics.

Just: It's speaking up that's crucial here, in fact. We can't very well champion our concerns—safeguarding cultural property, safeguarding documents—if we don't speak about them. Dietrich Schüller has done a great job of that his entire life long: he's talked lots about it and achieved quite a bit by doing so. And we

Like when I think of how one can now do genealogical research at the computer in the comfort of one's own home [...] that's a perfect example of how the protection of cultural property and digitisation have had an impact that people notice right away.

should continue doing that, too. Austria has been a pioneer in a number of areas. Like when I think of how one can now do genealogical research at the computer in the comfort of one's own home by looking through all those church registers on the Internet ... that's a perfect example of how the protection of cultural property and digitisation have had an impact that people notice right away. It's all well and good if I can view the Golden Bull online, but being able to search for my own relatives connects me with the topic in an entirely different way.

Dr. Schüller: What are your wishes for this programme and for the Advisory Panel?

I'm happy about one thing above all: we've gone through a process of rejuvenating and diversifying our membership, including in terms of topography. I'm very optimistic that this will help drive the programme forward with even more vigour and also help us raise its visibility. It's really important that the members themselves be actively involved in the goings-on, as opposed to what's been the case more recently, where we've had far more "wise old sages". While it can make a lot of sense to have such people on board, they can't be the driving force. And in this respect, there's not a doubt in my mind that under Thomas Just and the now-rejuvenated Advisory Panel, we'll be seeing a new dynamic that really can be put to work to acquire the means necessary for pursuing our mission.

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© Just

DIETRICH SCHÜLLER studied technical physics at the Technische Hochschule in Vienna (today's TU Wien) from 1957 to 1959 and then switched subjects to pursue ethnology and comparative musicology at the University of Vienna, where he earned his PhD in 1970. From 1972 to 2008, he served as Director of the Phonogrammarchiv at the Austrian Academy of Sciences. He also was and still is a member of numerous national and international bodies, and he has authored approximately 200 publications focusing on sound recordings as sources in research, on phonographic field research, and on the storage, conservation, and restoration of audiovisual documents. He has also pursued broad-based teaching, research, and consulting activities in the aforementioned fields and beyond.

THOMAS JUST studied history in Vienna and is a member of the Institute of Austrian Historical Research. In 2001, he was hired by the Austrian State Archives after having worked for the Municipal and Provincial Archives of Vienna, for the City of Vienna's urban archaeology unit Stadtarchäologie Wien, and for Austria's national broadcaster ORF. Since 2009, he has headed the Austrian State Archives' "Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv" department as its director.

¹ On this, see also the contribution by Ambassador Claudia Reinprecht in the 2020 ÖUK Annual Report, accessible at www.unesco.at.

MEDIA AND PRESS FREEDOM

UNESCO is the most important UN organisation with a mandate to protect the freedom of expression. In this context, press freedom and the safety of journalists are just as central as is gender equality in the media landscape. Furthermore, UNESCO runs initiatives that address media- and information-related skills as well as train journalists, and it also supports specific media projects through the International Programme for the Development of Communication (IPDC). In this way, the organisation contributes to the development of inclusive knowledge societies characterised by access to information and (digital) technologies for all people. To this end, a significant role is also played by the ethical development and use of those new technologies to whose influence societies are increasingly subject. Algorithms, for example, can limit freedom of opinion and ease the spread of misinformation and disinformation. Such misleading or false information represents a not insignificant danger to democratic processes, and it also undermines social solidarity. A free, independent, and pluralistic media landscape in print, broadcast, and digital media can counteract this and contribute to peace, sustainability, the fight against poverty, and human rights.

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[...] a significant role is also played by the ethical development and use of those new technologies to whose influence societies are increasingly subject.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Press freedom is relevant above all to aspects of **SDG 16**: Substantially reduce corruption and bribery in all their forms / Develop effective, accountable, and transparent institutions at all levels / Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements.

Safety of Journalists

Contributing to the safety of journalists is a core element of UNESCO's work in the area of press freedom. On average and worldwide, every day sees one journalist killed in connection with practicing their profession. However, kidnappings, harassment, intimidation, and illegal and arbitrary imprisonment likewise number among the serious problems that this occupational group faces on a regular basis all over the world. In this regard, it is especially conspicuous that crimes committed against journalists frequently go unpunished. UNESCO contributes to making this situation visible in that the currently serving director-general has publicly condemned every single murder of a journalist since 1997. Furthermore, the period since 2008 has seen a report on the safety of journalists published every two years for consideration by the Intergovernmental Council of the Programme for the Development of Communication (IPDC).

UNESCO / Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom Prize

This prize, which is worth USD 25,000, honours exceptional contributions to the defence, upholding, and expansion of press freedom. It is named for the Colombian journalist Guillermo Cano Isaza, who was murdered outside the headquarters of his newspaper *El Espectador* in 1986. The prize is sponsored by the Guillermo Cano Isaza Foundation (Colombia), the Helsingin Sanomat Foundation (Finland), and the Namibia Media Trust.

In 2021, in accordance with the recommendation of an international jury of experts, the UNESCO / Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom Prize was awarded to the Philippine investigative journalist and media manager Maria Ressa. This prize hence goes to a journalist from a region that is especially severely affected by violence against journalists: according to UNESCO's monitoring, 112 journalists have been murdered in the Philippines since 1993.

The many years of Maria Ressa's career have included work as the lead investigative reporter for CNN in the Asian region, and she has also led the News and Current Affairs Division of the Philippine television and online network ABS-CBN. She has additionally involved herself in numerous international initiatives aimed at safeguarding press freedom. Recent years have seen her become a target of online attacks as well as legal persecution, especially in connection with her activities as CEO and editor-in-chief of the Philippine online news portal Rappler. Ressa and her business

partners have been accused of tax evasion as well as omissions from tax filings, accusations that they have always denied and that may have been made in retaliation to a critical report on a Philippine businessman. At the same time, she became the target of a hate campaign that culminated in her receipt of an average of over 90 hate messages per hour via Facebook.

Ressa has already received numerous awards in the past, including the Golden Pen of Freedom Award of the World Association of Newspapers and News Publishers (2018), the Gwen Ifill Press Freedom Award of the Committee to Protect Journalists (also 2018), and the Tucholsky Prize of the Swedish branch of PEN International (2020). 2021 also saw her awarded the Nobel Peace Prize together with the Russian journalist Dmitry Muratov.

Maria Ressa 2015

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APPENDIX

THE AUSTRIAN COMMISSION FOR UNESCO

Under Section 2 of its statutes, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO serves as a National Commission pursuant to Article VII of the Charter of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO). Its activities are of a non-profit nature.

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Advisory Panel on Cultural Diversity

Working Group on Cultural Diversity

Advisory Panel on Intangible Cultural Heritage

Advisory Panel on Information Preservation/Memory of the World National Committee

AUSTRIAN WORLD HERITAGE SITES

1996 **Historic Centre of the City of Salzburg**

1996 **Palace and Gardens of Schönbrunn**

1997 **Hallstatt-Dachstein/Salzkammergut Cultural Landscape**

1998 **Semmering Railway**

1999 **City of Graz – Historic Centre and**

2010 **Schloss Eggenberg**

2000 **Wachau Cultural Landscape**

2001 **Historic Centre of Vienna**

2001 **Fertő/Neusiedler See Cultural Landscape** (jointly with Hungary)

2011 **Prehistoric Pile Dwellings Around the Alps** (jointly with France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Switzerland)

2017 **Ancient and Primeval Beech Forests of the Carpathians and Other Regions of Europe** (jointly with Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Italy, Austria, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and Ukraine), with Austrian properties in the Dürrenstein Wilderness Area (Lower Austria) as well as in the Kalkalpen National Park (Upper Austria).

2021 **Great Spa Towns of Europe** (jointly with Belgium, Germany, France, Great Britain, Italy and Czech Republic)

2021 **Frontiers of the Roman Empire – Danube Limes (Western Segment)** (jointly with Germany and Slovakia)

AUSTRIAN BIOSPHERE RESERVES

2000 **Großes Walsertal**, Vorarlberg

2005 **Vienna Woods**, Vienna / Lower Austria

2012 **Lungau/Nockberge**, Salzburg/Carinthia

2019 **Lower Mura Valley**, Styria, The world's first 5-country biosphere reserve (Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Hungary, and Serbia)

AUSTRIAN UNESCO GEOPARKS

2004 **Styrian Eisenwurzen**

2013 **Karawanken/Karavanke**
(together with Slovenia)

2014 **Ore of the Alps**

INSCRIPTIONS ON THE REPRESENTATIVE LIST OF THE INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE OF HUMANITY

2012 **Falconry**, a Living Human Heritage
(multinational nomination by altogether 18 states)

2012 **Schemenlaufen, the carnival of Imst**

2015 **Classical Horsemanship and the High School of the Spanish Riding School Vienna**

2017 **Resist Block Printing and Indigo Dyeing in Europe** (multinational nomination with Germany, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Hungary)

2017 **Avalanche Risk Management**
(bilateral nomination with Switzerland)

2019 **Transhumance – the Seasonal Droving of Livestock along Migratory Routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps** (multinational nomination with Greece and Italy)

INSCRIPTIONS ON THE INTERNATIONAL ICH REGISTER OF GOOD SAFEGUARDING PRACTICES

2016 **Regional Centres for Craftsmanship: a strategy for safeguarding the cultural heritage of traditional handicraft**

2020 **Craft techniques and customary practices of cathedral workshops, or Bauhütten, in Europe, know-how, transmission, development of knowledge and innovation**

AUSTRIAN UNESCO “CREATIVE CITIES”

2011 **Graz – “City of Design”**

2014 **Linz – “City of Media Arts”**

AUSTRIAN ENTRIES IN THE MEMORY OF THE WORLD REGISTER

1997 **Vienna Dioscurides**
Austrian National Library

1997 **Final Document of the Congress of Vienna 1815**, Austrian State Archives

1999 **Historical Collections (1899–1950)**
Audiovisual Research Archives of the Austrian Academy of Sciences

2001 **Papyrus Erzherzog Rainer**
Austrian National Library

2001 **Schubert Collection**
Vienna City Library

2003 **Atlas Blaeu-Van der Hem**
Austrian National Library

2005 **Brahms Collection**
Vienna Society of Friends of Music

2005 **Collection of Gothic Architectural Drawings**, Academy of Fine Arts, Vienna

2005 **Bibliotheca Corviniana**
Austrian National Library (jointly with Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, and Italy)

2007 **Tabula Peutingeriana**
Austrian National Library

2011 **Arnold Schönberg Estate**
Arnold Schönberg Center

2011 **Mainz Psalter**
Austrian National Library

2013 **The “Golden Bull”**, Austrian State Archives (jointly with Germany)

2017 **Philosophical Nachlass of Ludwig Wittgenstein** (jointly with Great Britain, Canada, and the Netherlands)

2017 **Historical Documents on the Semmering Railway**
Vienna Technical Museum

AUSTRIAN UNESCO CHAIRS

UNESCO Chair in Intercultural and Inter-religious Dialogue for South-East Europe, established in 2007, University of Graz, Faculty of Catholic Theology | Occupant: Pablo ARGÁRATE

UNESCO Chair for Peace Studies, established in 2008, University of Innsbruck | Occupant: Wolfgang DIETRICH

UNESCO Chair in Cultural Heritage and Tourism, established in 2011, University of Salzburg, Department of Communication Science, Transcultural Communication | Occupant: Kurt LUGER

UNESCO Chair on Integrated River Research and Management, established in 2014, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences | Occupant: Helmut HABERSACK

UNESCO Chair in Human Rights and Security, established in 2015, University of Graz | Occupant: Gerd OBERLEITNER

UNESCO Chair for Bioethics, established 2015, Medical University of Vienna | Occupant: Christiane DRUML

UNESCO Chair on Conservation and Preservation of Tangible Cultural Heritage, established in 2019, University of Applied Arts Vienna | Occupant: Gabriela KRIST

UNESCO Chair for Global Citizenship Education – Culture of Diversity and Peace, established in 2020, University of Klagenfurt | Occupant: Hans Karl PETERLINI

UNESCO Chair for Sustainable Management of Conservation Areas, established in 2020, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences Klagenfurt | Michael JUNGMEIER

UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Future Design, established in 2021, University of Art and Design Linz, Occupant: Michael SHAMIYEH

UNESCO CATEGORY II CENTRES

Category II Centre for the Promotion of Human Rights at the Local and Regional Levels as part of the European Training and Research Centre for Human Rights and Democracy (ETC-Graz) | Head: Klaus STARL

AUSTRIAN UNESCO ASSOCIATED SCHOOLS

As of 2021, Austria has 96 UNESCO Associated Schools

IMPRINT

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Austrian Commission for UNESCO

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Tombstone of T. Calidius Severus,

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This important first-century find bears witness to ancient Roman life at the Danube Limes. The western segment of the Danube Limes was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List as a transnational site in 2021.

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We likewise thank all of our cooperating partners and supporters.

**Austrian Commission
for UNESCO**

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Austrian Commission for UNESCO

Annual Report 2021

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Österreichische
UNESCO-Kommission
Austrian Commission
for UNESCO

FOREWORD

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Patrizia Jankovic, Secretary-General

2021, much like the year that preceded it, was still characterised quite strongly by pandemic-related restrictions: it remained the case that more than a few events could “only” be held in digital formats, while working in “remote mode” finally became normal. Even so, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO (ÖUK) can look back upon a successful year. The contributions on the following pages serve to highlight our wide array of activities:

The presentation of the new Global Education Monitoring Report (entitled “Non-State Actors in Education: Who Chooses? Who Loses?”) traced an arc between the Global South and the Global North and was once again the object of international attention. The UNESCO Associated Schools Conference offered a variety-packed programme whose theme was “Futures of Education”, and the ÖUK’s new initiative to offer schools various workshops on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals generated a great deal of resonance among school students and teachers alike.

This year once again saw numerous outstanding contributors to basic research awarded UNESCO-L’ORÉAL Austria Fellowships as part of the “For Women in Science” initiative. Our science activities also featured the establishment of the “UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Futures Design” at the University of Art and Design Linz.

In the realm of culture, Austria’s National Point of Contact to the *UNESCO Convention on the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* opened up a new thematic emphasis on the issue of preferential treatment in (post-)migrant Austria as well as antidiscrimination in (international) cultural policy with the event series “Forum Fair Culture”.

18 April 2021 witnessed the observance of Austria’s first World Heritage Day, a day of action involving all Austrian World Heritage sites that calls attention to the outstanding universal value of World Heritage in Austria and worldwide. On the international level, the past year also witnessed successful inscription of “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (including the town of Baden, just south of Vienna) as well as the positive conclusion of the multi-year nomination process for “Frontiers of the Roman Empire – The Danube Limes (Western Segment)”. In terms of intangible cultural heritage, the focus in 2021 was on traditional irrigation methods: starting from the National Inventory element “Meadow Irrigation in Tyrol”, Austria coordinated the preparatory work for a multinational nomination to the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

These successes have only been possible thanks to good cooperation on the part of all those involved—and I would like to extend special thanks to all ÖUK employees and to the ÖUK Executive Committee and Board for their great dedication and tireless efforts as well as to those federal ministries that have long provided us with support.

Patrizia Jankovic

Sabine Haag, President

Today UNESCO is more important than ever as a forum of global intellectual cooperation, with the COVID-19 pandemic having played no small role in making clear that the challenges of our present era can only be overcome cooperatively and multilaterally.

Part of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO's work is to implement the goals of UNESCO in Austria. Our other focus is on working together with the competent Austrian ministries in order to anchor Austrian positions, concerns, and projects within UNESCO.

Every two years, representatives of UNESCO's member states gather as the General Conference, UNESCO's supreme decision-making and monitoring body. November 2021 once again saw Austria represented in Paris by the competent federal ministries and the Austrian Commission for UNESCO along with experts from the arts, culture, education, and science. We are also especially proud that this 41st General Conference of UNESCO saw Austria elected to be part of UNESCO's Executive Board, the institution's most important executive body, for the fourth time.

Austria is represented not only there but also on numerous further UNESCO committees and boards, such as currently on the International Coordinating Council of UNESCO's "Man and the Biosphere" (MAB) Programme, the Intergovernmental Council of the "Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme" (IHP), and the Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions—to name just a few. Common to the ÖUK's involvement with all of the abovementioned groups is the significant contribution it makes to the

coordination of Austrian expertise in the interest of more solidly undergirding the substantive discussion. In turn, the participation of Austrian experts in international programmes ends up internationalising the associated Austrian debates more or less as a matter of course. An example of such cross-pollination in this Annual Report would be the interview with Günter Köck regarding his many years of work for the MAB Programme.

Our collaboration with Dr. Köck and the Austrian Academy of Sciences is just one of numerous instances in which the ÖUK relies on expert knowledge from the sciences, the arts, and the cultural and educational realms in its activities. Highly regarded experts currently work as part of six advisory committees that advise and inform the ÖUK as well as assess the implementation of UNESCO's goals in Austria. I would like to extend my thanks to them here for their always-beneficial collaboration and our numerous fruitful discussions!

We would also like to most cordially thank all of our partner organizations and sponsors, especially those from the competent federal ministries, for their support and partnership!

Sabine Haag

Open Science & Artificial Intelligence – Two Forward-Looking UNESCO Recommendations

At its 41st meeting in November 2021, the General Conference of UNESCO adopted a recommendation on the topic of open science as well as a widely-noted recommendation regarding the ethics of artificial intelligence (AI). Dr. Stefan Hanslik, head of the Technical Sciences Department at Austria's Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, points out the significance of both UNESCO instruments in terms of the development of corresponding measures and policies in Austria and introduces Austria's current position.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science – A Further Step in the Right Direction

The vision of open science is to make scientific processes more open and effective and to harness scientific excellence as well as innovative and applied research in order to take on current and future societal, socioeconomic, and ecological challenges. Open science is an important tool in efforts to make significant advances toward overcoming present and future societal challenges. With the preparation of a standard-setting international instrument in the form of a “Recommendation on Open Science”, UNESCO took a crucial step in the interest of guiding and governing the multi-layered global open science movement for the benefit of all. Together with the objectives of the EU in the field of research and data policy, this recommendation formed the basis for the development of an Austrian policy (in the sense of a common orientation) on Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Developing open, transparent, and inclusive science and promoting the fair handling of research processes and their results is an Austrian priority. Open Science was hence also included in the Federal Government's strategy for research, technology, and innovation (RTI Strategy 2030) in the form of a clear commitment to “Horizon Europe” and Austria's active participation in the European Research Area (ERA).

As a result, intense effort was devoted to the development of an Austrian policy on Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud. Alongside the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF), this

process also involved the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (BMK) and the Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs (BMDW). These efforts revealed

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the great relevance of proactive participation in the process of implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), a World Wide Web for FAIR research data and services intended to keep research data as free, accessible, and open as possible.

In a timely manner and corresponding to the UNESCO activities, February 2022 saw the “Open Science Policy Austria” adopted on the occasion of a joint Ministerial Council presentation by the three Austrian ministries with primary competency regarding the Open Science movement: the BMBWF, BMDW, and BMK. By implementing UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science, Austria is actively promoting the development of an open, transparent, and inclusive environment for science and hence also the fair handling of research processes and their results on the national level.

Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence – An Important Prerequisite for Dealing with AI

In light of how rapid technological developments such as the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) are already having deep-reaching effects on our societies, this UNESCO recommendation represents an important prerequisite for dealing with artificial intelligence in a global context. There can be no doubt that the question of which skills and parameters the human world needs to develop in order to continue evolving peacefully in an increasingly automated world will be growing enormously in its significance.

In knowledge societies, artificial intelligence can be employed in areas such as teaching and learning in order to render these processes interactive and personalized, thus helping to enhance the quality of teaching and learning as well as the variety of teaching methods. AI must and will be part of activities such as education and further training in the STEM field as well as in teacher

training in order to ensure that state-of-the-art education is of high quality.

Artificial intelligence can be of great benefit to marginalized groups such as children, youth, and adults living in rural areas or crisis regions as well as people with disabilities insofar as they have access to new technologies. Granting such access and taking the necessary steps to eradicate the digital gap are significant prerequisites.

By implementing UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science, Austria is actively promoting the development of an open, transparent, and inclusive environment for science and hence also the fair handling of research processes and their results on the national level.

As AI technologies are not neutral, and as AI is currently blind to the consequences of its application, Austria emphatically supports UNESCO’s commitment to artificial intelligence and especially its focus on the ethical dimension thereof. “Responsible Science” as a concept for bringing together scientific excellence and social relevance can contribute significantly to raising awareness of the potential challenges and risks entailed by this new, emerging technology.

Human analysis as well as strict control of AI-based decisions must be ensured: AI cannot and must not replace natural intelligence; instead, it must serve humankind in specific domains and with expertise as well as human oversight. For this and other reasons, we need to more strongly involve people in the process of developing AI and the framework surrounding it irrespective of gender, descent, worldview, age, sexual orientation, or special needs.

Only an approach based on human rights, ethics, and scientific integrity can

provide a framework that will enable both the successful use of artificial intelligence and the protection and consideration of each individual’s personal rights and needs as well as the assurance of fairness and transparency in all societal areas.

In sum, Austria considers it to be of great importance to work on a national AI Framework as well as to agree on a standard-setting international instrument concerning the ethics of artificial intelligence such as the one adopted by UNESCO.

© Hanslik

STEFAN HANSLIK holds a doctorate in biology and genetics. He heads the Technical Sciences Department at the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research. He represents Austria in numerous international bodies including various HORIZON Europe programme committees, the OECD’s Working Group on Biotechnology, and the Council of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility.

EDUCATION

With its adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the international community of states emphasised the central role to be played by education in implementing the Agenda's 17 Sustainable Development Goals. In this respect, it is key to anchor sustainability in educational systems worldwide and to drive forward the 17 SDGs' implementation.

Painting & Printmaking

759 – 769

Photography & Music

779 – 781

UNESCO'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES

Towards a Fairer World for All

To shape peaceful, just, and sustainable futures, education itself needs to be transformed.

This is the demand asserted by the Global Report of the *International Commission on the Futures of Education*, entitled “Reimagining Our Futures Together: A New Social Contract for Education”. This report asks what role education can play in shaping our world and our common future with an eye to 2050 and beyond. The presented recommendations are the outcome of a two-year global process of engagement and collaboration. The report is devoted to topics such as reshaping spaces of learning, decolonialising curricula, and the significance of social and emotional learning, and it addresses real and growing fears of climate change, of crises such as COVID-19, of fake news and the digital divide. Education—the way in which we organise teaching and learning throughout our lives—plays a fundamental role in shaping human societies. It connects us with the world and with one another, shows us new possibilities, and reinforces our abilities to engage in dialogue and take action.

Education Agenda – No One Shall Be Left Behind

While the expansion of educational systems has opened up new opportunities for numerous people, the quality of the education available to many is lacking. The way in which education is organised worldwide is currently inadequate to the mission of ensuring fair and peaceful societies, a healthy planet, and shared progress that benefits all. In actual fact, several difficulties in this respect can be attributed to the way in which education is provided. The enormous transformative potentials of digital technologies need to be used, while more active civic involvement and the growing sphere of activism that opposes discrimination and injustice need to be integrated into educational activities in order to strengthen education as a public concern and an element of the common good.

Education and the SDGs

The Global Education 2030 Agenda is derived from the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which was adopted by the United Nations in September 2015. Education plays a central role in the successful implementation of all 17 Sustainable Development Goals, also having a Sustainable Development Goal of its own that aims to “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030. And UNESCO, as the only specialized agency of the United Nations with a mandate to cover all aspects of education, is leading the way in implementing this goal's various targets.

SGD 4 – Quality Education

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030.

4.1. By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable, and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes.

4.2. By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care-, and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education.

4.3. By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university.

4.4. By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurship.

4.5. By 2030, eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, and children in vulnerable situations.

4.6. By 2030, ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults achieve literacy and numeracy.

4.7. By 2030, ensure all learners acquire knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

The Austrian Commission for UNESCO assumes support and advisory functions that serve the various protagonists working to implement international educational programmes in Austria. In doing so, it orients itself toward the various current working emphases of UNESCO as a whole and in particular toward the Global Education 2030 Agenda.

• Presentation of UNESCO's 2021/22 Global Education Monitoring Report

Ever since the United Nations' adoption of the 17 Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report (GEM Report) has been shedding light on worldwide progress as well as the development of education policy in the individual countries in the interest of achieving SDG 4. This report serves to monitor, document, and analyse implementation of the Education 2030 agenda as well as to formulate recommendations that help better facilitate its implementation. The 2021/22 report is entitled "Non-State Actors in Education: Who Chooses? Who Loses?" and was published in December 2021. In this edition, UNESCO demands better oversight of private educational institutions in order to reduce inequalities and calls upon member states to set quality standards for state and non-state institutions: to reinforce efforts toward free primary and secondary schooling, to bring together stakeholders from diverse areas of the educational field, to strengthen the capacity of the state to monitor compliance with and enforce regulations, and above all, to protect education from narrow vested interests.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Education and the SDGs Education sits at the core of the 2030 Agenda. It plays a central role in the successful implementation of all 17 Sustainable Development Goals, and it also has its own goal, SDG 4, which aims to: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030.”

- **Advisory Panel on Global Citizenship Education, Global Learning, Education for Sustainable Development**

The Advisory Panel on Transformative Education/ Global Citizenship Education, which was established at the Austrian Commission for UNESCO in March 2017, devotes itself to monitoring and accompanying the national implementation of SDG 4, in particular SDG 4.7. In 2021, this body added Dr. Gerhard Bisovsky, at the time Secretary-General of the Association of Austrian Adult Education Centres, as its newest member.

- **The Youth Representative of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO**

In the interest of amplifying young people’s voices, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO created the two-year position of “Youth Representative” in 2019. This individual acts as a representative of the ÖUK’s youth-relevant positions in the outside world and works together with the ÖUK Secretariat to realise UNESCO-relevant youth activities. In 2021, Maria Blomenhofer took over this honorary post, which she will hold until mid-2023.

- **“Turning Point”: Education for the SDGs**

“Turning Point: Youth for Sustainable Development” is an event series of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO’s Youth Representative. It brings together young people in order to discuss urgent problems of our time.

25th and 26th January witnessed the online workshop “Your Rights – Your World!” It was organised in combination with the project “Know Your Rights” and offered around 140 young people between the ages of 14 and 25 the opportunity to engage in exchange on the topics of human rights and sustainability, learning more about the complex ways in which human rights and protecting the climate and the environment interrelate.

Is privatisation a solution or a symptom?

The Global Education Monitoring Report 2021/22, entitled "Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses?" addresses the question of the impact of (increasing) privatization in the education sector.

To bridge the gap between the Global North and the Global South with regard to non-state actors in education, Dr. Maria Ron-Balsera, TaxEd Alliance Coordinator, uses a study conducted in Ghana, Kenya and Uganda to explain the situation and challenges of those countries.

In 2015 governments around the world committed to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all', with the leading principle of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development to 'leave no one behind'. The effects of COVID-19 threaten to derail the progress made in these two decades, resulting in hundreds of million people falling back into extreme poverty, and a growing backlog in the implementation of the 2030 agenda. Due to the way the COVID-19 pandemic was managed, on top of years of austerity policies, education systems face a devastating crisis in public financing, and uncertainty over the quality of learning available when children return to education.

Many voices are pushing for stronger partnerships with private actors. However, the negative effects on equity and other areas of the increasing privatisation of education is becoming a central concern for education, development and human rights scholars and practitioners. The GEM Report for 2021/22 rallying call: Who chooses, who loses? Is very telling of the impact of the increasing privatisation of education, with growing evidence in terms of exclusion, segmentation, segregation, inequality of opportunities, stigmatisation of public education, diversion of essential funds, lowering teaching standards, narrowing

of the curriculum, etc. which the GEMR partly analyses.

The Abidjan principles on the human rights obligations of States to provide public education and to regulate private involvement in education were adopted in 2019. They provide rigorous guidelines to assess the role of private providers and consolidate international legislation into a single document, underlining governments' responsi-

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lities to respect, protect and fulfil the right to education. Principle 25 refers to the state's obligation to prevent or redress direct or indirect discrimination in or through education, for example, including systemic disparities in educational opportunities or outcomes, highlighting socio-economic disadvantage. Principle 48 affirms that private actors can supplement, but not supplant or replace state provision of education, and that they cannot create any adverse

systematic impact, such as creating or entrenching educational disparities.

Our study in Ghana, Kenya and Uganda and the collaborative research in Malawi, Mozambique, Nigeria and Tanzania used these Principles to understand the impact of privatisation on the right to education. They concluded:

- These states are not meeting their obligations to provide free and quality education and to adequately regulate private providers of education
- Private providers are supplanting rather than supplementing public education
- The financial allocations for public education provision are inadequate
- Privatisation is creating and exacerbating social inequalities
- Ideological arguments are used to support the agenda, rather than evidence, which remain inconclusive about the advantages of private providers

Therefore, privatisation is not a solution, but rather a symptom of the lack of availability and quality of public education. This is partly the result of the chronic inadequate financing of education. As our research shows, many countries fail to allocate their maximum available resources and often taken retrogressive steps, lowering the education budget without justification. These countries have staggering losses

¹ Funded by GPE-EOL, the TaxEd Alliance connects Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) stakeholders working on tax issues with those working on education to create an effective transnational CSO response. Bringing together ActionAid, Education International, the Global Campaign for Education, Tax Justice Network, the Global Alliance for Tax Justice and its regional networks Tax And Fiscal Justice Asia and Tax Justice Network - Africa.

Financing the future: Education financing and tax incentives

Country	Education as share of national budget	Tax/GDP	Estimated annual revenue foregone from tax incentives	20 percent of this sum would amount to	This money could pay for
Nepal	14.1% (2018)	18% (13% indirect, 5% direct taxes) (2017)	\$1.68 billion	\$336.6 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for all the out-of-school places for children left out of primary and lower-secondary school • The basic salary for 5,000 primary and 5,000 lower secondary teachers • Free school meals for 600,000 children • Expanding the annual scholarship for vulnerable groups to an additional 1 million young people • The estimated annual financing gap (US\$81 million in 2021) in the Nepalese School Sector Development Plan (SSDP) mid-term review
Senegal	22.1% (2020)	16.8% (11,7% indirect, 5,1% direct taxes) (2020)	\$1.19 billion	\$238 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for all around half (350,000) of the primary aged children currently out-of-school • 10,000 teachers (of the 35,000 gap required to be filled by 2030) • Double the number of children who receive a free school meal annually
Zambia	12.4% (2020)	16.7% (9% indirect, 7,7% direct taxes) (2019)	\$406 million	\$81.2 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School places for 350,000 children in primary school (around 2/3rds of the current out-of-school primary school children) • 4,000 extra primary school teachers (the estimated current primary school teacher gap) • Free school meals for 1/2 million children annually
Ghana	18.6% (2018)	12% (5,8% indirect, 6,5% direct taxes) (2019)	\$1.2 billion	\$240 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A place in a primary school for the 319,000 out-of-school children • An extra 10,000 qualified teachers • Free school meals for 1 year for 557,892 children
Uganda	11.2% (2018)	11.5% (7,4% indirect, 1,4% direct taxes) (2019)	\$272 million	\$54.4 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A place in a primary school for the 477,000 out-of-school children • An extra 20,000 qualified teachers • Free school meals for 1 year for 412,047 children

to tax incentives that can be seen in the table below.

In 2016 the Education Commission calculated that 97% of the estimated financing gap in education should be coming from domestic sources, and 3% from international assistance. Unfortunately, despite the small proportion, international assistance continues to dominate the debate and not enough attention is paid to how to raise the majority of the funds in a sustainable way that encourages sustainable

economic growth, strengthens governance, protects the environment and complies with human rights. Progressive tax reform can address all of these and should be at the centre of plans to finance the SDGs.

The Incheon Declaration recommended a minimum allocation of 15–20% of the government budget to education, with low-income countries requiring a minimum of 20%. For too many years the education community has been fixated on the share of the

budget competing with other priorities such as health, without understanding the dynamics that underpin the size of the government budget. To adequately finance education to achieve SDG4 and for countries to fulfil their obligations towards the right to education, they need to increase the **4Ss**:

1. **Share** of the budget to a minimum of 20%;
2. the **Size** of the budget by increasing the tax/GDP through progressive tax reform;

3. the **Sensitivity** of the budget, by ensuring that the budget allocation follows an equity criteria;
4. and the **Scrutiny** of the budget, by ensuring transparency, participation, efficiency, and accountability.

Without getting technical, the most democratic and sustainable way to increase the size of the budget is through progressive taxation. Progressive taxation or tax justice, promotes the **4Rs**: **Revenue**, generating sustainable funds for public services such as education; **Redistribution**, to curb vertical and horizontal inequalities (those between individuals and those between groups); **Repricing**, to limit public “bads” such as tobacco consumption or carbon emissions; **Representation**, to build healthier democratic processes, recognising that higher reliance of government spending

If we are serious about achieving SDG4, we need to focus on sustainable domestic resource mobilisation, both increasing revenue and reducing revenue loss through illicit financial flows and corruption.

on tax revenues is strongly linked to higher quality of governance and political representation.

The table above illustrates the current education financing linking it to the revenue lost to tax incentives in five countries. These countries vary in terms of the share of the government budget allocated to education, with Senegal going over the recommended 20% (although data from other sources also has Ghana surpassing the 20% benchmark), with Nepal, and particularly Zambia and Uganda chronically allocating shamefully low shares to education. Although advocacy to ensure that countries reach or maintain an adequate share of the budget is vital, if we are serious about education financing,

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we need to look at the size of the government budget, which is intimately linked to the tax to GDP ratio. The table shows that none of the five countries reach even the low bar of a 20% tax to GDP ratio (contrasting with the 41.3% average in the European Union, accounting for 89.3 % of total government revenue in 2020). Not only these 5 countries have low tax to GDP ratios, particularly Uganda or Ghana, but also, many of them show an overdependence on indirect taxation (such as VAT or sales taxes) which tend to be more regressive, as is the case for Nepal and Senegal. Tax incentives have been used to attract foreign direct investment, although there is much research showing that more often than not, they are unnecessary, and the IMF now consider most forms of tax incentive to be harmful to the economy. The table provides estimates in terms of the revenue losses to these harmful tax incentives and what 20% of that amount could have provided for in terms of education inputs. The TaxEd Alliance partners in these countries are engaging with their respective governments to address these issues, proposing progressive tax reforms to fill the education financing gap.

When government revenue falls short there are increases in the proportion of education spending borne by households, which now reaches 38% in low-income countries (EFW, 2021). This is a profoundly regressive way of financing education, which exacerbates gender and other social inequalities, widening vertical and horizontal inequalities, within and between countries. Considering that the abolition

of school fees in the early 2000s was pivotal to gains in school enrolment and achieving gender parity in many countries, the growing discourse on ‘affordability’ leading to more costs passed on to families, is deeply problematic and can undo the progress we have achieved in the last couple of decades. If we are serious about achieving SDG4, we need to focus on sustainable domestic resource mobilisation, both increasing revenue and reducing revenue loss through illicit financial flows and corruption. Countries must fulfil their obligations to provide free public education of the highest attainable quality by increasing the size, share, sensitivity, and scrutiny of the budget, to give the necessary resources to public schools, and to adequately regulate private providers.

© Ron-Balsera

MARIA RON-BALSERA finished her PhD in Education from Bielefeld University (Germany) in 2014, with a Marie Curie Fellowship. She also holds an MSc in Human Rights from the London School of Economics and an LLM in Human Rights from Universidad Carlos III in Madrid. She has done research at the Institute of Education (UCL) as a visiting research associate, and at UC Berkeley through a research exchange program. She is currently working as the Tax and Education Alliance Coordinator, a transnational partnership that brings together ActionAid, Education International, Global Campaign for Education, Tax Justice Network and the Global Alliance for Tax Justice.

UNESCO ASSOCIATED SCHOOLS IN AUSTRIA

“Learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, learning to live together”

UNESCO Associated Schools comprise a world-wide network of over 11,500 educational institutions in 182 countries. The 96 Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools are part of this international network and contribute to the preservation of peace and security by acquainting young people with the concepts of understanding, tolerance, and friendship between all nations and peoples at the earliest possible age.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **UNESCO Associated Schools / 2021 Conference**

Since 1997, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO has been organising annual networking meetings for all of the Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools' contact persons.

These annual conferences make a significant contribution to further training, faculty networking, and the exchange of ideas. In workshops and lectures, on field trips, and via project-based exchange, the UNESCO Associated Schools' contact persons can acquire new knowledge and skills as well as encourage each other to take on challenging in-class projects specially designed for children and adolescents. 13th and 14th October 2021 saw the annual conference once again held virtually. The theme of this year's conference was “Futures of Education”, in keeping with the projection report: “Reimagining Our Futures Together: A New Social Contract for Education”. The focuses of this conference were of a substantive and structural nature: in terms of substance, there were workshops on intangible cultural heritage and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Structurally, deep insights were provided into the educational work of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and its entire range of activities including an outlook featuring future projects for Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools. Finally, the “Market of Possibilities”

offered teachers an opportunity to engage in virtual exchange. This event was participated in by representatives of 75 schools.

- **The Magazine FORUM**

The annually published periodical FORUM shows the wide variety of approaches and the great creativity and dedication brought to bear by Austria's UNESCO Associated Schools in their implementation of UNESCO's guiding principles and their respective annual themes. The current issue of FORUM (vol. 33/2021) is entitled Futures of Education.

Contributions from 50 UNESCO Associated Schools document the diversity of the topics with which their students dealt practically in class during the 2020/2021 academic year. The fundamental emphasis lay on the SDGs, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, meaning that the schools went in depth on biodiversity, sustainability, and climate change but also dealt to an increased degree with topics such as civil courage, integration, peace education, and human rights due to the special conditions of virtual and hybrid teaching associated with the ongoing pandemic. For example, there were several online remedial tutoring projects by and for students as well as donation drives and assistance projects for people living in precarious circumstances. And fully in keeping with the “Futures of Education” theme of the abovementioned projection report published by UNESCO, there were also participative workshops and projects that gave students the opportunity to help actively shape their everyday lives at school, the actual rooms and places where they learn, and even individual lessons. A further important theme of the report is that of teaching about the use of digital tools in a way that enables students to acquire the relevant technical skills as well as the critical spirit and distance needed to use them in ways that make sense.

UNESCO-SCHULEN

Founded by UNESCO in **1953**

Over **11,500** educational institutions in **182** countries

Austria has participated since **1957**, with schools of all types in all **9** federal provinces

96 UNESCO associated schools,
20 candidate schools

Guiding principles: learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, learning to live together

Themes: peace and human rights education, global citizenship education, education for sustainable development, cultural education, Sustainable Development Goals

Role of the ÖUK: national coordination of advising, project initiation, informational activities, and cooperation; one three-day conference annually; FORUM magazine, website

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/:

Central informational website with a list

of all Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools, current events, projects, and projects

• Cultural Education

2019 witnessed the Europe-wide initiation of the UNESCO-EU pilot project "Teaching and Learning with Living Heritage" in cooperation with ten UNESCO Associated Schools, including one from Austria. The ÖUK introduced this project at the annual UNESCO Associated Schools Conference, which took place virtually from 13 to 14 October. November 2021 then saw the ÖUK's intangible cultural heritage and education staff organise a networking meeting between the various bearers of intangible cultural heritage and the contact persons of Austria's UNESCO Associated Schools that was enthusiastically received both by the bearers and by the schools' contact persons. This project is being continued in the 2022 calendar year, during which it will be implemented Austria-wide by UNESCO facilitators.

Further information:

www.unesco.at/bildung/unesco-schulen/lehr-und-lernmaterial/immaterielles-kulturerbe

• SDG Workshops

Due to the great success of "Turning Point. Youth for Sustainable Development", the event series by and for young people in Austria, and due to the great demand coming from schools, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO is expanding its offerings of SDG workshops tailored specifically to the country's UNESCO Associated Schools. Austrian UNESCO Associated Schools will have the opportunity to book online workshops given by SDG experts with various thematic emphases. The broad diversity of available content is suitable for integration into various school subjects.

The participating students, aged 14 to 19, can deal in depth with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from various perspectives in order to expand their knowledge while also getting a feel for the SDGs' multifaceted nature and transdisciplinary applicability. These workshops are interactive and encourage students to deal independently with this complex theme.

SCIENCE

Science embodies the cornerstone of modern, enlightened, democratic societies. Scientific research allows us to identify societal developments and challenges as well as to arrive at answers to the questions of our times. Science is a fundamentally international undertaking; no state is capable of advancing research in isolation. At UNESCO, all Member States work together to strengthen scientific research worldwide amidst the tension between scientific freedom and social responsibility. UNESCO promotes global research on the urgent questions of humankind and supports people in putting knowledge to use in order to build just and inclusive societies.

THE UNESCO SCIENCE PROGRAMMES

The UNESCO Science Programmes

UNESCO's science-related thematic focuses include climate change and the preservation of biodiversity, the advancement of knowledge pertaining to the protection of oceans and coasts, and ensuring the availability of drinking water.

Exemplary here are the longstanding UNESCO programmes Man and the Biosphere (MAB), the Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP), and the International Geoscience Programme (IGCP), all three of which are devoted to researching and protecting the living environment of human beings.

In Austria, these programmes are overseen by the MAB and Geo/Hydro Sciences National Committees at the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

• Man and the Biosphere

The UNESCO programme Man and the Biosphere (MAB) develops the scientific and practical fundamentals upon which the natural basis of our existence as well as biodiversity can be preserved for the long term. The objective here is sustainable development of the relationship between humankind and the environment: achieving a balance between the protection of biological diversity, the promotion of economic and social development, and the preservation of our respective cultural values. This programme's World Network of Biosphere Reserves currently encompasses 727 biosphere reserves in 131 countries. In Austria, four biosphere reserves (Wienerwald, Großes Walsertal, Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, and Unteres Murtal) have been established so far.

Austria is also a highly active participant in the MAB Programme's international decision-making bodies and committees. Austria's Dr. Günter Köck of the Austrian Academy of Sciences currently represents the "Europe and North America" region in the MAB Bureau. Köck, as Austria's delegate to the UNESCO-MAB programme's International Coordinating Council, was also elected in the autumn of 2020 to serve a fourth term as vice-chair of this body and hence of the programme.

• IHP (Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme) and IGCP (International Geoscience Programme)

UNESCO's Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP) is the only intergovernmental programme in the UN system devoted to hydrological research and water management as well as capacity-building in this field. This programme's underlying aim is to support an interdisciplinary and integrated approach to dealing with watersheds and aquifer management that also accounts for the social

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MAB – MAN AND THE BIOSPHERE

The first intergovernmental environmental programme devoted to the **relationship between human beings and their environment** and to the sustainable use of natural resources

Global network of UNESCO biosphere reserves—model regions that work to achieve harmony between the protection of nature, the preservation of biological diversity, and regional development.

4 biosphere reserves in Austria: Großes Walsertal, Wienerwald, Salzburger Lungau & Kärntner Nockberge, Unteres Murtal

Implementation in Austria by the **MAB National Committee**

Role of the ÖUK: information platform for the programme, public relations work

Further information on the "Man and the Biosphere Programme":

dimension of water resources and both supports and helps develop international hydrological and limnological research.

The International Geoscience Programme (IGCP), founded in 1973, supports geoscientific cooperative projects with research focuses that are precisely defined by UNESCO. These projects include the UNESCO Global Geoparks, of which Austria can boast three: Styrian Eisenwurzen, Ore of the Alps, and the transnational geopark Karawanken/Karavanke.

- **UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme**

The UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme, established in 1992, provides important impulses that are intended to anchor UNESCO's concerns at institutions of higher learning. It supports such institutions' research and educational activities as well as their further development by forming university networks and promoting transnational cooperation between institutions.

This programme can now boast a worldwide pool of over 700 participating institutions, ten of which are in Austria.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **4 UNESCO-L'ORÉAL Scholarships in Austria**

The World needs Science – Science needs Women

A central aim of UNESCO's science programmes is to strengthen the role of women in science, particularly in the life sciences. The "L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Initiative" is part of these efforts. Every year, the L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Awards Ceremony at UNESCO's headquarters in Paris sees five prizes worth € 100,000 each as well as fifteen "L'Oréal-UNESCO Rising Talents" scholarships awarded to outstanding woman scientists.

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2021's scholarship recipients and congratulatory speakers: Kerstin Rastädter, Sabine Haag, Monika Malik, Martin Netzer, Alice Laciny, Wioletta Rosolowska, Anna Bregler, Helmut Denk (from l. to r.)

This cooperative relationship also extends to the national level: since 2007, L'Oréal Austria—in cooperation with the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the Austrian Academy of Sciences and with support from the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)—has been awarding four annual scholarships worth € 25,000 each to outstanding young women scientists in Austria. They may be applied for by women who pursue research in the natural sciences, mathematics, and/or medicine.

These scholarships aim to recognise, support, and encourage young women by helping to create role models. They additionally serve to make the general public aware of excellent scientific achievements while also showing them the female face of research.

IHP – INTERNATIONAL HYDROLOGICAL PROGRAMME

1975: first multilateral programme for water research and water management – International Hydrological Programme (IHP)

8th IHP, 2014–2021: in its 8th phase, the IHP is devoted to improving water quality while taking into account local, regional, and global challenges

The core of this programme: sustainable water management, promotion and development of international water research, and global networking

Part of the **2030 Agenda**

Role of the ÖUK: information platform for the programme, public relations work

Further information on the 8th phase of implementation:

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The SDGs and Science UNESCO's science programmes make a significant contribution to all of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The natural sciences, technology, and innovation play particularly central roles here, while the social sciences and humanities make their own contributions toward these goals' achievement by bolstering our understanding of current challenges.

UNESCO's natural science programmes make their largest contributions toward the achievement of **SDG 12** (Responsible Consumption and Production), **SDG 15** (Life on Land), and **SDG 13** (Climate Action). The organisation's social sciences and humanities programmes most strongly support the realisation of **SDG 16** (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). All science programmes also make contributions to the realisation of **SDG 5** (Gender Equality) and **SDG 17** (Partnerships for the Goals).

Recipients in 2021:

- Dr. Anna Breger, applied mathematician, University of Vienna
- Alice Laciny, PhD, zoologist, Konrad Lorenz Institute for Evolution and Cognition Research
- Monika Malik, MSc, pharmacist, University of Vienna
- Dipl.-Ing.in Kerstin Rastädter, biotechnologist, TU Wien

The scholarship recipients were formally honoured at a ceremony held in the Großer Festsaal at the Austrian Academy of Sciences on 27th October. Dr. Anton Zeilinger, in his opening address, stressed the importance of female role models in science and research. Thereafter, L'ORÉAL Austria's CEO and Country General Manager Wioletta Rosolowska emphasised the great importance of these scholarships to L'ORÉAL. Dr. Sabine Haag, president of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO, spoke of the significance of women in science and research when it comes to looking for innovative solutions for urgent present-day problems that concern us globally. Federal Minister Dr. Heinz Faßmann was represented at this event by Secretary General Martin Netzer, who pointed out the challenges faced by female researchers due to the current situation and spoke to the importance of far-reaching structural measures aimed at achieving gender justice at university-level educational and research institutions.

• UNITWIN/UNESCO Chairs Programme

In 2021, the "UNESCO Chair in Anticipatory Techniques and Future Design" was established at the University of Art and Design Linz as the tenth such professorial chair in Austria. The chairholder is Univ.-Prof. Dr. Michael Shamiyeh. The chair enables research on new social techniques and abilities pertaining to innovation and leadership that make it possible to open up alternative perspectives, patterns of thought, and patterns of perception. In this regard, a highly important point is action research on present-day processes of transformation in organisations as well as the analytical reappraisal of historical examples.

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IGCP – INTERNATIONAL GEOSCIENCE PROGRAMME

Founded in **1973**

The core of this programme: worldwide scientific collaboration with an emphasis on North-South collaboration; currently focused on applied geosciences, above all with an eye to dealing with natural disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, and volcano eruptions

UNESCO Global Geopark (UGG) label established in **2015**

161 UGGs worldwide, of which **3** are in Austria

In Austria: overseen by the Geo/Hydro Sciences National Committees at the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW) as part of its Earth System Sciences Programme

Role of the ÖUK: central point of contact for the geoparks together with the ÖAW

© G. Šafarek

The Drava in Croatia

So Many Years Without a Major Misstep – Günter Köck and “his” MAB Programme

Biologist Günter Köck can boast around four decades of involvement in a great number of research projects in the field of environmental toxicology. And since 1997, Köck has been spending his summers in the far northern reaches of Canada, where he investigates the effects of environmental pollution and climate change on fish and occasionally also battles wolves as part of an Austrian-Canadian Arctic research project. Less spectacular, perhaps, but no less important is Köck’s second area of professional activity: alongside his research, he has dedicated himself to the coordination of international research programmes. March 2022 saw Köck relinquish some of his functions as he entered semi-retirement. In the following conversation, he takes stock of his professional work within and specifically on behalf of UNESCO’s “Man and the Biosphere” Programme.

Günter, you worked for 18 years at the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW) as coordinator of its Earth System Science programme’s international thematic orientations, as part of which the Man and the Biosphere National Committee and the National Committee for Geo-/Hydrosciences double as the national committees of their respective UNESCO programmes. You’re also

Austria’s delegate to the International Coordinating Council of UNESCO’s Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB-ICC) and have served several times as the UNESCO MAB Programme’s deputy chair. When did you first come into contact with UNESCO and the ÖUK?
It was actually right after I’d assumed my position at the ÖAW in 2004 that I encountered UNESCO, since the seven

national committees we were running at the time included three UNESCO programmes (MAB, IGCP, IHP¹). The ÖUK was, obviously, represented on these national committees. As the 33rd meeting of the MAB International Coordinating Council in Paris in October 2004 drew near, the national committee’s then-chair Georg Grabherr—who knew me and my international orientation on account of my Arctic project, which had already been running for seven years by that point—asked me to represent the national committee in Paris. A bit surprisingly, that meeting saw Austria elected to join the MAB Bureau—and I became a vice-chair of the programme. It should be said, though, that this election was a way of saying thank-you to Austria for its willingness to host the meeting of the EuroMAB² group at the Wienerwald Biosphere Reserve in 2005. That meeting, whose organisation and financing was led by the ÖUK, was a huge success and resulted in even more seamless collaboration between the National Committee and the ÖUK.

UNESCO’s MAB Programme focuses on the relationship between human beings and their environment. And in view of the threats posed by climate change, this programme is now more relevant than ever. But what sets the MAB programme apart? What’s special enough for you to have dedicated so much effort to it?

I’ve already spent many years deeply involved in environmental research at the University of Innsbruck, and I’ve been investigating how climate change influences aquatic ecosystems since 1997 as part of my Austrian-Canadian research project in the Arctic. All this explains why I immediately recognised how special the MAB Programme is: it attempts to reconcile the needs of nature and of human beings.

¹ MAB – Man and the Biosphere; IGCP – International Geoscience Programme; IHP – Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme

² EuroMAB – a group comprised of the biosphere reserve managers and MAB national committees of the “Europe and North America” region that meets biannually

With support from the Austrian MAB National Committee, I got involved in the quality improvement process right at the beginning. This process ran for many years and was only just recently concluded, to no small success. Which brings me to one of this programme's outstanding assets: its ability to transform: Over the 50 years of its existence so far, the programme has never shied away from global challenges such as climate change, and it's been given refinements and adaptations about every 10 years. Thanks to this, it's definitely among UNESCO's premier programmes—and amidst an increasingly imbalanced relationship between human beings and the environment, with climate conferences racing from one compromise to the next, it's never been as necessary as it is today.

Austria, as one of the first countries to have taken part in this programme, set up its MAB National Committee at the ÖAW all the way back in 1972, and Austria has continued to be quite present internationally. What does the programme mean to Austria, and what does Austria mean to the programme?

The MAB Programme offers Austria the opportunity to bring environmental protection, the preservation of biodiversity, and regional development into harmony—putting sustainability into actual practice. The four Austrian biosphere reserves—“Großes Walsertal”, “Salzburger Lungau und Kärntner Nockberge”, “Wienerwald”, and “Unteres Murtal”—are not only established nationally as model regions for sustainable development but also play a pioneering international role in their implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Special mention here is certainly deserved by the management of the Nockberge region, who've been quite deeply involved in the MAB Programme and the World Network of Biosphere Reserves for many years now and will be hosting the EuroMAB Group meeting in September

2022. Also noteworthy is the biosphere reserve Unteres Murtal, which has been part of the world's first trans-border biosphere reserve “Mura-Drava-Danube” since 2021.

Looking back upon your many years' worth of activities: What have been your greatest successes to date? What are your favourite memories? And what will you perhaps end up missing someday?

I'd like to say here that my successes would almost certainly not have been possible without the great trust that Georg Grabherr placed in me from the very beginning. Georg wanted to modernise and reorient the National Committee, I thought that its international orientation was too weak, and we therefore complemented each other perfectly. The experience of working together with his successor Arne Arnberger was likewise outstanding. Speaking about one's own successes is a bit difficult, of course, but there are a few things I'm really proud of. Like the fact that Austria's National Committee and its biosphere reserves now feature a strong international orientation and are quite actively involved in the work of the programme at large. And we've also provided financial support to many activities of the international MAB Programme over the years, funding successful research projects in other countries (such as Peru). Which brings me to what's probably the most important point, to what makes our National Committee fairly unique worldwide: the fact that it had its own research budget from the very beginning. That enabled us to do a whole lot of things, and I hope it will stay that way in the future, as well. The Austrian MAB National Committee has built an outstanding reputation for itself in the international community! And what else? Perhaps the two prizewinning books that I initiated, Planet Austria and the Kochbuch der österreichischen Biosphärenparks [Cookbook of the Austrian Biosphere Reserves], which also attracted quite

a bit of attention in the MAB community. And an example of a fond memory would be of how my international colleagues presented me with a cake for my 60th birthday in front of the audience at the MAB-ICC 2019, and of how the Austrian ambassador to UNESCO took me to lunch with prominent MAB collaborators.

I'll enjoy continuing my work for the international MAB Programme for the time being. But one thing I truly will miss someday is the MAB Programme's wonderful internationality, with its opportunities to get to know so many cultures and ways of thinking, to accept them, and to act accordingly. And something I'm really proud of is that throughout all those years during which I represented Austria in Paris, I managed to commit not a single major political or scientific misstep.

This conversation with Dr. Günter Köck has been condensed to save space. The full interview can be found at www.unesco.at.

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GÜNTER KÖCK is a vice-chair of the MAB Bureau and the rapporteur to the International Man and the Biosphere Coordinating Council of UNESCO as well as a member of the Austrian MAB National Committee at the ÖAW, which he chaired for 18 years. He is also a member of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the Scientific Council of the Hohe Tauern National Park as well as a delegate to the International Scientific Committee for Alpine Research. Furthermore, he is among the founding editors of the scientific journal *eco.mont*, which was established in 2009. As an Arctic researcher, Köck is an associated scientist at the Institute for Interdisciplinary Mountain Research in Innsbruck and an initiator of the Austrian-Canadian Arctic research project “HighArctic”. This long-term project, led by Köck and Derek Muir (Environment and Climate Change Canada), has been studying the influences of changes to the climate on fish from lakes in the Canadian Arctic since 1997.

CULTURE

Culture is the basis of social cohesion and societal advancement. Its diverse forms of expression—from historical architecture to living traditions and on to contemporary art—are fundamental to the sustainable development of our world. UNESCO has dedicated itself to the furtherance of culture on all levels: it works worldwide to promote clear political conditions and legal frameworks for activities in the cultural field, providing support to Member States as well as local civil society protagonists in order to protect cultural heritage and support cultural diversity.

UNESCO'S CULTURAL FOCUSES: CULTURAL DIVERSITY | WORLD HERITAGE | PROTECTION OF CULTURAL PROPERTY | INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE | The working emphases of the Austrian Commission for UNESCO in the cultural field are oriented toward active implementation of UNESCO's seven culture-related conventions. Special attention is paid to promoting the diversity of cultural expressions, to the protection and safeguarding of tangible and intangible cultural heritage, and to the protection of cultural property.

PROTECTING AND PROMOTING DIVERSITY in the Arts and Culture

The *UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* promotes the diversity of cultural expressions as the facilitation of diverse modes of creation, production, dissemination, and distribution of as well as participation in the arts and culture. The core purpose of the Convention is to ensure states the right to independent arts and cultural policy so that the arts and culture shall not be reduced to their economic aspects.

This Convention is the first international legal instrument to recognise that cultural goods and services function as bearers of identity and expressions of values and aesthetic positions. Though they do also carry economic significance as wares and consumable products, their value is not limited to that which can be expressed in financial terms.

In its Article 16, "Preferential Treatment for Developing Countries", the Convention places global structures of inequality and the disadvantaging of the Global South firmly in focus. This provision obligates the Global North to implement measures that support both the mobility of arts and cultural professionals as well as the exchange of cultural goods and services from the Global South.

The Austrian Commission for UNESCO serves as a National Point of Contact for questions regarding the Convention's implementation in Austria. A central concern of the ÖUK is dialogue and cooperation with relevant stakeholders in order to shape favourable structures and overall conditions for cultural diversity in Austria.

Advising and Supporting Bodies

Advisory Panel on Cultural Diversity: supports the ÖUK in the coordination of all matters pertaining to the Convention.

Working Group on Cultural Diversity: dialogue platform for the active involvement of civil society.

The core purpose of the Convention is to ensure states the right to independent arts and cultural policy so that the arts and culture shall not be reduced to their economic aspects.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 8: Decent Work: social and economic security is essential for both artists and cultural workers in order that they may engage in free artistic and creative work. **SDG 10:** Promoting the diversity of cultural expressions goes hand in hand with reducing inequality within and among countries. **SDG 16** and **SDG 17:** A fundamental pillar of the Convention is participation by and partnership with civil society; only in this manner—in the cultural field, as elsewhere—can policies be shaped in a way that is transparent, participative, and needs-oriented.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **Forum Fair Culture**

The event series *Forum Fair Culture* was launched in December 2020 as a collaborative effort between the Austrian Commission for UNESCO and the organisation “kulturen in bewegung”. It opened up space to discuss the obligation to afford preferential treatment in (post-)migrant Austria as well as interconnections with the thematic area of antidiscrimination. Discursive formats questioned what “southern perspectives” actually are, as well as which forms of discrimination, exclusion, and racism play influential roles in Austria. The purpose of preferential treatment is to balance out the existing imbalance between the so-called Global North and South—a process that, in a globalised society, needs to unfold not only between states but also within national borders. Accordingly, preferential treatment—and, associated therewith, development toward greater justice—also applies to community work in Austria, which makes it possible to more closely examine the cultural sector’s actual inclusiveness. The Austrian Commission for UNESCO’s collaboration with “kulturen

in bewegung” made it possible to gain insights into actual practice and take stock of the present situation. A total of four events were held in various live and online formats. The most important findings were published in the form of a booklet.

- **2021 Closed Conference of the Working Group on Cultural Diversity in Graz**

2021 saw the Austrian Commission for UNESCO host a renewed edition of the Closed Conference on Cultural Diversity at Forum Stadtpark in Graz. In a detailed Final Communiqué, the undersigned experts of the Working Group on Cultural Diversity presented their findings concerning the current state of and progress made in implementing the *UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions*. The discussions centred on questions and demands pertaining to the social and economic situation of cultural workers, critiques of discrimination, artistic mobility, and numerous further topics. “In the current deep-reaching crisis, it is radical processes of reconsideration in the political and economic sectors that have become most crucial to survival. Protagonists from the cultural sector are developing feasible visions and indeed already living them. It is high time that such individuals are not only heard but also afforded the standing that they deserve on account of their indispensability. It is hence imperative that a sufficient basis be created upon which arts and cultural professionals can survive in an environment that values their work,” states the preamble of the Final Communiqué.

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CONVENTION on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions

2005 adopted by UNESCO

2006 ratified by Austria

151 States Parties (150 states plus the European Union)

120 projects for the structural reinforcement of cultural creation supported in

62 countries in the Global South by the "International Fund for Cultural Diversity"

166 periodic, publicly available national reports on implementation, including

3 Austrian implementation reports (2012, 2016 and 2020)

Role of the ÖUK: maintaining the Convention's Austrian Point of Contact

ÖUK Priorities: informing and advising, dialogue forums for inter-ministerial coordination and the involvement of civil society, representation of Austria in UNESCO governing bodies on the Convention, public relations work

• Artistic Freedom: The kùltür gemma! Fellowship

Beginning in November 2021, the ÖUK hosted a latest recipient of the six-month kùltür gemma! Fellowship for work on the topic of artistic freedom. This fellowship is worth € 1,300 per month. In keeping with the intentions of kùltür gemma!, it offers an arts or cultural professional who defines him/herself as a migrant or a person of colour the opportunity to develop a project having to do with the theme of artistic freedom. kùltür gemma! fellow Daria Tchapanova used a video project to address the topic of artistic mobility with the objective of using artists' and cultural workers' voices to render barriers to mobility visible. After all: artistic freedom does not necessarily equal freedom of art. The former is far-reaching and also has to do with the mobility of artists and cultural workers. Reality, however, shows that artists from non-EU countries classified as "third country nationals" have difficulty pursuing their work freely in Austria due to bureaucratic and structural challenges.

• Digital Transformations: Fair Culture on the Internet

In 2019, UNESCO published an Open Roadmap for the Implementation of the *Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* in the Digital Environment. This roadmap serves the Parties to the Convention as a benchmark for the Convention's implementation in the digital era. In 2021, furthermore, Laura Wiesböck conducted an analysis on the state of its implementation in Austria for the Austrian Commission for UNESCO. The findings from her analysis, intended to provide the starting point for a National Roadmap in the spirit of the UNESCO Convention, were presented and discussed on 14 December 2021 as part of an expert workshop on the topic of a "Fair Digital Future for the Arts and Culture". The Open Roadmap is aimed primarily at state protagonists, but it is also important to recognise that experts from civil society are already contributing to implementation and that such experts can make a valuable contribution in this regard in the future. Collaboration in the digital environment between protagonists from both the arts and cultural sector and the cultural and creative industry was bolstered by this exchange, thus making a lasting contribution to the further development of measures.

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What it means to decolonize is to restore humanity

Why do we speak of decoloniality? Why do we need decolonial strategies? A conversation between Sara Hassan and Jumoke Sanwo, participants in the Forum Fair Culture, gives insight into the many layers of (post)coloniality

Sara: I have the impression that the term “decolonialization” has become such a trend. All of a sudden, every institution claims to practice it, and everything is intersectional and decolonial. When I hear that claim, I want to dig into that and ask: What is it precisely that you want to do? Do you actually want to work decolonially? Or do you just want to make it look like you do?

Jumoke: That is a really interesting question – we look at decolonization

from the context of our realities. For example, I live in the city of Lagos, West Africa. So therefore, that terminology has a different connotation for me versus somebody else who has a completely different reality. Even within the same geographical construct. The essence is to question what decolonial means. To even begin to have this conversation we must begin from the same premise. What aspect of decolonization are we engaging with? You are in New York, Sara, I am in Lagos.

Colonization of the world at large meant that it had a profound — and still has — a profound influence in how people move, think, and speak.

Sara: Yes! All these layers that you just laid open allow an insight into the multitude of colonial practices. This is what it is truly about. This is what I want to ask people who express that they want to “decolonize” this, that, and the third: Are you truly willing to acknowledge that colonization of the world at large meant that it had a profound — and still has — a profound influence in how people move, think, and speak? When you ask these kinds of questions, the air in the room is getting a little tense, because an anxiety of certain institutions emerges, when realizing that if they sift through all of these layers of imperial violence, at the end of the day there might not be much left. If they really decolonize themselves.

Jumoke: I loved what you just said. Very interesting is also the idea of the urgency to decolonize – where is the urgency coming from?

Sara: Yes. When engaging in decolonial practices and approaches, when it is coming from a hegemonial space, from a space of power, it is often not so much about allowing “the other” person to be the human they are and a person with agency. Within these hegemonial practices the colonized subject is asked to show the colonizer the way out.

Bringing back the artefact in itself does not actually solve anything.

Jumoke: The reality of decolonization is that there are certain steps that need to take place. It has to go through many different stages, and it has not even started. We have all of these conversations ongoing, even in cultural spaces. There is now a drive to repatriate the items that were looted during the imperial project. But the real challenge is, what has happened to culture on the continent? What is the people’s relationship to the artefacts that were taken? Bringing back

the artefact in itself does not actually solve anything. It is an act that would soothe the consciousness of the colonizers, but it has very little impact on the colonized. I am very skeptical about this whole drive for decolonization.

Sara: That is the center of the problem, because it does not restore anything, but it is a prolongation of existing power relationships. You need to start thinking about how justice can be restored.

Jumoke: There is also the economic factor. The artefacts generated income. The value of some of these artefacts have now been transformed into digital assets. If an object has been at a museum for hundreds of years generating revenue, what percentage of the total revenue are you repaying back?

Sara: This is very telling, because the artefacts without the process, the trail and the flow of capital do not mean so much. When we are talking about decolonization, we need to talk money. We need to talk capital.

Jumoke: We want to have true conversations about development, also in cultural spaces, which is a space that I am very much involved in. What sort of economic system is currently affecting the cultural space? The government, local authorities are not investing in culture. What is UNESCO doing about this for example? We have to begin having conversations about the budget ratio that actually goes to cultural development. What about the cultural policy? I think the last update that was done here (in Lagos, Nigeria) was probably in the 1980s or thereabout. How do we ensure that cultural policies are up to date, facing the present and current needs of the community?

Decolonization of the heart

Sara: I am very impressed by, – I guess it is also still my generation – younger activists. They are very articulate, very self-aware, very powerful. But I am sometimes worried that now that we have all these amazing tools, many lenses, many very sharp knives to cut

through all of these levels of systemic oppression, how do we use these tools? Maybe also with each other? How can we truly build collectives where violence is not reproduced? The only way out is to work in collectives and to resist the idea of divide and conquer. Everybody is talking about decolonization of the mind, but sometimes I feel like, what about decolonization of the heart?

Jumoke: Absolutely, I completely agree with you. I think basically what needs to be introduced is the existence of the soul in general in public discourse.

We have programs at Revolving Art Incubator like “Words as therapy”, that have helped people significantly, using poetry as a way of healing, connecting to the core of their humanity. Because at the end of the day you realize, we need to go back to humanity. One of the ways that the imperial project took hold of the continent was the fact that people were considered savages. It took away their humanity and objectified them. Is the North willing to engage with people in the Global South as humans? If they are willing to do that, the interaction changes completely. And we would not even need to have long conversations about what it means to decolonize. What it means to decolonize is to restore humanity to public discourse in the Global North and South. That is all, that is what it means. Just very simple.

The Forum Fair Culture initiative, a joint project of *kulturen in bewegung/VIDC* and the Austrian Commission for UNESCO, opened the space to reflect on power relations in international cultural politics. The organizers of the forum conducted an extensive conversation with Sara Hassan and Jumoke Sanwo, excerpts of which are printed here. The long version of the text can be found in the publication “Critical Diversity - Reflections of the Forum Fair Culture” at www.unesco.at/publikationen.

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SARA HASSAN is a publicist, moderator, podcaster. She has been working in the field of political communication since 2012, most recently specifically at the intersection of political education and knowledge transfer. Hassan produces podcasts with an explicitly anti-racist, intersectional-feminist approach. She is co-author of the 2020 book “Grauzonen gibt es nicht,” a text about abuse of power and how we can recognize the first signs of it. She lived in Brussels for five years, worked there among others for the European Parliament and then started her own business. Today she works as a moderator and gives lectures on the abuse of power.

JUMOKE SANWO is a visual storyteller and cultural producer from Lagos, Nigeria. She holds a Bachelor of Arts (B.A) in English Studies from the Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-ife in Nigeria. As an artist, she works primarily in Photography, Video Art and Virtual Reality. Her work reflects on self-perception and separation experienced through time and space, while rethinking and engaging the discourse on spatiality and temporality in postcolonial societies.

INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE

Creativity, Identity, Continuity

Intangible cultural heritage is everywhere. In many people's lives, some tradition, custom, and/or form of knowledge plays an important role. For some, this may be something like the Traismauer Nativity Play, Manual Graphic Printing, Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen*, or *Gautschen*. These examples have in common their status as part of the intangible cultural heritage to be found in Austria. "Intangible Cultural Heritage" as defined by UNESCO encompasses numerous areas including cultural practices, rituals, experiential knowledge, and masterful craftsmanship. Each such area contains a diversity of traditions that are important to the identities of their practitioners as well as to society at large. The *Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage* (2003), which Austria ratified in 2009, brings precisely this diversity to light. Here, the central focus is on those people who carry forward the knowledge associated with such practices.

© Hans P. Wieland

Historical and Decorative Painting Techniques Using Traditional Materials

The Austrian National Inventory of the Intangible Cultural Heritage

The National Inventory makes the diversity of living cultural heritage visible. It describes not only traditions' processes and content but also traditions' significance to the identity of their bearers, it highlights successful models of dealing with resources, and it provides impulses for sustainable living. The National Inventory was established in 2010, and its currently 147 entries contribute to a better understanding of the astounding diversity of living knowledge and practices to be found in Austria.

An interdisciplinary Advisory Panel on Intangible Cultural Heritage makes regular decisions regarding traditions' inscription on the Austrian Inventory and any nominations of national elements for one of UNESCO's three international lists.

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Gautschen

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Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen* and Wearing of Women's Traditional Dress

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• International Nominations and Inscriptions

On 31 March 2021, Timber Rafting was nominated for inscription on UNESCO's Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. This nomination arose on the basis of international cooperation between timber rafters in Germany, Latvia, Poland, Spain, and the Czech Republic. A prerequisite for this nomination's submission at the international level is the national listing of a corresponding element in each of the participating countries. In Austria, "Knowledge of Timber Rafting on the Upper Drava" has been part of the National Inventory since 2014, with this element of cultural heritage being upheld by 150 rafters, volunteers, and associations.

2021 also featured a focus on traditional irrigation methods. Starting from the element "Meadow Irrigation in Tyrol", Austria coordinated the preparation of a nomination for the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. This multi-national nomination was joined by in by bearers, experts, and NGOs from Belgium, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland. Between December 2020 and March 2021, a series of regular online workshops were held that culminated in a combined meeting for exchange in Zams, Tyrol in October of 2021. There, the participants collaborated on preparing the nomination file and were also introduced to the Tyrolean method of meadow irrigation. Submission of this nomination is planned for March 2022.

• New Admissions to the National Inventory

In 2021, the National Inventory of the Intangible Cultural Heritage in Austria was expanded by 14 traditions that were presented publicly as part of the conferral of certificates held in the village of Obertraun by the Hallstättersee.

- Knowledge of Alpinism and Skills of Mountain and Ski Guides (Austria-wide)
- Traditional Craftsmanship in Gmunden: Pottery Flaming (Upper Austria)
- The Custom Tailoring of Men's Full Evening Dress (Austria-wide)
- *Garnierspenzer*, Hat, and *Steppmieder* (Salzburg)
- *Gautschen* (Austria-wide)
- Historical and Decorative Painting Techniques Using Traditional Materials (Austria-wide)
- Production of Bregenz Forest *Juppen* and Wearing of Women's Traditional Dress (Vorarlberg)
- Nativity Scene Traditions in Austria (Austria-wide)
- Manual Graphic Printing (Austria-wide)
- The Traismauer Nativity Play (Lower Austria)
- Dry Stone Walling (Austria-wide)
- South Bohemian Brass Band Music in Brand-Nagelberg (Lower Austria)
- The Knowledge of Artisanal Millers (Burgenland, Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Salzburg, Styria, Tyrol, Vorarlberg)
- *Anklöpfeln* (Knocking on Doors) in Stans (Tyrol)

© Max Mayrhofer

Conferral of Certificates in Obertraun

© alpsolut / Johannes Mair

Mountain guides at work in the Stubai Alps

© Knize&Comp

The Custom Tailoring of Men's Full Evening Dress

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Intangible Cultural Heritage and Reducing the Effects of Natural Disasters (SDG 11.5) The further development of centuries-old knowledge about dealing with and assessing natural hazards and conditions strengthens the ability to adapt in response to climate-related hazards and natural disasters. “Avalanche Risk Management” (inscription on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, 2018) and “Knowledge of Alpinism and Skills of Mountain and Ski Guides (admitted to the National Inventory in 2021) have been handed down orally and developed further over numerous generations, and they are now also being added to via professionalisation and scientific research. This knowledge, constantly adapted to a changing natural environment, contributes to the ability to deal safely and sustainably with nature in the Alpine region.

- **A Focus on Intangible Cultural Heritage and Education**

The safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage lives from the creative process of transmission from one generation to the next, and it is closely linked with matters of education and outreach.

2021 saw an online workshop held in cooperation with UNESCO, the EU, and the UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet) that introduced educational materials for German-speaking educators. These materials demonstrate how one can go beyond just teaching about ICH to render it graspable by using ICH itself. This workshop also introduced the Austrian project “Teaching and Learning with Living Heritage. Design and Creation of a ‘Glöcklerkappe’”. This presentation was complemented by an additional workshop, held during the autumn, that brought together tradition bearers and teaching personnel for the purpose of exchange concerning possible cooperative efforts.

Screenshot from the introduction of UNESCO’s toolkit for teachers

- **Periodic Report**

The so-called Periodic Report is one of the Convention’s key mechanisms in terms of both national progress and international cooperation. It allows states and communities to benefit from the experiences of other States Parties and to exchange information on effective safeguarding measures and strategies. This report conveys an overall impression of the past few years and highlights Austria’s activities as they relate to the Convention. The present Periodic Report is Austria’s second report concerning the 2003 Convention (the first of which was published in 2015). It reflects the Convention’s implementation to date and lays out a forward-looking way in which to continue. In its report, special attention was paid to the input and feedback of the individual bearers and the various stakeholders on the national, regional, and local levels. Here, the ÖUK functions as a point of coordination.

CONVENTION for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage

- 2003** adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO

- 2009** ratified by Austria

- 180** States Parties

- 529** elements on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity

- 71** elements on the List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Need of Urgent Safeguarding

- 29** proven programmes, projects, and activities aimed at safeguarding intangible cultural heritage

- 147** traditions in the National Inventory of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Austria

Role of the ÖUK: awareness-raising in the interest of safeguarding, conveying, and supporting intangible cultural heritage in Austria; compilation of the National Inventory

Topics for the ÖUK in 2021: inscription of 14 further traditions on the Austrian National Inventory of ICH; emphases: ICH and education; knowledge concerning nature and the universe; international cooperation

• Cooperation with Sudan: Digital National Inventory

The UNESCO project *Strengthening National Capacities for Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage in Sudan* saw the ÖUK, the UNESCO field office in Khartoum, and the Sudanese National Commission for UNESCO collaborate to compile a digital inventory of the intangible cultural heritage of Sudan. The ÖUK prepared the technical foundation for this and also worked closely with national stakeholders in Sudan to guide the project editorially.

Digital inventory of the intangible cultural heritage of Sudan – Website

• International

During 2021, Austria took part in a UNESCO Working Group convened in order to engage in some long-awaited reflection on the international lists. This included discussion of improvements to both the nomination process and the process for removing elements from the international lists as well as discussion of proposals for dealing with the rising number of nominations to all three lists. The discussion outcomes were adopted at the 16th meeting of the Intergovernmental Committee.

The knowledge and practices that have accumulated over time are employed in order to use natural resources sustainably and minimise the effects of climate change. Intangible cultural heritage can contribute to the protection of biological diversity and to ecological sustainability.

© Albert Janssen

Traditional Irrigation in Europe – A Practice that Brings People Together

One of 2021's main themes in the area of intangible cultural heritage was that of traditional irrigation methods. Bearers of relevant traditions from Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland worked together throughout the year to prepare the according nomination to the international Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. But what is traditional irrigation, and why is it important not only to those who practice it but also to the regions where it is practiced? Karina Liechti of the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) provides a glimpse into this important form of intangible cultural heritage, which is held in common by so many countries and people.

witteren, flüxen, rieseln, wassern, fléizen, bevroeien, irriguer par ruissellement, wässru...

The traditional irrigation of interest here is a centuries-old way of bringing water to cultivated plants in the interest of their optimum growth. Practised on both flat and sloping land, it is based on the deliberate use of gravity and on hand-built infrastructure such

as canals and ditches designed to bring water from springs, glaciers, streams, and rivers closer to areas under cultivation. Damming up the water creates spill-over that can then be used to irrigate agricultural land. At the same time, this serves to build up and fertilise soil in a natural manner. This type of irrigation is an elaborate activity based on a huge amount of experience. In Upper Valais (Switzerland),

for example, irrigators use *Wässerplatten* [watering boards], water irons, and slabs of stone to dam up and direct water, which is then “drawn” across the meadows with a *Wasserhau* [watering axe]¹. Then, beneath the meadows, the excess *Zettwasser* has to be guided away. Accomplishing this requires a deep understanding of the landscape, weather conditions, the topography, and the flow of water.

¹ Schweizer R, Rodewald R, Liechti K, Knoepfel P. 2014. Des systèmes d'irrigation alpins entre gouvernance communautaire et étatique – Alpine Bewässerungssysteme zwischen Genossenschaft und Staat. Zurich/Chur: Rüeegg.

Impoundment of water with a watering board

Impoundment of water on the Mals Heath, Italy

...and a whole lot more:

The practice of traditional irrigation goes far beyond simply the provision (i.e., the capture, redirection, and distribution) of water²: it is a complex socio-ecological system in which factors such as a collective form of organisation with established rules concerning the allocation of water, rights, and obligations as well as the constant renewal of knowledge refined over generations and the associated cultural anchoring in local and regional identities and traditions enjoy equal priority. Major tasks

such as the construction of canals are typically organised collaboratively by the affected water-users, who are united in water cooperatives. The allocation of water to the primarily agricultural users is done according to recognised, documented water rights and an established rotation (the so-called *Kehrordnung*; on this, see the excerpt from a historical *Kehrordnung*). Maintenance of the irrigation facilities (water intakes, canals, distribution systems, etc.) is done mostly as a group (and hence referred to as *Gemeinwerk*, or “common work”)³. Today, however, the involvement and

support of public authorities and further organisations is desired and indeed necessary.

Presence in Europe

Traditional irrigation is done in both flat and mountainous areas and is hence present in most European countries, even in Northern Europe. There exists an extremely wide diversity of systems, from traditional to modern, from small to vast, and from vital to deteriorating. As part of a project to inventory traditionally irrigated sites in Europe, it has so far been possible to identify 130 locations where traditional irrigation is documented historically, preserved in the form of landscape relics and cultural relics, or still practiced as a way of working the land⁴. While traditional irrigation was widely employed prior to the invention of modern sprinkler systems and electrical pumps, only a few traditionally irrigated areas have remained so to this day.

The Diverse Functions of Traditional Irrigation

Alongside its primary agricultural significance, traditional irrigation performs a variety of additional functions. Thanks to the construction of canals, locks, and/or water wheels and to slope irrigation, many places saw the emergence of a mosaic of drier and moister sites, areas of high species diversity, and hence a multitude of habitats and landscape qualities. Irrigated landscapes are also viewed as attractive and are hence playing an increasingly prominent role in tourism. In mountainous regions, canals carrying water bring moisture to mountain forests and thereby stabilise the slopes, provide water with which to fight forest fires, and help prevent floods by enabling surface water to be regulated and diverted. Furthermore, often peculiar structures used to feed

Workshop in Zams, October 2021

² Leibundgut C, Kohn I. 2014. “European traditional irrigation in transition part I: Irrigation in times past – a historic land use practice across Europe.” *Irrigation and Drainage*, 63(3), 273–93.

³ ⁴ Leibundgut C, Vonderstrass I. 2016. *Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe Europas*. Langenthal: Merkur.

Excerpt from the historical water regulations of the Niwärsch Water Canal, 1381 (Ausserberg, Switzerland)

The cooperative members of the new water canal Niwärsch, in the presence of the cleric Nycolinus von Mohlhussen of the Diocese of Munich, conclude the following water regulations⁵:

- 1) Johannes Tufecher am Bort is to have the right to the water canal of half a day and half a night. The heirs of the deceased Johannes Mathien von Baltschieder one quarter. Hans, son of the deceased Furer am Ranfte, one quarter. Petrus am Troyen... (list continues; 14-day rotation);
- 2) The water is to go from one to the other, distributed as above;
- 3) It has been decided that if a break in the water canal should occur, no matter on what day or at what hour this may happen, the entitled member shall receive his water as soon as the canal has been repaired;
- 4) He who has a share in this water canal now or in the future must perform his work or pay seven dinars for a day's work in accordance with the magnitude of his obligation. If one should fail to perform his work (...), then the members of the cooperative are entitled to punish the delinquent by replacing him with another with no possibility of objection by the judge or any other;
- 5) Should a break in the water canal occur due to force majeure (...), now or in the future, each member must perform his work in accordance with the share that he holds. He must otherwise pay ten dinars per day's work.

and distribute water, manual labour-intensive traditional irrigation techniques, and common management and use according to longstanding rules and customs are valuable witnesses to a regionally diverse cultural history and building culture. Traditional irrigation is hence of great importance to regional identity, representing a lively and valuable aspect of cultural heritage⁵. Finally, practices of traditional irrigation

provide opportunities for the broad involvement of the non-agrarian population, as well: women and men, children, adolescents, and entire families, people with local roots and migratory backgrounds alike, volunteer to participate in the necessary maintenance work. What's more, traditional irrigation is an interesting object of study—and a traditionally irrigated region is also a place of education for sustainable development.

⁵ Bär R, Liechti K. 2020. Traditionelle Bewässerung – ein Kulturerbe mit Zukunft? Naters/Bern: Einblicke-Ausblicke.

⁶ Wasserverordnung – Neuwerk 1381; übersetzt aus dem Lateinischen am 31. Mai 1981 von Emil Schmid, Pfarrer; aus: SAC Ortsgruppe Ausserberg. 1981. 600 Jahre Wasserleitung Niwärsch 1381–1981, Ausserberg. Visp: nbv Druck.

International Cooperation and Submission to UNESCO

For all of these reasons, still-active communities from seven European countries came together to submit a multilateral nomination for the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. For many years, now, there have been efforts to bring together still-active irrigators and other involved protagonists as well as to reactivate disused irrigation systems. The international exchange that this entails helps to revitalise traditional irrigation, to support protagonists in their work, and to continually augment knowledge. The attendant international cooperation has also made it possible to set up an International Centre for Traditional Irrigation as Cultural Heritage of Europe (IZTB), which is to open in Switzerland in the autumn of 2022.

The nomination, entitled "Traditional Irrigation in Europe: Knowledge, Technique, and Organisation" will be submitted to UNESCO for inscription on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2022. The text above is based in part on the nomination submitted to UNESCO, to which a multitude of individuals from the participating countries have contributed.

© C. Rytter

KARINA LIECHTI studied geography at the University of Bern. She now works as a project head at the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) and as a researcher at the Centre for Development and Environment (CDE) at the University of Bern. Her work focuses on commons, landscape change, and societal transformation processes.

WORLD HERITAGE

Raising Awareness of Outstanding Universal Value

Since 1972, safeguarding the world's common cultural and natural heritage has been the stated objective of the *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World's Cultural and Natural Heritage* (commonly known as the *World Heritage Convention*). Alongside the concrete protection of what are by now 1,154 world heritage sites of

outstanding universal value, this also includes communication and awareness-raising with regard to the responsibilities and obligations of the States Parties that have ratified the Convention. Austria, by ratifying the Convention in 1992, committed to preserving its unique witnesses to cultural and natural history for future generations in the interest of all of humanity.

The role of the Convention, as one of the most important international legal instruments where the protection of cultural property and nature are concerned, is reflected in its near-complete, universal validity: by now, over 194 States Parties have come to recognise the rights and obligations formulated therein. The importance of this global commitment to cooperatively protect our common heritage is made clear by the increasingly numerous threats to these cultural and natural sites. The consequences of the climate crisis, which are by now becoming quite palpable, affect the preservation of world heritage sites just as directly as do continually intensifying economic pressures.

Even if 2021 brought with it numerous instances of relief compared with the previous year, the challenges stemming from the ongoing global health crisis remained considerable. Alongside economic implications that, among other things, have immediate effects on the preservation of World Heritage sites, the accessibility of these cultural and natural monuments was likewise severely reduced. The numerous initiatives undertaken in the virtual realm were only partly capable of replacing the physical experience of these unique places (which was limited for considerable portions of the year) and the associated manifestation of their value.

For Austria, however, this year also included some welcome aspects: alongside successful efforts to deepen cooperation between the Austrian World Heritage sites, the number of these sites increased by two: with the inscription of "Great Spa Towns of Europe" and of "Danube Limes (Western Segment)" as part of the multinational site "Frontiers of the Roman Empire", Austria can now boast 12 World Heritage sites.

© R. Kuhnbe-Strack

CONVENTION Concerning the Protection of the World's Cultural and Natural Heritage

- 1972 adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO
- 1992 ratified by Austria
- 194 States Parties
- 1,154 World Heritage sites worldwide
- 12 World Heritage sites in Austria

Role of the ÖUK: coordinating office of the Austrian World Heritage Site Conference, support, information, and advising

ÖUK priorities: networking of Austrian World Heritage-related entities, World Heritage education, awareness-raising

➤ **Danube Limes World Heritage:** the so-called "Heathens' Gate" (Heidentor) in Carnuntum, Lower Austria numbers among Austria's best-preserved architectural monuments from antiquity and attests to the significance of this ancient city

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 11: The World Heritage Convention contributes to cities' and human settlements' sustainability by calling for the strengthening of efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage (Target 11.4). **SDG 13:** The protection of cultural heritage contributes to strengthening resilience and the capacity to adapt to climate-related hazards and natural disasters (Target 13.1).

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• 1. Austrian World Heritage Day

At the initiative of the ÖUK and based on a resolution of the Austrian World Heritage Site Conference, 18 April 2021 saw all of the Austrian sites observe Austria's first World Heritage Day. Taking after the "International Day of Monuments and Sites" and "International World Heritage Day", the "Austrian World Heritage Day"—a shared day of action organised by the Austrian World Heritage sites—is intended to draw attention to and raise awareness of the exceptional universal value of World Heritage in Austria and worldwide. A website created expressly for World Heritage Day (www.welterbetag.at) now functions as a common web presence of the Austrian World Heritage sites. In keeping with the motto "World Heritage is more...", special events and activities will aim to provide unaccustomed views of the familiar, open up new perspectives, and convey an impression of the work and effort that go into protecting and preserving these unique places. Even if 2021's planned Austrian World Heritage Day programme had to go largely unrealised due to the pandemic situation, this day's broad resonance in the media impressively demonstrated the existing interest in the topic of UNESCO World Heritage.

Further information:
www.welterbetag.at

• Extended 44th Session of the World Heritage Committee (Fuzhou, China; online)

From 16 to 31 July 2021, the World Heritage Committee came together once more after a one-year hiatus due to the pandemic. This session, originally scheduled for the summer of 2020 in Fuzhou, was chaired by China and held virtually for the first time. Physically present on location were only a very small number of individuals representing the UNESCO Secretariat. This session was of interest to Austria for multiple reasons. Following the successful inscription of "Great Spa Towns of Europe" (which includes the town of Baden, just south of Vienna), the long-running nomination process for "Frontiers of the Roman Empire – Danube Limes (Western Segment)" was likewise brought to a positive conclusion. Regarding the World Heritage site

"Historic Centre of Vienna", which has been on the List of World Heritage in Danger since 2017, the Committee's positive confirmation of the "Desired State of Conservation" (DSOCR) represented an important step.

• 16th Austrian World Heritage Site Conference (Schönbrunn)

The Austrian World Heritage Site Conference is the most important national forum for cooperation between what are now twelve Austrian World Heritage sites.

From 13 to 14 October 2021, the 16th Austrian World Heritage Site Conference—which had been postponed from the year before—was held in cooperation with the World Heritage site "Palace and Gardens of Schönbrunn". With its theme of "More than a Monument: Monument Protection and Care in the Context of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention", the conference facilitated important discussions addressing the thematic complexes around caring for architectural and horticultural monuments and the handling of buffer zone management. A concluding panel discussion specified types of action that need to be taken in order to successfully protect World Heritage in the future.

Panel discussion

© Stadt Baden/Fürnkranz

Significant elements of this serial World Heritage site are historic baths, such as the former Josefsbad in Baden

Baden as Part of the UNESCO World Heritage Site “The Great Spa Towns of Europe”

On 24 July 2021, “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (GSTE) were inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. And with that, Austria—in what was a surprise to many—became home to a new World Heritage location: the town of Baden, just south of Vienna.

The Path to World Heritage

On 24 July 2021, “The Great Spa Towns of Europe” (GSTE) were inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. And with that, Austria—in what was a surprise to many—became home to a new World Heritage location: the town of Baden, just south of Vienna. It was around the end of the 1990s that a number of spa towns simultaneously

voiced the desire to be inscribed on the UNESCO List. The World Heritage Centre in Paris advised them to attempt a serial nomination. In 2012, ICOMOS Germany compiled a thematic study¹ that came to positive conclusions regarding the spa town phenomenon’s potential for successful nomination. For the development of the nomination documents and a common structure for the serial sites as well as for the purpose of coordinating the process, the participating states and cities then set up multiple working groups on the multinational and multicomunal levels: the International Steering Group and the International Working Group with ministry representatives and academics from the various states, the Mayor Steering Group consisting of municipal-level political representatives, and the Site Manager Group with experts from the various spa towns. The overall process was coordinated by a Secretariat-General staffed by Great Britain. The Lead Partner in this nomination process was the Czech Republic.

In 2013, the UNESCO World Heritage Focal Point of the Republic of Austria listed the City of Baden near Vienna, among other places, as a possible candidate for GSTE. 2014 and 2015 saw the International Working Group

develop selection and elimination criteria for the participation of spa towns in the GSTE nomination that ultimately resulted in the list of components since entered into the UNESCO World Heritage List. Between 2016 and 2018, the property borders and buffer zones were defined, the nomination dossier was authored, thematic maps and atlases were compiled, property and local management plans were developed, and cooperation between the various towns was placed on solid foundations. January 2019 then saw all documents submitted to the World Heritage Centre in Paris, after which they were inspected by ICOMOS.

Recognition of GSTE as UNESCO World Heritage

With the pandemic having forced 2020’s planned 44th Meeting of the World Heritage Committee to be cancelled, the Committee’s decision came only a year later. It was thus that on 24 July 2021, the “outstanding universal value” of the GSTE was officially recognised:

The Great Spa Towns of Europe embody an exceptional testament to the European spa phenomenon that experienced its heyday between ca. 1700 and the 1930s. This transnational serial “site” encompasses eleven spa towns in seven countries: Baden bei Wien (AT); Spa (BE); Karlovy Vary, Františkovy Lázně and Mariánské Lázně (CZ); Vichy (FR); Bad Ems, Baden-Baden, and Bad Kissingen (DE); Montecatini Terme (IT); and the City of Bath (UK). This series of towns comprises the most modern, most dynamic, and most international among the hundreds of spa towns that contributed to this European cultural phenomenon.

Although every spa town is structured differently, all such towns have in common their development around mineral water springs that catalysed a spatial model of organisation devoted to healing, therapeutic, recuperative, and social functions. Ensembles of spa buildings include bathhouses, pump rooms,

¹ ICOMOS, National Committee of the Federal Republic of Germany: Europäische Kurstädte und Modebäder des 19. Jahrhunderts; ICOMOS Deutschland Hefte LII 1. Auflage Stuttgart 2012.

drinking halls, facilities for therapeutic treatments, and colonnades and galleries designed to harness the natural mineral water resources and to allow their practical use for bathing and drinking. External and internal treatments (“taking the cure”) were complemented by physical exercise and social activities necessitating facilities like assembly halls, casinos, theatres, hotels, villas, and their attendant infrastructure (ranging from water distribution systems and salt production facilities to railways and funiculars).

All of these facilities are integrated into an overall context of urban planning that encompasses a carefully managed recreational and therapeutic environment comprised of parks, gardens, promenades, athletic facilities, and woods. Buildings and rooms connect visually and physically with the surrounding landscape, which is used regularly for athletic activities that contribute to therapeutic treatments, relaxation, and general enjoyment.

GSTE Local Management, Baden bei Wien

Baden has a long tradition of safeguarding its architectural heritage. And while its inscription on the World Heritage list does further heighten the moral obligation to treat this heritage with care, it entails hardly any need to adjust the regulations that already protect this historic spa town. World Heritage is cross-cutting material. In keeping with this fact, the local management plan envisions the involvement of all levels of Baden’s civil society, political decision-making, and administration. The mayor represents Baden on the GSTE Management Board and also heads local World Heritage site management. Operative implementation is the responsibility of a local site manager and the executive city councillor chosen to handle World Heritage issues. A local steering committee consisting of municipal politicians and administrators, stakeholders, and members of the

The urban architecture of the “Great Spa Towns of Europe” is characterised not only by bath and spa facilities, but also by extensive cultural infrastructure such as theatres

Expert Panel on World Heritage will work to further deepen the sense of responsibility for this World Heritage among decision-makers and society at large. Said Expert Panel consists of individuals specialised in the thematic areas relevant to the site’s “outstanding universal value” (OUV). And furthermore, structures are to be created that enable broad involvement of the local populace and stakeholders in World Heritage management.

... not a monument, but a whole philosophy

Eight years of close collaboration have welded the eleven cities’ representatives into an active, forward-looking community that transcends linguistic boundaries and national borders. Management is accompanied by national state representatives as well as by a complex structure representing the eleven GSTE cities and presided over by these cities’ democratically elected mayors. The aforementioned secretariat-general and eleven local site management organisations are charged with monitoring, reporting on, and implementing the management plans. Cooperative programmes have been quick to develop in the areas of tourism, spa medicine, and cultural and youth exchange. Other project ideas are currently being examined.

Cooperation between the local site

managers is being deepened. On questions having to do with monitoring, researching the spa towns’ urban and natural landscapes, and the harmonisation of management objectives, meetings and online workshops are being held on an ongoing basis.

The GSTE, comprising eleven lively spa towns, represent a complex and exceptional piece of world heritage but also an outstanding example of the European spirit and intermunicipal cooperation across national borders. It has given rise to a strong league of cities that is willing and able to ensure its common interests and common heritage and to promote sustainable development.

HANS HORNYIK has worked as a civil servant for the Province of Lower Austria since 1980; his work currently involves both the Building Culture and UNESCO World Heritage sites. Hornyik studied communication science and sinology in Vienna and in Taipei from 1985 to 1999. He has been a city councillor of the City of Baden since 2000 and an executive city councillor since 2005 (with responsibility for building from 2005 to 2010, for culture from 2010 to 2020, and for planning since 2020). He has also been the City of Baden’s “UNESCO World Heritage” appointee since 2013.

PROTECTION OF CULTURAL PROPERTY

Bringing Witnesses to the Past into the Future

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CONVENTION on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property

1970 adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO

2015 ratified by Austria

141 States Parties

THE HAGUE CONVENTION for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict

1954 adopted in The Hague; expanded by the Second Protocol in 1999

1964 ratified by Austria

133 States Parties

Role of the ÖUK: provision of support, advising and public relations work; founding member and board member of Blue Shield Austria

ÖUK priorities: support of implementation, participation in the Cultural Property Panel, awareness-raising activities

Beginning with the *Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict*, the period since 1954 has seen UNESCO adopt four conventions under international law aimed at protecting movable and immovable cultural property. In particular, the *Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property*, which celebrated 50 years of existence in 2020, is now increasingly in focus due to the global effects of the illicit cultural property trade.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

• Cultural Property Panel

It was in order to network the various protagonists who deal with aspects of protecting cultural property at the national level, especially in the context of the Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property (1970), that Austria's Federal Ministry Of The Interior (BMI) formed its Cultural Property Panel. 2021 once again saw the ÖUK participate in this forum together with other relevant institutions—above all the Federal Ministry of Arts and Culture, Civil Service and Sport (BMKÖS), the Austrian Federal Office for the Care of Monuments (BDA), ICOM Austria, and Blue Shield Austria—in order to support the Convention's implementation.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 13: The protection of cultural property correlates directly with strengthening the resilience and the capacity to adapt to climate-related hazards and natural disasters (Target 13.1). **SDG 16:** The implementation of the UNESCO Convention supports the recovery and return of stolen assets, in particular cultural property, and thus combats organised crime and helps to reduce illicit financial flows (Target 16.4).

COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION

In its efforts pertaining to Communication and Information, UNESCO promotes the development of modern knowledge societies by working to support freedom of opinion and freedom of the press, the development of independent media, and universal access to knowledge and information. In doing so, sustainably preserving and providing access to documents of all kinds—books, manuscripts, photos, films, and audio media—is essential and hence the focus of UNESCO’s Memory of the World programme.

DOCUMENTARY HERITAGE / MEMORY OF THE WORLD PROGRAMME

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 4: Inclusive and equitable quality education can be ensured only if knowledge and information are sustainably preserved and passed on. Democratic access to knowledge and information contributes to gender equality (**SDG 5**) and to the reduction of inequality within and among countries (**SDG 10**). **SDG 9:** Access to knowledge and information also serves to foster scientific and technical innovation.

An important precondition for access to information is the preservation of documents. As carriers of information, documents ensure knowledge transfer, facilitate communication, and form the basis of what we know about historical processes and pasts. In doing so, history's important written works and documents of everyday life are of equally central significance. All of them contribute to the foundation upon which our knowledge and information society stands.

The challenges involved in their preservation are manifold: in addition to the classic problems of physical deterioration, questions of digital storage and preservability are now likewise of the highest relevance. How, for example, do we

ensure the transfer of information stored on data media for which playing and/or reading devices no longer exist?

UNESCO's "Memory of the World" programme, founded in 1992, deals with precisely those themes that are relevant to the preservation of documents—and its International Register helps make visible the documentary heritage of humanity. At the national level, the "Memory of the World" National Committee, which also serves the Austrian Commission for UNESCO as the Advisory Panel on Information Preservation, deals with this complex of themes and maintains the national register "Memory of Austria". This register encompasses and serves to make visible documentary holdings that are of significance to Austria.

A particularly important event for the programme in 2021 was the resolution of a multi-year conflict at the international level that had led to a halt on activities regarding the international register and, consequently, Austria's national register.

SELECTED ACTIVITIES, 2021

- **Working Group on Restructuring the Advisory Panel on Information Preservation / Memory of the World National Committee**

Since 2011, the Memory of the World National Committee has been anchored at the Austrian Commission for UNESCO as an independent advisory panel. Alongside experts from the realms of archiving, history, and document preservation, it also includes representatives of relevant institutions and ministries. In order to react appropriately to current issues and questions, 2021 saw a working group set up that has since been collaborating with outside experts in the development of recommendations for a substantive reorientation as well as an expansion in terms of personnel. This working group has so far urged that regional-level protagonists be involved to a greater extent and that consideration be given to the thematic areas of digitisation and digital humanities as well as restoration, recommendations that were subsequently realised via the restructuring and expansion of the Advisory Panel / National Committee.

MEMORY OF THE WORLD PROGRAMME

Preservation of and Access to Documentary Heritage

1992 programme founded

2014 Initial inscriptions on Austria's National Memory of the World Register; now 59 entries

427 inscriptions on the International Memory of the World Register

15 of these from Austria

59 inscriptions on the Austrian National Register

Role of the ÖUK: administrative support of the National Committee, compilation of the National Register, awareness-raising.

ÖUK priorities: support of the National Committee, submission of international nominations, keeping and maintaining Austria's National Register

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Final document of the Congress of Vienna, 1815

© Österreichisches Staatsarchiv

Augsburg Confession ("Confessio Augustana"), 1530

“It won’t make you famous” – A Conversation on UNESCO’s Memory of the World Programme

After many years leading the Memory of the World National Committee, Dr. Dietrich Schüller is handing over its chairmanship to Thomas Just. In this conversation with the ÖUK, the two provide a look at their personal approaches to the topic of documentary heritage.

Dr. Schüller, you’ve been accompanying the “Memory of the World” (MoW) programme for many years, now—decades, in fact. How did you first encounter the programme?

I was a member of the Advisory Panel on Cultural and Communication Research under the chairmanship of Kurt Blaukopf, who was also a member of the UNESCO Executive Board. I’ve also been representing Austria in the General Conference as an expert since 1989. Before that, I’d been very actively involved in the establishment of the Technical Committee at the International Association of Sound and Audiovisual Archives. It was in the context of all this that I encountered the Memory of the World Programme, which was founded in 1992. “Digitisation” was already an oft-used buzzword in the early 1990s. But back then, it wasn’t yet so much about “born-digital documents”—it was more about providing easy access

to especially valuable and for the most part fragile documents that were inaccessible otherwise. But at the General Conference of UNESCO in 1993, I somewhat rebelliously demanded a more comprehensive concept, saying that we need digitisation not only to ease access but also—and above all—in order to preserve audiovisual documents over the long term. As far as such documents go, it was clear even back then: digitisation is the only way in which they can be preserved for posterity. With documents of the sort, it’s the case that the digital surrogate must take the place of the original because neither the original nor the player devices can be preserved in the long run. This led to the invitation to form a working group, the Technical Subcommittee for MoW, which is now called the Preservation Subcommittee. And in 2015, I was also made a member of the International Advisory Committee.

Mr. Just, it was two decades later that you became a member of the MoW National Committee. In your function as Director of the Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv at the Austrian State Archives, you deal with the topic of document preservation on a daily basis. How is this UNESCO programme relevant from your perspective?

Just: Archives in countries like Austria are of course fortunate to have relatively rich holdings. But with our large volume of old materials, we do face the challenge of bringing it all into the digital world—because, for one thing, this content is in demand. And we also want to do so because we’d otherwise become less relevant—and this relevance is very important to us, since it makes the ministries to which we report aware of how we’re actually about a whole lot more than just important anniversaries. The other reason is that, as Dietrich

Audio recordings documenting Austrian dialects, 1951–1983

Schüller said, it's our job to preserve things. And in the context of documentary heritage, digitisation is among the options for doing so. Now it's indeed the case that we've long been producing exclusively digital data. But the significance of Austria's archives lies above all in Austria's history, in connection with which there's just so much material that needs to be digitised. So in this respect, it's important to have an Advisory Panel like ours that acts to warn—with an eye to ensuring that this information is preserved and transformed for a new era.

The MoW Programme has gone through several changes over the course of its existence and has also been pitted against challenges, not least due to the international difficulties that brought its Register to a standstill. What do you think about how the programme's developed?

Schüller: I've got to be careful, here. There exists a fundamental problem, namely overemphasis of the Register compared with the actual programme. And I have no qualms about saying this quite loudly, because I was among those who were calling vehemently for the international register and for the recognition of special documents during the mid-1990s. I remember there being a long debate, but only one true opponent: the Secretary-General of the International Council of Archives...

Just: ...That will have been Albada—Joan van Albada.

Schüller: Right. And it turned into a vigorous discussion that ultimately saw the Register's proponents prevail. Albada's stance was that it's impossible to put documents in a hierarchy: a note on a slip of paper, he said, was just as important as the Golden Bull. The majority, on the other hand, viewed a Register as being an indispensable tool for encouraging documents' preservation. But Albada insisted that there

And there literally doesn't exist any document that one could consider more important or less important: the certificate of registration is indeed just as important as the Golden Bull.

were no documents that were "better" or "worse". In any case, the International Register has been a blockbuster ever since its initial inscriptions in 1997—thereby papering over the true purpose of the Memory of the World Programme, which is to encourage States Parties to preserve and expand their holdings of documents and ensure that every document remains accessible to everyone. And there literally doesn't exist any document that one could consider

more important or less important: the certificate of registration is indeed just as important as the Golden Bull.

So the core of this programme is the safeguarding of all documents and not the Register. Mr. Just, you've now assumed the position of chair, and your main job is as the head of an important institution in the field. What are the challenges—as well as the opportunities—that lie ahead when it comes to protecting and preserving our documentary heritage?

Just: This is a question that's both easy and difficult. The one thing is that the documents we produce today are way more fragile than those we've already been holding for a thousand years. Digital documents probably need more attention and care than, say, a parchment document; we know how to store the latter, but in the case of the digital document, we only think we know how. The other thing is getting through to policymakers and raising their awareness—not only of how this Register is a great thing, but also about how even a resident registration certificate is a great thing. Perhaps we should put such a certificate on the list someday—to show how even an inconspicuous object can be so interesting and unbelievably revealing in terms of the information it contains. One essential goal of the Advisory Panel will need to be to advance the National Register and generate more public attention for it. And out in the Austrian provinces, for instance, there are some really great objects. Not everything happens in Vienna, after all!

Dr. Schüller, you're stepping down as chair of the National Committee—but you will, thankfully, be remaining a member. Based on your many years of experience: where do you think the programme is headed, both nationally and internationally?

Schüller: It's only starting now that we'll be getting an inkling of where things will go. On the international level, we've

been through a four-year reform process that had to do mainly with the Register. It was touched off by nominations that were made with the purpose of revealing such things as war crimes but were unacceptable for the states thus addressed. This led to things including clear financial threats. To put it very neutrally: the MoW Programme was beginning to do damage to UNESCO because of the disquiet thus caused¹.

How will the programme develop? At present, we can't yet say. If things continue going well, then the Register will run on quietly and no longer evoke substantial conflict. I'll still be a member of the International Advisory Committee until 2023, and as one of my final efforts there, I'm pushing very hard to have significantly more attention paid to basic training in the preservation of documents. It ultimately comes down to: How do I keep something like an audio-tape? It needs to be digitised; otherwise, its content will be lost because we won't have any more player devices! On the other hand, I don't need to worry much about the papyrus collections if I keep them at their proper temperature and protect them against humidity, hungry insects, etc. In between, there are a thousand different shades of nuance. It's there that I, personally, perceive to be the greatest amount of necessary work—and I hope that it will be possible to tackle these none-too-attractive things in a more thorough manner. It won't make you famous...

Just (laughing): ...but it will end up making you pretty unpopular along the way.

Mr. Just, in closing: What pops into your head when you hear the name Dietrich Schüller?

Just: I think of a very dedicated person who's eager to be of help and who's been the motor behind this Advisory Panel as well as the entire programme here in Austria for several decades.

And I think it's quite safe to say that you've created some huge boots for us all to fill, in which we're now attempting to take some baby steps.

Schüller: I'm just an emotional person who doesn't like holding his tongue. And it appears as if that combination hasn't been entirely unsuccessful over my years of dealing with these topics.

Just: It's speaking up that's crucial here, in fact. We can't very well champion our concerns—safeguarding cultural property, safeguarding documents—if we don't speak about them. Dietrich Schüller has done a great job of that his entire life long: he's talked lots about it and achieved quite a bit by doing so. And we

Like when I think of how one can now do genealogical research at the computer in the comfort of one's own home [...] that's a perfect example of how the protection of cultural property and digitisation have had an impact that people notice right away.

should continue doing that, too. Austria has been a pioneer in a number of areas. Like when I think of how one can now do genealogical research at the computer in the comfort of one's own home by looking through all those church registers on the Internet ... that's a perfect example of how the protection of cultural property and digitisation have had an impact that people notice right away. It's all well and good if I can view the Golden Bull online, but being able to search for my own relatives connects me with the topic in an entirely different way.

Dr. Schüller: What are your wishes for this programme and for the Advisory Panel?

I'm happy about one thing above all: we've gone through a process of rejuvenating and diversifying our membership, including in terms of topography. I'm very optimistic that this will help drive the programme forward with even more vigour and also help us raise its visibility. It's really important that the members themselves be actively involved in the goings-on, as opposed to what's been the case more recently, where we've had far more "wise old sages". While it can make a lot of sense to have such people on board, they can't be the driving force. And in this respect, there's not a doubt in my mind that under Thomas Just and the now-rejuvenated Advisory Panel, we'll be seeing a new dynamic that really can be put to work to acquire the means necessary for pursuing our mission.

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© Just

DIETRICH SCHÜLLER studied technical physics at the Technische Hochschule in Vienna (today's TU Wien) from 1957 to 1959 and then switched subjects to pursue ethnology and comparative musicology at the University of Vienna, where he earned his PhD in 1970. From 1972 to 2008, he served as Director of the Phonogrammarchiv at the Austrian Academy of Sciences. He also was and still is a member of numerous national and international bodies, and he has authored approximately 200 publications focusing on sound recordings as sources in research, on phonographic field research, and on the storage, conservation, and restoration of audiovisual documents. He has also pursued broad-based teaching, research, and consulting activities in the aforementioned fields and beyond.

THOMAS JUST studied history in Vienna and is a member of the Institute of Austrian Historical Research. In 2001, he was hired by the Austrian State Archives after having worked for the Municipal and Provincial Archives of Vienna, for the City of Vienna's urban archaeology unit Stadtarchäologie Wien, and for Austria's national broadcaster ORF. Since 2009, he has headed the Austrian State Archives' "Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv" department as its director.

¹ On this, see also the contribution by Ambassador Claudia Reinprecht in the 2020 ÖUK Annual Report, accessible at www.unesco.at.

MEDIA AND PRESS FREEDOM

UNESCO is the most important UN organisation with a mandate to protect the freedom of expression. In this context, press freedom and the safety of journalists are just as central as is gender equality in the media landscape. Furthermore, UNESCO runs initiatives that address media- and information-related skills as well as train journalists, and it also supports specific media projects through the International Programme for the Development of Communication (IPDC). In this way, the organisation contributes to the development of inclusive knowledge societies characterised by access to information and (digital) technologies for all people. To this end, a significant role is also played by the ethical development and use of those new technologies to whose influence societies are increasingly subject. Algorithms, for example, can limit freedom of opinion and ease the spread of misinformation and disinformation. Such misleading or false information represents a not insignificant danger to democratic processes, and it also undermines social solidarity. A free, independent, and pluralistic media landscape in print, broadcast, and digital media can counteract this and contribute to peace, sustainability, the fight against poverty, and human rights.

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[...] a significant role is also played by the ethical development and use of those new technologies to whose influence societies are increasingly subject.

Relevance to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Press freedom is relevant above all to aspects of **SDG 16**: Substantially reduce corruption and bribery in all their forms / Develop effective, accountable, and transparent institutions at all levels / Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements.

Safety of Journalists

Contributing to the safety of journalists is a core element of UNESCO's work in the area of press freedom. On average and worldwide, every day sees one journalist killed in connection with practicing their profession. However, kidnappings, harassment, intimidation, and illegal and arbitrary imprisonment likewise number among the serious problems that this occupational group faces on a regular basis all over the world. In this regard, it is especially conspicuous that crimes committed against journalists frequently go unpunished. UNESCO contributes to making this situation visible in that the currently serving director-general has publicly condemned every single murder of a journalist since 1997. Furthermore, the period since 2008 has seen a report on the safety of journalists published every two years for consideration by the Intergovernmental Council of the Programme for the Development of Communication (IPDC).

UNESCO / Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom Prize

This prize, which is worth USD 25,000, honours exceptional contributions to the defence, upholding, and expansion of press freedom. It is named for the Colombian journalist Guillermo Cano Isaza, who was murdered outside the headquarters of his newspaper *El Espectador* in 1986. The prize is sponsored by the Guillermo Cano Isaza Foundation (Colombia), the Helsingin Sanomat Foundation (Finland), and the Namibia Media Trust.

In 2021, in accordance with the recommendation of an international jury of experts, the UNESCO / Guillermo Cano World Press Freedom Prize was awarded to the Philippine investigative journalist and media manager Maria Ressa. This prize hence goes to a journalist from a region that is especially severely affected by violence against journalists: according to UNESCO's monitoring, 112 journalists have been murdered in the Philippines since 1993.

The many years of Maria Ressa's career have included work as the lead investigative reporter for CNN in the Asian region, and she has also led the News and Current Affairs Division of the Philippine television and online network ABS-CBN. She has additionally involved herself in numerous international initiatives aimed at safeguarding press freedom. Recent years have seen her become a target of online attacks as well as legal persecution, especially in connection with her activities as CEO and editor-in-chief of the Philippine online news portal Rappler. Ressa and her business

partners have been accused of tax evasion as well as omissions from tax filings, accusations that they have always denied and that may have been made in retaliation to a critical report on a Philippine businessman. At the same time, she became the target of a hate campaign that culminated in her receipt of an average of over 90 hate messages per hour via Facebook.

Ressa has already received numerous awards in the past, including the Golden Pen of Freedom Award of the World Association of Newspapers and News Publishers (2018), the Gwen Ifill Press Freedom Award of the Committee to Protect Journalists (also 2018), and the Tucholsky Prize of the Swedish branch of PEN International (2020). 2021 also saw her awarded the Nobel Peace Prize together with the Russian journalist Dmitry Muratov.

Maria Ressa 2015

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APPENDIX

THE AUSTRIAN COMMISSION FOR UNESCO

Under Section 2 of its statutes, the Austrian Commission for UNESCO serves as a National Commission pursuant to Article VII of the Charter of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO). Its activities are of a non-profit nature.

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Youth Advisory Panel

Advisory Panel on Cultural Diversity

Working Group on Cultural Diversity

Advisory Panel on Intangible Cultural Heritage

Advisory Panel on Information Preservation/Memory of the World National Committee

AUSTRIAN WORLD HERITAGE SITES

1996 **Historic Centre of the City of Salzburg**

1996 **Palace and Gardens of Schönbrunn**

1997 **Hallstatt-Dachstein/Salzkammergut Cultural Landscape**

1998 **Semmering Railway**

1999 **City of Graz – Historic Centre and**

2010 **Schloss Eggenberg**

2000 **Wachau Cultural Landscape**

2001 **Historic Centre of Vienna**

2001 **Fertő/Neusiedler See Cultural Landscape** (jointly with Hungary)

2011 **Prehistoric Pile Dwellings Around the Alps** (jointly with France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Switzerland)

2017 **Ancient and Primeval Beech Forests of the Carpathians and Other Regions of Europe** (jointly with Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Italy, Austria, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and Ukraine), with Austrian properties in the Dürrenstein Wilderness Area (Lower Austria) as well as in the Kalkalpen National Park (Upper Austria).

2021 **Great Spa Towns of Europe** (jointly with Belgium, Germany, France, Great Britain, Italy and Czech Republic)

2021 **Frontiers of the Roman Empire – Danube Limes (Western Segment)** (jointly with Germany and Slovakia)

AUSTRIAN BIOSPHERE RESERVES

2000 **Großes Walsertal**, Vorarlberg

2005 **Vienna Woods**, Vienna / Lower Austria

2012 **Lungau/Nockberge**, Salzburg/Carinthia

2019 **Lower Mura Valley**, Styria, The world's first 5-country biosphere reserve (Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Hungary, and Serbia)

AUSTRIAN UNESCO GEOPARKS

2004 **Styrian Eisenwurzen**

2013 **Karawanken/Karavanke**
(together with Slovenia)

2014 **Ore of the Alps**

INSCRIPTIONS ON THE REPRESENTATIVE LIST OF THE INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE OF HUMANITY

2012 **Falconry**, a Living Human Heritage
(multinational nomination by altogether 18 states)

2012 **Schemenlaufen, the carnival of Imst**

2015 **Classical Horsemanship and the High School of the Spanish Riding School Vienna**

2017 **Resist Block Printing and Indigo Dyeing in Europe** (multinational nomination with Germany, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Hungary)

2017 **Avalanche Risk Management**
(bilateral nomination with Switzerland)

2019 **Transhumance – the Seasonal Droving of Livestock along Migratory Routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps** (multinational nomination with Greece and Italy)

INSCRIPTIONS ON THE INTERNATIONAL ICH REGISTER OF GOOD SAFEGUARDING PRACTICES

2016 **Regional Centres for Craftsmanship: a strategy for safeguarding the cultural heritage of traditional handicraft**

2020 **Craft techniques and customary practices of cathedral workshops, or Bauhütten, in Europe, know-how, transmission, development of knowledge and innovation**

AUSTRIAN UNESCO “CREATIVE CITIES”

2011 **Graz – “City of Design”**

2014 **Linz – “City of Media Arts”**

AUSTRIAN ENTRIES IN THE MEMORY OF THE WORLD REGISTER

1997 **Vienna Dioscurides**
Austrian National Library

1997 **Final Document of the Congress of Vienna 1815**, Austrian State Archives

1999 **Historical Collections (1899–1950)**
Audiovisual Research Archives of the Austrian Academy of Sciences

2001 **Papyrus Erzherzog Rainer**
Austrian National Library

2001 **Schubert Collection**
Vienna City Library

2003 **Atlas Blaeu-Van der Hem**
Austrian National Library

2005 **Brahms Collection**
Vienna Society of Friends of Music

2005 **Collection of Gothic Architectural Drawings**, Academy of Fine Arts, Vienna

2005 **Bibliotheca Corviniana**
Austrian National Library (jointly with Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, and Italy)

2007 **Tabula Peutingeriana**
Austrian National Library

2011 **Arnold Schönberg Estate**
Arnold Schönberg Center

2011 **Mainz Psalter**
Austrian National Library

2013 **The “Golden Bull”**, Austrian State Archives (jointly with Germany)

2017 **Philosophical Nachlass of Ludwig Wittgenstein** (jointly with Great Britain, Canada, and the Netherlands)

2017 **Historical Documents on the Semmering Railway**
Vienna Technical Museum

AUSTRIAN UNESCO CHAIRS

UNESCO Chair in Intercultural and Inter-religious Dialogue for South-East Europe, established in 2007, University of Graz, Faculty of Catholic Theology | Occupant: Pablo ARGÁRATE

UNESCO Chair for Peace Studies, established in 2008, University of Innsbruck | Occupant: Wolfgang DIETRICH

UNESCO Chair in Cultural Heritage and Tourism, established in 2011, University of Salzburg, Department of Communication Science, Transcultural Communication | Occupant: Kurt LUGER

UNESCO Chair on Integrated River Research and Management, established in 2014, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences | Occupant: Helmut HABERSACK

UNESCO Chair in Human Rights and Security, established in 2015, University of Graz | Occupant: Gerd OBERLEITNER

UNESCO Chair for Bioethics, established 2015, Medical University of Vienna | Occupant: Christiane DRUML

UNESCO Chair on Conservation and Preservation of Tangible Cultural Heritage, established in 2019, University of Applied Arts Vienna | Occupant: Gabriela KRIST

UNESCO Chair for Global Citizenship Education – Culture of Diversity and Peace, established in 2020, University of Klagenfurt | Occupant: Hans Karl PETERLINI

UNESCO Chair for Sustainable Management of Conservation Areas, established in 2020, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences Klagenfurt | Michael JUNGMEIER

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As of 2021, Austria has 96 UNESCO Associated Schools

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Tombstone of T. Calidius Severus,

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This important first-century find bears witness to ancient Roman life at the Danube Limes. The western segment of the Danube Limes was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List as a transnational site in 2021.

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